

Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients, Triangular Numbers and Square-Root

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Abstract

By *selfie numbers*, we understand that the numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations, such as, *basic operations, factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, etc.* These are by use of single variable. In two variables, we worked with *binomial coefficients type selfie numbers with basic operations, factorial and square-root.* This paper brings *binomial coefficient triangular type selfie numbers, i.e., binomial coefficients and triangular numbers together.* This is done by use of only *basic operations and square-root.* The work is in *digit's order and in reverse order of digits.* The work is up to 5-digits numbers.

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(i) Consider the following classical number famous as **printer's error** (Dudeney, 1917, pp. 379 [5]):

$$2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2 \quad (1)$$

Actually it is not a **printer's error**, it a represents number in its own digits. The first number similar property is $25 = 5^2$, but is in **reverse order**.

(ii) Let consider another examples (Madachy, 1966, pp.167-175 [11]):

$$\begin{aligned} 34425 &:= 3^4 \times 425 \\ 312325 &:= 31^2 \times 325 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Above two are represented their own digits. Moreover, if we multiply by both sides by 10, they continued with property of same digits both sides. These kinds of numbers are famous as **number patterns**. Still there is another number with different property, i.e.,

$$27594 := 73 \times 9 \times 42 = 7 \times 3942 \quad (3)$$

In this case, the two expressions on right side of (4) are with same digits, but the total value is with different digits. This type of study is not under work.

(iii) Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [11] also gave an interesting property with factorials know by **sum of factorials**:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= 1! \\ 2 &:= 2! \\ 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Above numbers also have the property of same digits on both sides, but with factorial and addition.

In all the three situations, we observe that we are dealing with numbers those have same digits on both sides, where one side is number another with same digits with certain operations. Based on above idea of numbers, the author studies numbers calling **selfie numbers**, i.e., numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. Some studies in this direction can seen in the works of Friedman [6, 7] and Rose [2, 3, 4].

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** extending the idea of equation (2) using the operations of addition and subtraction with **factorial**:

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &= 1! + 4! + 5! & 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \\ 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! \\ 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\ 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\ 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! \\ 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! \\ 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! \\ 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! \\ 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\ 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\ 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\ 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\ 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\ 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \end{aligned}$$

0.1 Selfie Numbers with Binomial Coefficients

See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order and reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 6435 &:= C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\ 15504 &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ 54264 &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4 + 5})!) \\ 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) & 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) & 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) & 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) & 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\ 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) & 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\ 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) & 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\ 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) & 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!) & 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)) \end{aligned}$$

The symbol C used for binomial coefficients is given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For more details refer author's work [22, 31]. Also refer [5, 11] for historical books on numbers. Some initial study on **selfie numbers** are given in [6, 7], and for extensions refer [2, 3, 4]. The last Section 3 is dedicated to the summary of **selfie numbers** done by author with different functions.

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients,**

s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

Selfie numbers with:

1. **Basic Operations**; [29];
2. **Factorial**: [26, 27];
3. **Square-root**: [14, 15];
4. **Factorial and Square-root**: [14, 15, 16];
5. **Fibonacci sequence**: [23, 24];
6. **Triangular numbers**: [21, 32, 33];
7. **Fibonacci and Triangular numbers**: [24];
8. **Binomial coefficients**: [22];
9. **Binomial coefficients: Fibonacci**: [31];
10. **Binomial coefficients: Triangular**: [34];
11. **S-gonal numbers**: [17];
12. **Centered Polygonal**: [17];
13. **Concatenation-Type**: [28];
14. **Quadratic numbers**: [25];
15. **Cubic numbers**: [29];

The last Section 3 is dedicated to summary of **selfie numbers** in different situations along with necessary references.

The aim of this paper is to bring **selfie numbers** by use of **binomial coefficients** and **Triangular numbers**. This can be done in three parts. One is by use of **basic operations**, second by use of **factorial** and third by use of **square-root**. This work is concentrated only with **basic operations** and **square-root**. The use of **factorial** shall be dealt elsewhere. The use of only basic operations can be seen in Taneja [34].

1 Binomial-Coefficient-Triangular-Square-Root-Type Selfie Numbers - Digit's Order

1.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

This subsection brings selfie numbers represented in symmetric way. These are blocks of either 10 or 100.

$$3990 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 0$$

$$3991 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 1$$

$$3992 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 2$$

$$3993 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 3$$

$$3994 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 4$$

$$3995 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 5$$

$$3996 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 6$$

$$3997 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 7$$

$$3998 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 8$$

$$3999 := \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + 9$$

$$5490 := \left(T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(9) + 0$$

$$5491 := \left(T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(9) + 1$$

$$5492 := \left(T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(9) + 2$$

$$5493 := \left(T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(9) + 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5494 &:= (T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 4 \\ 5495 &:= (T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 5 \\ 5496 &:= (T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 6 \\ 5497 &:= (T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 7 \\ 5498 &:= (T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 8 \\ 5499 &:= (T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9240 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 0 \\ 9241 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 1 \\ 9242 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 2 \\ 9243 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 3 \\ 9244 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 \\ 9245 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 5 \\ 9246 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\ 9247 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 7 \\ 9248 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 8 \\ 9249 &:= \sqrt{C(9,2)} \times T(T(T(4))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12920 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 0 \\ 12921 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 1 \\ 12922 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 2 \\ 12923 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 3 \\ 12924 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 4 \\ 12925 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 5 \\ 12926 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 6 \\ 12927 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 7 \\ 12928 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 8 \\ 12929 &:= C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18970 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 0 \\ 18971 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 1 \\ 18972 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 2 \\ 18973 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 3 \\ 18974 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18975 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 5 \\ 18976 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 6 \\ 18977 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 7 \\ 18978 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 8 \\ 18979 &:= C(18, T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20580 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 0 \\ 20581 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 1 \\ 20582 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 2 \\ 20583 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 3 \\ 20584 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 4 \\ 20585 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 5 \\ 20586 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 6 \\ 20587 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 7 \\ 20588 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 8 \\ 20589 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), .05) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24480 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 0 \\ 24481 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 1 \\ 24482 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 2 \\ 24483 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 3 \\ 24484 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 4 \\ 24485 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 5 \\ 24486 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 6 \\ 24487 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 7 \\ 24488 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 8 \\ 24489 &:= C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), 4) \times 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24990 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) + 0 \\ 24991 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) + 1 \\ 24992 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24993 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T\left(C(9, \sqrt{9})\right) + 3 \\ 24994 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T\left(C(9, \sqrt{9})\right) + 4 \\ 24995 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T\left(C(9, \sqrt{9})\right) + 5 \\ 24996 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T\left(C(9, \sqrt{9})\right) + 6 \\ 24997 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T\left(C(9, \sqrt{9})\right) + 7 \\ 24998 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T\left(C(9, \sqrt{9})\right) + 8 \\ 24999 &:= (T(2) + 4) \times T\left(C(9, \sqrt{9})\right) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25830 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 0 \\ 25831 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 1 \\ 25832 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 2 \\ 25833 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 3 \\ 25834 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 4 \\ 25835 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 5 \\ 25836 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 6 \\ 25837 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 7 \\ 25838 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 8 \\ 25839 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25840 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 0 \\ 25841 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 1 \\ 25842 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 2 \\ 25843 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 3 \\ 25844 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 4 \\ 25845 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 5 \\ 25846 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 6 \\ 25847 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 7 \\ 25848 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$25849 := \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(4) + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26460 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 0 \\ 26461 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 1 \\ 26462 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 2 \\ 26463 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 3 \\ 26464 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 4 \\ 26465 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 5 \\ 26466 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 6 \\ 26467 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 7 \\ 26468 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 8 \\ 26469 &:= T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27930 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 0 \\ 27931 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 1 \\ 27932 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 2 \\ 27933 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 3 \\ 27934 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 4 \\ 27935 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 5 \\ 27936 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 6 \\ 27937 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 7 \\ 27938 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 8 \\ 27939 &:= C(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32890 &:= C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 0 \\ 32891 &:= C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 1 \\ 32892 &:= C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 2 \\ 32893 &:= C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 3 \\ 32894 &:= C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 4 \\ 32895 &:= C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 5 \\ 32896 &:= C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 6 \\ 32897 &:= C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$32898 := C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 8$$

$$32899 := C\left(3^{T(2)}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 9 + 9$$

$$34580 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 0$$

$$34581 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 1$$

$$34582 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 2$$

$$34583 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 3$$

$$34584 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 4$$

$$34585 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 5$$

$$34586 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 6$$

$$34587 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 7$$

$$34588 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 8$$

$$34589 := C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 9$$

$$35940 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 0$$

$$35941 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 1$$

$$35942 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 2$$

$$35943 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 3$$

$$35944 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 4$$

$$35945 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 5$$

$$35946 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 6$$

$$35947 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 7$$

$$35948 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 8$$

$$35949 := T(3) \times \left(5 + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right)\right) + 9$$

$$37240 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 0$$

$$37241 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 1$$

$$37242 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 2$$

$$37243 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 3$$

$$37244 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 4$$

$$37245 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 5$$

$$37246 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 6$$

$$37247 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 7$$

$$37248 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 8$$

$$37249 := (T(T(3)) + 7) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + 9$$

$$48510 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 0$$

$$48511 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 1$$

$$48512 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 2$$

$$48513 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 3$$

$$48514 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 4$$

$$48515 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 5$$

$$48516 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 6$$

$$48517 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 7$$

$$48518 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 8$$

$$48519 := C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(T(5+1)) + 9$$

$$48930 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 0$$

$$48931 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 1$$

$$48932 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 2$$

$$48933 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 3$$

$$48934 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 4$$

$$48935 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 5$$

$$48936 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 6$$

$$48937 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 7$$

$$48938 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 8$$

$$48939 := \left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right) + 9$$

$$49560 := C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49561 &:= C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 1 \\
 49562 &:= C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 2 \\
 49563 &:= C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 3 \\
 49564 &:= C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 4 \\
 49565 &:= C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 5 \\
 49566 &:= C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 6 \\
 49567 &:= C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 7 \\
 49568 &:= C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 8 \\
 49569 &:= C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \times (5 + T(T(6))) + 9 \\
 \\
 49700 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 0 \\
 49701 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 1 \\
 49702 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 2 \\
 49703 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 3 \\
 49704 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 4 \\
 49705 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 5 \\
 49706 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 6 \\
 49707 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 7 \\
 49708 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 8 \\
 49709 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(70) + 9 \\
 \\
 51480 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 0 \\
 51481 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 1 \\
 51482 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 2 \\
 51483 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 3 \\
 51484 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 4 \\
 51485 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 5 \\
 51486 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 6 \\
 51487 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 7 \\
 51488 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 8 \\
 51489 &:= C\left(T(5), 1 + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 8 + 9 \\
 \\
 54380 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 0
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54381 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 1 \\
 54382 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 2 \\
 54383 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 3 \\
 54384 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 4 \\
 54385 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 5 \\
 54386 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 6 \\
 54387 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 7 \\
 54388 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 8 \\
 54389 &:= T(T(5)) - 4 + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 9 \\
 \\
 54670 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 0 \\
 54671 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 1 \\
 54672 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 2 \\
 54673 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 3 \\
 54674 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 4 \\
 54675 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 5 \\
 54676 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 6 \\
 54677 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 7 \\
 54678 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 8 \\
 54679 &:= C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), 6\right) + T(T(7)) + 9 \\
 \\
 55980 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 0 \\
 55981 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 1 \\
 55982 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 2 \\
 55983 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 3 \\
 55984 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 4 \\
 55985 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 5 \\
 55986 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 6 \\
 55987 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 7 \\
 55988 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 8 \\
 55989 &:= \left(T(5) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times T(8) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 58450 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 0 \\
 58451 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 1 \\
 58452 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 2 \\
 58453 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 3 \\
 58454 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 4 \\
 58455 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 5 \\
 58456 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 6 \\
 58457 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 7 \\
 58458 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 8 \\
 58459 &:= T(T(5+8)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 63840 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 0 \\
 63841 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 1 \\
 63842 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 2 \\
 63843 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 3 \\
 63844 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 4 \\
 63845 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 5 \\
 63846 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 6 \\
 63847 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 7 \\
 63848 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 8 \\
 63849 &:= C(T(6), 3) \times 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64800 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 0 \\
 64801 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 1 \\
 64802 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 2 \\
 64803 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 3 \\
 64804 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 4 \\
 64805 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 5 \\
 64806 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 6 \\
 64807 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 7 \\
 64808 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 8 \\
 64809 &:= C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(80) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65780 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 0 \\
 65781 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 1 \\
 65782 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 2 \\
 65783 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 3 \\
 65784 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 4 \\
 65785 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 5 \\
 65786 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 6 \\
 65787 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 7 \\
 65788 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 8 \\
 65789 &:= C(T(6) + 5, T(\sqrt{T(7) + 8})) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67830 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 0 \\
 67831 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 1 \\
 67832 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 2 \\
 67833 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 3 \\
 67834 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 4 \\
 67835 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 5 \\
 67836 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 6 \\
 67837 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 7 \\
 67838 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 8 \\
 67839 &:= C(T(6), \sqrt{7 + T(8)}) / 3 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68790 &:= -6 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{9}) + 0 \\
 68791 &:= -6 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{9}) + 1 \\
 68792 &:= -6 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{9}) + 2 \\
 68793 &:= -6 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{9}) + 3 \\
 68794 &:= -6 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{9}) + 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 68795 &:= -6 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times C\left(T(7), \sqrt{9}\right) + 5 \\ 68796 &:= -6 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times C\left(T(7), \sqrt{9}\right) + 6 \\ 68797 &:= -6 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times C\left(T(7), \sqrt{9}\right) + 7 \\ 68798 &:= -6 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times C\left(T(7), \sqrt{9}\right) + 8 \\ 68799 &:= -6 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times C\left(T(7), \sqrt{9}\right) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74970 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 0 \\ 74971 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 1 \\ 74972 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 2 \\ 74973 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 3 \\ 74974 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 4 \\ 74975 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 5 \\ 74976 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 6 \\ 74977 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 7 \\ 74978 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 8 \\ 74979 &:= C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)\right) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76440 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 0 \\ 76441 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 1 \\ 76442 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 2 \\ 76443 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 3 \\ 76444 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 4 \\ 76445 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 5 \\ 76446 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 6 \\ 76447 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 7 \\ 76448 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 8 \\ 76449 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 79380 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 0 \\ 79381 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 1 \\ 79382 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 2 \\ 79383 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 79384 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 4 \\ 79385 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 5 \\ 79386 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 6 \\ 79387 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 7 \\ 79388 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 8 \\ 79389 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 79920 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 0 \\ 79921 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 1 \\ 79922 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 2 \\ 79923 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 3 \\ 79924 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 4 \\ 79925 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 5 \\ 79926 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 6 \\ 79927 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 7 \\ 79928 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 8 \\ 79929 &:= T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \times T(C(9,2)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 82440 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 0 \\ 82441 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 1 \\ 82442 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 2 \\ 82443 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 3 \\ 82444 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 4 \\ 82445 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 5 \\ 82446 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 6 \\ 82447 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 7 \\ 82448 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 8 \\ 82449 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C\left(T(4), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 83720 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T\left(T(7 + T(T(2)))\right) + 0 \\ 83721 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T\left(T(7 + T(T(2)))\right) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 83722 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T(T(7+T(T(2)))) + 2 \\
 83723 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T(T(7+T(T(2)))) + 3 \\
 83724 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T(T(7+T(T(2)))) + 4 \\
 83725 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T(T(7+T(T(2)))) + 5 \\
 83726 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T(T(7+T(T(2)))) + 6 \\
 83727 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T(T(7+T(T(2)))) + 7 \\
 83728 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T(T(7+T(T(2)))) + 8 \\
 83729 &:= C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T(T(7+T(T(2)))) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 89670 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 0 \\
 89671 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 1 \\
 89672 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 2 \\
 89673 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 3 \\
 89674 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 4 \\
 89675 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 5 \\
 89676 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 6 \\
 89677 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 7 \\
 89678 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 8 \\
 89679 &:= T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T(6) + T(T(7))) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99750 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 0 \\
 99751 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 1 \\
 99752 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 2 \\
 99753 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 3 \\
 99754 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 4 \\
 99755 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 5 \\
 99756 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 6 \\
 99757 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 7 \\
 99758 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 8 \\
 99759 &:= C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 75 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99960 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 0 \\
 99961 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 1 \\
 99962 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 2 \\
 99963 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 3 \\
 99964 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 4 \\
 99965 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 5 \\
 99966 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 6 \\
 99967 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 7 \\
 99968 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 8 \\
 99969 &:= T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(C(9,6)) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1.1. Most of the *selfie numbers* appearing in the subsection below are with lot of extra brackets "(...)". These can be removed easily after making simplifications.

1.2 General Representations

Below are selfie numbers in a general way. The results are up to 7-digits numbers.

$$\begin{aligned}
 429 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) - (T(29))\right) \\
 441 &:= \left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{C(4,1)}} \\
 452 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) - (C(T(5), T(2)))\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 453 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - C(T(5), 3) \right) \right) \\
 459 &:= \left(4 + C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 544 &:= \left(T \left(\left(- (5) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 445 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - T(4) \right) \\
 594 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 229 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 924 &:= C \left((9 + T(2)), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 1029 &:= \left(T(C(10,2)) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 1139 &:= \left(- (1) + C \left(- (1) + T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 1329 &:= \left(- (1) + C \left(T((3 \times 2)), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 1491 &:= \left(T \left(\left(- (1) + T(T(4)) \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \\
 1554 &:= \left((-1 + T(5)) + T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 1585 &:= -\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} + T(C(8,5)) \\
 1593 &:= \left(T \left(\left(1 + T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) - 3 \right) \\
 1595 &:= \left(- (1) + T \left(C \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9} \right), 5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 1599 &:= \left(T \left(\left(1 + T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 1828 &:= \left(\left(1 + T(C(8, T(2))) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 1842 &:= \left(\left((1 \times 8) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - T(T(2)) \right) \\
 1848 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(- ((1 - 8)), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 1942 &:= \left(\left((- (1) + T(9))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + T(T(2)) \right) \\
 2024 &:= C \left((T(2) + T(T(T(02)))) , T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 2274 &:= \left(T(T(2)) + \left(T(T(2)) \times C \left(T(7), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2279 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(2))) - C \left(- ((T(2) - T(7))), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 2292 &:= \left(T \left((2 + T(T(T(2)))) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \\
 2358 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T(2)^3 \right) \right) + T(5) \right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 2427 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(2)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)) \right) \\
 2437 &:= \left(C \left(2, \sqrt{4} \right) + T(3) \times T(T(7)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2456 &:= - \left(\left(\left(2^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))} \right) + (T(T(5)) \times (-T(6))) \right) \right) \\
 2482 &:= \left(- (T(2)) + T \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times T(8)) - 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 2486 &:= \left(T \left(\left(2^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))} \right) \right) + (T(C(8,6))) \right) \\
 2529 &:= \left((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5))) + (T(2) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 2584 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T \left((8 - \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 2639 &:= \left((2 \times C(T(6), 3)) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 2658 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(2)) - \left(\sqrt{T(6) - 5} \times T(T(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2742 &:= \left(- (2) + \left((T(7) / \sqrt{4})^{T(2)} \right) \right) \\
 2844 &:= \left(- (T(T(2))) + T \left(\left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T(T(4)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2859 &:= \left(\left(T(2) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T((T(T(5)) - T(9))) \right) \\
 2897 &:= \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(2)\sqrt{T(8)}}, \sqrt{9} \right) - (T(7)) \right) \\
 2976 &:= \left(T(T(2)) \times T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(C(7,6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 2993 &:= \left(- \left(T \left((-2) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) / 3 \right) \right) \\
 2997 &:= \left(T \left((-2) + C(9, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - T(T(7)) \\
 3274 &:= \left(- ((T(3) / T(2))) + C(T(7), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 3318 &:= -3 + T \left(\sqrt{C(3,1)^8} \right) \\
 3346 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), 3) + T \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 3462 &:= \left(\left(C(T(3), \sqrt{4}) \times T(T(6)) \right) - T(2) \right) \\
 3483 &:= - \left(\left(C(3, \sqrt{4}) - T(83) \right) \right) \\
 3493 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) / (-T(\sqrt{4})) \right) + (T(C(9,3))) \right) \\
 3494 &:= \left(- ((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + T \left(C(9, T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 3542 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) + T \left(T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \right) \times 2 \\
 3591 &:= \left(T(T(3)) \times T \left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 3654 &:= C \left(((3 + T(6)) + (5)), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 3741 &:= T \left(\left((3 \times T(7)) + \sqrt{C(4,1)} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3794 &:= \left((T(T(T(3))) - 7) + T\left(C\left(9, T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\
 3843 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(T(T(4)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 3876 &:= \left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / (-7) + T(6) \right) \\
 3945 &:= \left(3 \times \left(C\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(\sqrt{4})\right) - T(5) \right) \right) \\
 3954 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) + (-9) \times T\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \right) \\
 3976 &:= - \left(\left(T\left(C\left(T(3), \sqrt{9}\right)\right) - T(T((7+6))) \right) \right) \\
 4144 &:= \left(4 \times \left(1 + T\left(C\left(T(4), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 4244 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left((-T(2) + T(T(4)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 4248 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), T(2)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(8) \right) \\
 4299 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4})^{T(T(2))} \right) + T\left(C(9, \sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 4389 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), T(3)) \times T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) - T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 4414 &:= \left((-4) + T(T(T(4)+1)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4422 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times T(C((4 \times T(2)), 2)) \right) \\
 4424 &:= \left(- \left((T(T(T(4))) - C(T(T(T(2))), 4)) - T\left(T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right) \right) \right) \\
 4424 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), 4\right) - (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \right) \\
 4428 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + C(T(4), T(2)) \right) \times T(8) \right) \\
 4431 &:= \left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times (C(T(4), T(3)) + 1) \right) \\
 4454 &:= - \left(\left(T\left(\left(T(4) + T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right)\right) - T\left(\left(T(T(5)) - T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 4465 &:= T\left(\left(\left(T(4)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) - C(6, 5)\right)\right) \\
 4474 &:= \left(\left(4^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))} \right) + \left(C\left(T(7), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \right) \\
 4485 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(4)) \right) - (-T(8) \times T(T(5))) \right) \\
 4494 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) - C(9, 4) \right) \\
 4520 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) - 5 \right) \times 20 \right) \\
 4529 &:= \left(T(4) \times C(T(5), T(2)) - T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 4544 &:= \left(\left(T(4) \times C\left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) - T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) \\
 4545 &:= \left(\left(T(4) \times C\left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 4549 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left(C(T(5), T(4)) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4594 &:= \left(\left(4^5 \right) + T \left(C \left(9, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4597 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - C \left(T \left(5 \right), 9 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4686 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times T \left(68 \right) \right) - \left(6 \right) \right) \\
 4723 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4^7} \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4843 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 4844 &:= \left(\left(4 \times T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4845 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) - T \left(8 \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 4861 &:= \left(T \left(4 \right) + \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \times T \left(T \left(C \left(6, 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4862 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \times \left(-T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 4873 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(T \left(8 \right) \times T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) / 3 \right) \\
 4887 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 4896 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(4 \right) + 8 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 4970 &:= \sqrt{C \left(4, \sqrt{9} \right)} \times T \left(70 \right) \\
 5229 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(5 \right) + T \left(2 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 5234 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 5239 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 5242 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5245 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5383 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) + T \left(\left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} + T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5449 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-4 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5484 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), 4 \right) - \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \times \left(-4 \right) \right) \\
 5559 &:= \left(T \left(5 \right) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) / 5 \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5592 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) / 5 \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 5649 &:= \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5698 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), 6 \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 5742 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), 7 \right) - \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5745 &:= (T(5) \times (C(T(7), \sqrt{4}) + (5))) \\ 5748 &:= ((C(T(5), 7) - T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - (T(T(8)))) \\ 5844 &:= ((- (T(T(5))) + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 4)) - T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \\ 5847 &:= (C(T(5), 8) - (T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(7))) \\ 5884 &:= ((5 \times T(\sqrt{T(8) \times 8})) + 4) \\ 5922 &:= (((T(T(5)) + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times 2) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 5952 &:= (T(T(5)) + ((\sqrt{9} + T(5))^{T(2)})) \\ 5964 &:= ((- (T(5)) - T(\sqrt{9})) + (C(T(6), 4))) \\ 5985 &:= C(T((T(5) - 9)), \sqrt{T(\sqrt{T(8)} - 5)}) \\ 5994 &:= ((T(5) - T(\sqrt{9})) \times T((9 \times 4))) \\ 6458 &:= ((T(6) + \sqrt{4}) + C(T(5), 8)) \\ 6545 &:= ((- (T(T(6))) + T(T(C(5, \sqrt{4})))) \times 5) \\ 6582 &:= \sqrt{(-6 + T(5))^8 + T(T(T(2)))} \\ 6639 &:= ((T(66) \times 3) + T(\sqrt{9})) \\ 6699 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (C(6, \sqrt{9}) + 9)) \\ 6831 &:= ((T(6) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1))) \\ 6986 &:= (- (C(T(6), \sqrt{9})) + (T(8) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 7491 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - T(T(C(9, 1)))) \\ 7545 &:= ((- (T(C(7, 5))) + (T(T(\sqrt{4}))^5)) \\ 7679 &:= - ((T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (-C(7, \sqrt{9})))) \\ 7693 &:= (7 \times (C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 7798 &:= ((T(7) \times T(T(7))) - T(C(9, \sqrt{T(8)}))) \\ 7922 &:= ((T(7) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times (2 + T(T(T(T(2))))) \\ 7965 &:= ((C(7, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(5))) \\ 7993 &:= (- (7) + (C(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9})^3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7993 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(3), \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (7) \right) \\
 7999 &:= \left(C \left((7+9), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 9 \right) \\
 8244 &:= \left(T(8) \times \left(T \left(T \left((2+4) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 8424 &:= \left(\left(T(8) \times T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left((2+T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 8442 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 4 \right) \times T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8444 &:= \left(\left(T(8) + T \left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + T(4) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 8452 &:= \left(\left(T(8) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left((-5) + T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8470 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 4 \right) + (T(70)) \right) \\
 8472 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(T(8) \right) \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times T(7) \right) \right) \right) \times (-2) \right) \\
 8476 &:= \left(- (8) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T \left(T(7) \right) \right) \times (-T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 8484 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8589 &:= \left(C \left(\sqrt{9 \times T(8)}, 5 \right) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 8757 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (C(7,5) \times T(T(7))) \right) \\
 8842 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) - 2 \right) \\
 8883 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 8933 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T(8) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(3) \right) \right) / (-T(3)) \right) \\
 8973 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 8999 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T(9) \right) \\
 9044 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{04} \right) \right) \right) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9252 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times (2 + T \left(T \left(C(5,2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9262 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 2 \right) + \left(T(6)^{T(2)} \right) \right) \\
 9282 &:= \left(C \left((9 \times 2), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / 2 \right) \\
 9289 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)^{T(2)} + C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9294 &:= \left(\left((T(T(9)) - 2) \times 9 \right) - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9297 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{T(2)} \right) + C(9,7) \right) \\
 9317 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 3 \right) + 1 \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 9366 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 3 \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 9444 &:= \left(T(9) \times C(T(4), 4) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9482 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(- (T(4)) + \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right)^{T(2)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9527 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times C(T(5), T(2)) \right) - T(7) \right) \\
 9534 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times C(T(5), 3) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9549 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9555 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times C(T(5), (T(5)/5)) \right) \\
 9681 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(\left(- (T(T(6))) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \\
 9689 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - C(T(6), 8) \right) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9702 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times (7 \times T(T(02))) \right) \\
 9723 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + ((7 \times T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) \right) \\
 9758 &:= \left(T(97) + C \left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 9759 &:= \left((T(C(9,7)) \times T(5)) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9846 &:= \left(\left(T(9) + T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 9864 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(T(6)) \times (-T(4)))) \right) \right) \\
 9963 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times T((C(9,6) - 3)) \right) \\
 9998 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) - 9 \right) \times T(9) \right) + 8 \\
 10296 &:= \left(C \left((10 + T(2)), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 10398 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \times T(9) \right) + C(3,01) \\
 10549 &:= \left(T(T(10)) + \left(C(T(5), T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 10781 &:= \left(\left(T(T(10)) \times C \left(7, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 10785 &:= \left(\left(T(T(10)) \times C \left(7, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (5) \right) \\
 10927 &:= \left(\left(T(T(10)) + T \left(\sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) \right) \times 7 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11549 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(T (T (- ((1 - 5)))) \times C \left(T (4), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 12382 &:= \left(C \left((- (1) + (T (2) \times T (3))), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T (T (2)) \right) \\
 12397 &:= \left(C \left((1 \times 23), \sqrt{9} \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 12434 &:= \left((1 + (C (T (T (T (2)))), 4) + T (T (T (3)))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 12436 &:= \left(\left(C \left((1 + T (T (T (2)))), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + 3 \right) / 6 \right) \\
 12444 &:= \left(12 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + T \left(C \left(T (4), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 12453 &:= \left(-1 + \sqrt{C(T(T(T(2))), T(4)) + T(T(5))} \right) \times T(T(3)) \\
 12474 &:= \left(\left(1 + \sqrt{2^{T(4)}} \right) \times C \left(T (7), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 12529 &:= \left(\left((- (1) - T (T (T (T (2)))) \right) \times (- T (C (5, 2))) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 12629 &:= \left(C \left((- ((1 - 26)), T (T (T (2))) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 12858 &:= \left(- ((1 \times 2)) \times \left(\sqrt{T(8)} - C (T (5), 8) \right) \right) \\
 12859 &:= \left(\left(((1 - T (T (T (T (2))))) \times (- C (8, 5)) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 12881 &:= \left(\left(\left((- (1) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times C (8, T(2)) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 12882 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left((- (1) + T (T (2)) \right) \right), 8 \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 12919 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(C \left(T (T (T (2)) \right), \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \right) / 9 \right) \right) \\
 13293 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left((1 + T (3) \right), T (2) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times T (T (3)) \right) \\
 13298 &:= \left((- (1) - T (T (3))) + \left(C \left(T (T (2) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T (T (8)) \right) \right) \\
 13348 &:= \left(T \left((1 + T (3) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T (3), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T (T (8)) \right) \right) \\
 13449 &:= \left(\left(13 \times T \left(C \left(T (4), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 13456 &:= \left(1 + \left(C \left(\left(3^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right), 5 \right) / 6 \right) \right) \\
 13544 &:= \left((- (1) - (C (T (T (3) \right), T (5)) / (-4)) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 13565 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(C \left(T (T (3) \right), T (5) \right) / \sqrt{T(6) - 5} \right) \right) \\
 13728 &:= \left(C \left(13, \sqrt{72} \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 13799 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(T (3) \times C \left(\left(T (7) - \sqrt{9} \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 13824 &:= (1 \times 3 \times 8)^{C(T(2), \sqrt{4})} \\
 13924 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left((1 + 3) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13965 &:= \left((-1) + T \left(T(3) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times T(C(6,5)) \\ 13979 &:= \left(-1 + \left(T(T(3)) \times T(C(9,7)) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\ 13988 &:= \left(\sqrt{1+3} - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9,8)} \right) \right) \times (-T(T(8))) \right) \right) \\ 14279 &:= \left(-1 + \left(4 \times T \left(C(2+7, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\ 14344 &:= \left((-1) + \left(C(T(4), 3)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - T(T(4)) \right) \\ 14345 &:= \left((-1) \times T(T(4)) + \left(T \left(C(T(3), \sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\ 14392 &:= \left(T \left(T \left((1 + T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) - \left(T(T(3)) \times (-T(C(9,2))) \right) \right) \\ 14399 &:= \left(-1 + \left(C(T(4), 3) \times T \left((T(9) / \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\ 14534 &:= \left(-1 + \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times C((T(T(5)) / T(3)), 4) \right) \right) \\ 14559 &:= \left(-1 + \left(\sqrt{4^5} \times C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\ 14696 &:= \left((1 + T(4)) \times \left(C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) + (6) \right) \right) \\ 14789 &:= \left((1 + (4^7)) - T \left(C(8, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\ 14862 &:= \left(\left((1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \times T(T(8)) + C(T(6), 2) \right) \\ 14895 &:= \left(\left(T((-1) + C(T(4), 8)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times T(5) \right) \\ 14945 &:= \left(C \left(\left(-1 + \left(T(\sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right), 4 \right) - (5) \right) \\ 14952 &:= \left((1 - 4) \times \left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - (C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \right) \right) \\ 14953 &:= \left(1 + \left(- \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times \left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - (C(T(5), T(3))) \right) \right) \right) \\ 14954 &:= \left((1 \times 4) + C \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 5 \right), 4 \right) \right) \\ 14959 &:= \left((-1) - T(T(4)) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times C(T(5), 9) \right) \right) \\ 14964 &:= \left((1 \times 4) \times T \left(\left(C(9,6) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\ 14994 &:= \left((-1) + C \left(T(4), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times C(9,4) \\ 15243 &:= \left(\left((-1) + C(T(5), T(T(2))) \right) \times T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(3))) \right) \\ 15251 &:= T \left(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} \right) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + C(5,1) \\ 15288 &:= \left(C((-1) + T(5), T(2)) \times \left(T(8) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\ 15291 &:= T \left(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} \right) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(C(9,1)) \\ 15591 &:= T \left(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} \right) + T(5) \times T(T(C(9,1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15735 &:= \left(T(T((1+5))) + C\left(\sqrt{T(T(7)) - T(3)}, 5\right) \right) \\
 15942 &:= T\left(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))}\right) + C(9, 4)^2 \\
 16485 &:= \left(\left(C(T((1+6)), T(\sqrt{4})) + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 16555 &:= \left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{16}\right)\right)\right) + (C(T(5), 5) \times 5) \right) \\
 16646 &:= \left(T(T((1+6))) \times \left(C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) + (T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 16744 &:= \left(\sqrt{16} \times T\left(C\left(\frac{T(7)}{\sqrt{4}}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \\
 16785 &:= \left((-1) - T(6) + \left(C\left(7, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)^5 \right) \right) \\
 16796 &:= \left(C(T((1 \times 6)), (7 + \sqrt{9})) / T(6) \right) \\
 16954 &:= \left((-1) + C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) + \left(5^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))} \right) \right) \\
 16956 &:= \left(1 + \left(C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) + (5^6) \right) \right) \\
 17319 &:= \left(C((-1) + T(7), (3+1)) - T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 17424 &:= \left((T(17) - T(C(4, 2)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 17429 &:= \left((-1) + \left((T(7) + T(T(4))) \times T\left(C\left(T(T(2)), \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 17565 &:= \left(C\left((-1) + T(7), \sqrt{-5 + T(6)}\right) + (T(5)) \right) \\
 17639 &:= \left((-1) + \left((T(7) \times T(C(6, 3))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 17683 &:= \left((1 - T(T(7))) + \left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / 3 \right) \right) \\
 17724 &:= \left(T((1 \times 7)) \times \left(T(C(7, T(2))) + T\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \right) \right) \\
 17884 &:= \left((-1) + \left(\left(C\left(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) - (T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 17898 &:= \left(((-1) + T(7)) \times T(T(8)) - C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 17925 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T((1 \times 7)), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / T(T(T(2))) \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 17933 &:= \left((-1) + \left(\left(C\left(T(7), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / T(T(3)) \right) - (T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 17934 &:= - \left(\left(T(-((1-7))) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times C(T(T(3)), 4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17938 &:= \left((-1) + \left(\left(C\left(T(7), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - T(T(3)) \right) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) \\
 17939 &:= \left((-1) + \left(C\left(T(7), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / T(-((3-9))) \right) \right) \\
 17940 &:= \left(C\left(T((1 \times 7)), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) / T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4+0}\right)\right)\right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17941 &:= \left(1 + \left(C\left(T(7), T(\sqrt{9})\right) / T(T((4-1)))\right)\right) \\ 17942 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T((1 \times 7)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) / T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) + 2\right) \\ 17943 &:= \left(\left(T((1 + T(7))) - C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) / (-3)\right) \\ 17947 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T((1 \times 7)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) / T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) + 7\right) \\ 17949 &:= \left((1 - 7) + \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\ 17953 &:= \left(\left((-1) + T(T(7))\right) - C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(5)\right)\right) / (-3) \\ 17962 &:= \left(\left(1 - \left(C\left(T(7), T(\sqrt{9})\right) / (-T(6))\right)\right) + T(T(T(2)))\right) \\ 17967 &:= \left(-1 - \left(\left(C\left(T(7), T(\sqrt{9})\right) / (-T(6))\right) - T(7)\right)\right) \\ 17979 &:= \left(\left((-1) + T(7)\right) \times T(C(9,7)) - \sqrt{9}\right) \\ 17985 &:= \left(\left(\left(-1 + T(7)\right) + T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \times 5\right) \\ 17995 &:= \left(\left(1 + T(7)\right) + T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \times 5 \\ 18089 &:= \left(1 + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{T(08)}\right) / \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\ 18259 &:= \left(T(18) + \left(C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(5)\right) / \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\ 18294 &:= \left(C(18, T(T(2))) + \left(-T(9) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \\ 18332 &:= \left(\left(-1 - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) + C\left((3 \times T(3)), T(T(2))\right)\right) \\ 18334 &:= \left(\left(1 - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) + C\left((3 \times T(3)), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \\ 18339 &:= \left(C(18, T(3)) - T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{9})\right) \\ 18393 &:= -\left(\left(T(18) - C\left(\left(T(3) \times \sqrt{9}\right), T(3)\right)\right)\right) \\ 18428 &:= \left(C\left(18, T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - T((2 \times 8))\right) \\ 18429 &:= \left(C\left(18, T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - (T(2) \times T(9))\right) \\ 18444 &:= \left(C\left(18, T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \\ 18445 &:= \left(1 + \left(C\left((8 + T(4)), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - (T(T(5)))\right)\right) \\ 18454 &:= \left(C\left(18, T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - (T(T(5)) - T(4))\right) \\ 18474 &:= \left(\left((-1) - T(T(8))\right) \times T(\sqrt{4}) + (C(T(7), 4))\right) \\ 18479 &:= \left(-1 + \left(T((8 \times 4)) \times C\left(7, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\ 18529 &:= \left((1 - T(8)) + C\left((T(5) + T(2)), T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18542 &:= \left(\left(- (1) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + C \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right), T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 18543 &:= \left(C \left(18, T \left(\sqrt{5+4} \right) \right) - T(T(3)) \right) \\
 18544 &:= \left(\left(1 - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + C \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 18546 &:= \left(- (18) + C \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 6 \right) \right) \\
 18549 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - C \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 18558 &:= \left(C \left(18, T \left((T(5) / 5) \right) \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 18562 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{1+8} + T(5) \right), 6 \right) - 2 \right) \\
 18592 &:= \left(T \left(- ((1-8)) \right) + C \left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{9} \right), T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 18599 &:= \left(- (1) + T(8) \right) + C \left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{9} \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 18699 &:= \left(C(18,6) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times T(9) \right) \right) \\
 18754 &:= \left(1 - \left((T(T(8)) \times (-T(7))) - \left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 18864 &:= \left(C \left(18, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T((6 \times 4)) \right) \\
 18879 &:= \left(C \left(18, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + (7 \times T(9)) \right) \\
 18894 &:= \left(C \left(18, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 18990 &:= \left(\left(1 + T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times 90 \right) \\
 18997 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - (T(T(7))) \right) \right) \\
 19881 &:= \left(1 + \left(8 \times T \left(C \left(8, \left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 19884 &:= \left(\left(1 + \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(- (8) \times T(C(8,4)) \right) \right) \\
 20285 &:= \left(- \left(\left(2^{T(T(02))} \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 5 \right) \right) \\
 20294 &:= \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), \left(02 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - (T(T(4))) \right) \\
 20328 &:= \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), (03+2) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 20329 &:= \left(- (20) + C \left(T(T(3)), \left(2 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 20343 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(2)) - C \left(T(T(03)), \left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 20345 &:= \left((2 - T(03)) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20346 &:= \left(- (T(2)) + C \left(T(T(03)), \sqrt{4 + T(6)} \right) \right) \\
 20347 &:= \left(- (2) + C \left(T(T(03)), - \left((\sqrt{4} - (7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 20354 &:= \left(2 + \left(C(T(T(03)), 5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 20377 &:= \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{-03 + T(7)} \right) + (T(7)) \right) \\
 20454 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(2))) - C \left(T \left((\sqrt{04} + (5)) \right), 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 20485 &:= \left(T \left((2^{04}) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 5 \right) \right) \\
 20559 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), 05) + T \left(\left(T(T(5)) / T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 20884 &:= \left((C(20, 8) - T(T(8))) / T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 20944 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(T(2)))) \times C \left(09, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + (T(T(T(4)))) \right) \\
 20989 &:= \left((C(20, 9) / 8) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 20995 &:= \left(C(20, 9) / (\sqrt{9} + (5)) \right) \\
 21295 &:= \left(T \left(\left((T(T(T(2))) + 1) + T(T(T(2)))) \right) + C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), 5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 21349 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), (- (1) + T(3))) + \left((T(4)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \\
 21398 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(2))) + 1 \right) + \left(- (T(3)) \times T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 21399 &:= \left(- (21) + \left(T(3) \times T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 21489 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(T(2))) + 1), 4 \right) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + T(T(9)) \\
 21496 &:= \left(- \left((2^{T(1+4)}) \right) + C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), 6 \right) \right) \\
 21554 &:= \left(- (T(T(2))) - \left((1 - T(5)) \times T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 21574 &:= \left(C(21, 5) + T(\sqrt{74}) \right) \\
 21645 &:= \left(\left(T(T(2))^{\sqrt{16}} \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 5 \right) \right) \\
 21928 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(T \left((1 + C(9, T(2))) \right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 21946 &:= \left(\left(T \left(- \left((C(2, 1) - 9) \right) \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) - (6) \right) \\
 21949 &:= - \left(\left(T(2) - \left(C \left(- \left((1 - 9) \right), \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 22429 &:= \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), \left(T(2) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + T \left((2^{T(\sqrt{9})}) \right) \right) \\
 22435 &:= \left(\left(T \left((2^{T(T(2))}) \right) + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + (C(T(T(3)), 5)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22558 &:= \left((-2) + C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + T\left(T\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 22589 &:= \left((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) \times (-T(5))) / (-T(8)) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 22874 &:= -\left((T(2) - C((2 \times 8), 7)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 22925 &:= \left(-C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) - \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times (T(T(T(2))) \times (-5)) \right) \right) \\
 22938 &:= \left((T(22) + T(C(9, 3))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 22939 &:= \left((T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(T(2)) - T(T(9)))) + \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 23254 &:= \left(-2 + \left(C((T(T(3)) - 2), 5) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 23258 &:= \left(2 + \left(C((T(T(3)) - 2), T(5)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 23259 &:= \left(T(2) + \left(C((T(T(3)) - 2), T(5)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 23274 &:= \left((T(T(2)) - C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) / (-7)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 23279 &:= \left(-T(2) + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + \left(T(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 23387 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(2)), 3) + T(\sqrt{3^8}) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 23398 &:= \left(-2 + \left(C(3^3, \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 23454 &:= \left(\left((T(T(2))^{T(3)} + C(T(4), 5)) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 23544 &:= \left((T(T(2))^3) \times \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 23814 &:= \left((T(2) \times T(T(3))) \times C(T((8-1)), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 23919 &:= \left(\left(C(C(T(T(2))), 3, \sqrt{9}) - 1 \right) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 23934 &:= \left(T(2) \times \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}) \times T(3) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 23938 &:= \left(-2 - \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}) \times (-3) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 23964 &:= \left((-2 + T(3)) \times \left(T(\sqrt{9}) + C(T(6), 4) \right) \right) \\
 23974 &:= \left(\left(T(2^3) \right) \times T(C(9, 7)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 23978 &:= \left(\sqrt{-2 + T(3)} + \left(T(C(9, 7)) \times T(8) \right) \right) \\
 23979 &:= \left(\left(T(2^3) \right) \times T(C(9, 7)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 23982 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(T(2)), 3)^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) \right) \\
 23985 &:= \left(T((2+3)) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + T(C(8, 5)) \right) \right) \\
 23989 &:= \left(\left(T(2) + C(T(3), \sqrt{9}) \right) \times (8 + T(T(9))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23994 &:= \left(T(2) \times \left(\left(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 23995 &:= \left(\left(T(2) \times \left(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 24269 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(T(2)))) - \left(T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \times C(6, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 24289 &:= \left(C(((2 \times T(4)) - T(2)), 8) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 24415 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})) + ((T(T(T(4))) - 1) \times T(5)) \right) \\
 24448 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\left(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 4 \right) - 4 \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 24473 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7) \right)^3 \right) \right) \\
 24541 &:= \left(T(T(T(T(2)))) + \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(5) \right), (T(4) - 1) \right) \right) \right) \\
 24649 &:= \left(T(2^4) + T(6) \right)^{\text{sqrt}C(4, \sqrt{9})} \\
 24746 &:= \left(- (2) \times \left(T(\sqrt{4}) - C((7 + T(4)), 6) \right) \right) \\
 24827 &:= \left((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times \left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(T(2)) \right) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 24849 &:= \left(2 + \left((T(4) \times T(C(8, 4))) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 24865 &:= \left(- (T(T(2))) + \left(\left(T(T(4)) \times C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 6 \right) \right) / T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 24888 &:= \left(\left((T(2) \times T(C(T(4), 8))) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 24955 &:= \left(\left(T((T(2) + (4)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (C(T(5), 5)) \right) \\
 24959 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(T(2)))) - \left(T(T(4)) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 24969 &:= \left((T(2) + (4)) \times \left(T(C(9, 6)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 24976 &:= \left(\left(T(T(2)) \times T\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times T(9) \right) \right) \right) + T(T(C(7, 6))) \right) \\
 24982 &:= \left(\left(T(T(2)) \times \left(4^{T(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) + (T(C(8, 2))) \right) \\
 24985 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left((T(2) + \sqrt{4}) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - 8 \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 24987 &:= \left(- (T(2)) - \left(T\left(\left(C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) - T(8) \right) \right) \times (-7) \right) \right) \\
 25128 &:= \left((2 + T(C((T(5) - 1), 2))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 25198 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(T(T(5)) \times C\left((1 + 9), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 25258 &:= \left((2 + (C(T(5), T(T(2))) \times 5)) + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 25259 &:= \left(T(T(T(T(2)))) - \left((C(T(5), T(T(2))) \times (-5)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25279 &:= \left((C(25, T(T(2))) / 7) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 25285 &:= \left(\left(2 \times C\left((5^2), T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 25288 &:= \left(2 \times \left(C\left((5^2), T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 25297 &:= \left(- (T(2)) - \left(C\left((5^2), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) / (-7) \right) \right) \\
 25349 &:= \left(((T(T(2)) + (C(T(5), 3))) \times T(T(4))) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 25395 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(2))) \times \left(- (T(T(5)) - C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 25443 &:= \left(T(2) - \left(T(T(5)) \times \left(- (\sqrt{4} + C(T(4), T(3))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 25459 &:= \left((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - \left(C\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 5 \right) / 9 \right) \right) \\
 25474 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(7) \right) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 25478 &:= \left(- (2) - \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times (- (7 \times 8)) \right) \right) \\
 25483 &:= \left(T(2) - \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times (-C(8, 3)) \right) \right) \\
 25695 &:= \left(\left(C((- (2) + T(5)), 6) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times T(5) \right) \\
 25696 &:= \left((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - \left(C\left((T(6) + \sqrt{9}), T(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 25716 &:= \left((T(T(2)) - C(T(5), 7)) \times (-\sqrt{16}) \right) \\
 25734 &:= \left(((2 \times C(T(5), 7)) - 3) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 25871 &:= \left(\left(C\left(- ((T(2) - T(5))), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(7) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 25874 &:= \left(\left(C\left(- ((T(2) - T(5))), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(7) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 25949 &:= \left((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5))) - C\left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) + \sqrt{4}), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 25985 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(T(2))), 5) / (-\sqrt{9}) \right) + (8^5) \right) \\
 25994 &:= \left(- (T(T(2))) + \left(C\left((5 + T(T(\sqrt{9}))), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T(4) \right) \right) \\
 25998 &:= \left(T(T(2)) \times \left(\left(C(T(5), 9) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 26256 &:= \left(T(T(2)) + \left(C(T(6), 2) \times \sqrt{5^6} \right) \right) \\
 26297 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(2)^6}, T(2) \right) \times 9 \right) - T(7) \right) \\
 26334 &:= C\left((2 + C(6, 3)), (3 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 26369 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(T(2)))) + \left(- (C(6, 3)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 26384 &:= \left(\left((T(T(T(2))) \times C(T(6), 3)) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26484 &:= \left(T(T(2)) \times \left(\left(T(6) \times C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 26496 &:= \left(C\left(T(2) + T(6), \sqrt{4}\right) \times 96 \right) \\
 26832 &:= \left(C\left(-2 + T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T\left(T(T(3)) + T(2)\right) \right) \\
 26846 &:= \left(\left(C\left(-2 + T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T(T(4)) \right) - T(T(6)) \right) \\
 26873 &:= \left(\left(C\left(-2 + T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T(7) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \\
 26983 &:= \left(-2 + \left(-T(6) \times \left(T(9) - C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 3\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27129 &:= \left(C\left(-2 + T(7-1), T(T(2))\right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 27134 &:= \left(C\left(-2 + T(7-1), T(3) + \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\
 27138 &:= \left(C\left(-2 + T(7-1), T(3) + \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 27264 &:= \left(2^7 \times \left(T(2) + C\left(T(6), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \right) \\
 27298 &:= \left(-2 - \left(-C(7, T(2)) \times T\left(\sqrt{9} + T(8)\right) \right) \right) \\
 27334 &:= \left((2 - T(T(7))) - C(T(T(3)), T(3)) / (-\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 27339 &:= \left(T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(7) + C(T(T(3)), 3)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 27341 &:= \left(T(T(T(2))) \times \left(-T(7) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 27344 &:= \left(T(T(T(2))) \times \left(-T(7) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 27474 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), 7) / 4 - T\left(T(7) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\
 27544 &:= \left(T(T(2)) + T(T(7)) + C\left(T(5) + 4, T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\
 27582 &:= \left(\left(-2 - T(T(7)) + C\left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \times T(T(2)) \right) \\
 27587 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(2)) \times \left(T(T(7)) - C\left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) + 7 \right) \\
 27628 &:= \left(T\left(T(2) + T(7)\right) + C\left(T(6) - 2, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 27896 &:= \left(-\left(T(T(2)) + T(7)\right) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(6) \right) \right) \\
 27899 &:= \left(-\left(T(2) + T(7)\right) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \right) \\
 27925 &:= \left(T(T(T(2))) \times C\left(7 \times \sqrt{9}, T(2)\right) - 5 \right) \\
 27929 &:= \left(T(T(2)) - 7 + \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(2)\right) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \right) \\
 27930 &:= \left(C\left(T(2) \times 7, \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(T(3+0)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27943 &:= \left((27 \times T(T(9))) - \sqrt{C(4,3)} \right) \\
 27949 &:= \left((27 \times T(T(9))) + C(4, \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 27974 &:= \left((T(T(2)) \times (7 \times T(C(9,7)))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 27986 &:= \left(2 \times \left(C(7, T(\sqrt{9})) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 28255 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(2))) \times C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(2)\right) \right) + T((5 \times 5)) \right) \\
 28329 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (2) + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) + (C(T(T(3)), T(2))) \right) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 28369 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times (T(T(3)) + C(T(6), \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 28371 &:= \left(T(T(T(2))) \times \left(C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 3\right) + T((7-1)) \right) \right) \\
 28384 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + T(T(8)) \right) + \left(T(T(T(3))) \times T\left(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4})\right) \right) \right) \\
 28414 &:= \left(- (T(T(2))) + \left(C(8,4) \times T\left(T\left(\left(1 + T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 28431 &:= \left((T(2) + T(8)) \times \left(T(\sqrt{4})^{T(C(3,1))} \right) \right) \\
 28442 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (T(T(2))) - T\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)})\right) \right) \times \left(-C(T(4), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 28524 &:= \left((T(T(2)) \times T((-8) + C(T(5), 2))) + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 28551 &:= \left(T(T(T(T(2)))) + \left(\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)})\right) + 5 \right) \times T(T(C(5,1))) \right) \right) \\
 28561 &:= (T(T(T(2))) - 8) \sqrt{-5+T(C(6,1))} \\
 28584 &:= \left((T(T(2)) \times (T(C(8,5)) - 8)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 28598 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(8 \times \left(5 + T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 28625 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + T\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)})\right) \right) \times (T(C(6,2)) + (5)) \right) \\
 28843 &:= \left(C\left(\left(- (2) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T((T(T(4)) + 3)) \right) \\
 28952 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(T(2)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T(T(9)) \right) \times (-T((5+2))) \right) \\
 28999 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + \left(C(8, T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(9)) \right) \right) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 29970 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(2) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T((C(9,7) + 0)) \right) \\
 31395 &:= \left(C(T((T(3) + 1)), T(3)) / \left(- (\sqrt{9} - T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 31548 &:= \left(\left(T((T(T(3)) + 1)) + C(T(5), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 31824 &:= C\left(\left(T(3) \times \sqrt{1+8}\right), (T(2) + (4))\right) \\
 31845 &:= \left(T(T(3)) + \left(C\left(18, \left(\sqrt{4} + (5)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 32334 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) \times T\left(T\left(C\left((2+3), 3\right)\right)\right)\right) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\
 32339 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) \times T\left(T\left(T\left((-2) + T(3)\right)\right)\right)\right) - C\left(3, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 32359 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) - 2\right) - \left(-\left(T(T(3))\right) \times T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 32384 &:= \left(C\left(\left(T(T(3)) + T(2)\right), 3\right) \times \left(8 \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 32486 &:= \left(C\left(T(3), T(2)\right) - \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(4)\right)\right) + \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times \left(-T(6)\right)\right)\right) \\
 32488 &:= \left(-\left(C\left(T(3), T(2)\right)\right) + \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(4)\right)\right) + 8\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \\
 32564 &:= \left(\left(T(3) + \left(2^{T(5)}\right)\right) - C\left(T(6), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 32574 &:= \left(3 + \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right) + \left(T\left(T(5)\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 32578 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \times \left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right) + \left(T\left(T(5)\right)\right)\right)\right) + C\left(7, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \\
 32754 &:= \left(-\left(\left(\left(T(3) \times T(2)\right) - C\left(T(7), 5\right)\right) / T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\
 32869 &:= \left(-\left(T\left(T(3)\right)\right) + \left(C\left(\sqrt{T(2)^{\sqrt{T(8)}}}, 6\right) / 9\right)\right) \\
 32883 &:= \left(-3 + \left(\sqrt{T(2)^8} \times T\left(C(8, T(3))\right)\right)\right) \\
 32884 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(\left(T\left(T(3)\right) / T(2)\right)\right), T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) / T(8)\right) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\
 32886 &:= \left(\sqrt{C(3, 2)^8} \times T\left(C(8, 6)\right)\right) \\
 33244 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), 3\right) \times \left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right) + 4\right)\right) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\
 33247 &:= \left(-3 - \left(C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), T(2)\right) \times \left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - T(7)\right)\right)\right) \\
 33434 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(3) \times T(3)\right)\right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{C\left(T(3), \sqrt{4}\right)}\right)\right)\right) \\
 33439 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(3)\right)\right) - \left(\left(T\left(T(3)\right) \times T\left(T\left(T(4)\right)\right)\right) + \left(C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 33453 &:= \left(\left(-3 + T\left(C\left(\left(T(3) + \sqrt{4}\right), 5\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) \\
 33474 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), 4\right) - T\left(T(7)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 33882 &:= \left(-33 + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 8\right) / T\left(T(2)\right)\right)\right) \\
 33884 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T(3)\right) - \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), 8\right) / \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T(4)\right)\right)\right) \\
 33887 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left((3+3)\right), 8\right) / \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T(7)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33893 &:= \left(\left((-T(3)) + C(T(T(3)), 8) \right) / T(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(3)) \right) \\
 33914 &:= \left((-T(3)) + C(T(T(3)), (9-1)) \right) / T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 33918 &:= \left(3 + \left(C(T(T(3)), (9-1)) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 33937 &:= \left(-C(T(3), 3) + \left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 33954 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)) + C(9, 5) \right) - T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 34299 &:= - \left(T(T(3)) - \left(C(4^2, 9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 34338 &:= \left(- \left(T(3^4) \times T(3) \right) + C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 34349 &:= \left(-T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4))) + \left(C(T(T(3)), 4) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 34384 &:= \left(3 + T(T(T(4)) - T(3)) \right) \times C(8, \sqrt{4}) \\
 34452 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), 4) - T(\sqrt{4})^5 \right) \times T(T(2)) \\
 34464 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), 4) - T(4) - T(T(6)) \right) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 34476 &:= \left(T(T(3)) - T(C(T(4), \sqrt{4})) \right) \times (-T(7) + (6)) \\
 34565 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})) \times (5 + T(6)) - T(5) \right) \\
 34578 &:= \left(-T(3) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + (-C(T(5), 7) + T(T(8))) \right) \\
 34645 &:= \left((3 \times T(T(4))) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) - (5) \right) \\
 34665 &:= C(C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4})), 6) - T(6 \times T(5)) \\
 34713 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{4} + T(C(7, 1) + 3)) \\
 34720 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(7)) \right) \times 20 \\
 34784 &:= - \left(T(3) - \left((\sqrt{4} \times 7) \times T(C(8, 4)) \right) \right) \\
 34794 &:= - \left(T(T(3)) - \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(C(7, \sqrt{9})) \right) \times T(T(4)) \right) \\
 34827 &:= T(T(T(3)) / T(\sqrt{4})) + C(T(8) / 2, 7) \\
 34839 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), 4) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(3) - T(T(9)) \right) \\
 34859 &:= - \left(T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8)) \times T(C(5, \sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 34896 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), 4) \times \sqrt{T(8)} - T(T(9)) \right) + T(6) \right) \\
 34924 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) / T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4))) \\
 34937 &:= T(T(3)) + \left((\sqrt{4} + C(9, 3)) \times T(T(7)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34995 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(T(3)), 4) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - T(T(9)) \right) + T(T(5)) \right) \\
 35184 &:= \left(T(3) \times \left(-((T(T(5)) + 1)) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 4\right) \right) \right) \\
 35420 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \right) \times 20 \right) \\
 35423 &:= \left(3 + \left(T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \times 23 \right) \right) \\
 35426 &:= \left(T(3) + \left(T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \times (2 + T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 35493 &:= \left(3 + \left(C\left(T(5), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times T((9 + 3)) \right) \right) \\
 35499 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) - \left(\left(C\left(T(5), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) - T(T(9)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 35684 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(3))) - 5 \right) - \left(6 \times C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 4\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 35894 &:= \left(-((T(T(3)) - 5)) + \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 4\right) \right) \right) \\
 35929 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(3) + T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times \left(-2 + T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \right) \\
 35953 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), 5\right) - T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) + \left(5^{T(3)} \right) \right) \\
 35953 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), 5\right) - T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) + \left(5^{T(3)} \right) \right) \\
 35995 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) + 5^{T(\sqrt{9})} \right) + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 5\right) \right) \\
 36423 &:= \left(\left(3 + C\left(T(6), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \times T\left(T(2) \times T(3)\right) \right) \\
 36477 &:= \left(T(T(3)) + \left(\left(C\left(T(6), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) - T(7) \right) \times T(7) \right) \right) \\
 36897 &:= \left(T(T(3)) \times \left(\left(T(T(6)) + C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 37128 &:= \left(3 \times C\left(\left(7 + T\left(1 + T(2)\right)\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 37143 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times (-7) \right) + C\left(\left(-1 + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(3)\right) \right) \\
 37228 &:= \left(-T(3) - \left(\left(-T(7) \right) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(2)\right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 37234 &:= \left(-T(3) + \left(T(7) \times C\left(T\left(2 \times 3\right), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 37324 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) + 7 \right) \times \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(2)\right) + T\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \right) \right) \\
 37425 &:= \left(3 + \left(-\left(C\left(T(7), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \times \left(T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 37464 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), 7\right) / T\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \right) - \left(6^4 \right) \right) \\
 37597 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) \times C\left(T(7) - 5, \sqrt{9}\right) \right) + T(T(7)) \right) \\
 37639 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(T(7) \times \left(C\left(T(6), 3\right) + T\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 37674 &:= \left(\left(3 \times C\left(T(7), 6\right) \right) / \left(T(7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 37697 &:= C\left(\sqrt{-T(3)+T(T(7))}, 6\right) - T(T(9)) - T(7) \\
 37822 &:= \left(-T(3) + \left(T(7) \times \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(2)\right) + T(T(T(2)))\right)\right)\right) \\
 37884 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), 7) - T((T(8) + T(8)))\right) / T(\sqrt{4})\right) \\
 37940 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), 7) / \sqrt{9}\right) - T(40)\right) \\
 37945 &:= \left(\left(3 \times C\left(T(7) - \sqrt{9}, 4\right)\right) - (5)\right) \\
 37965 &:= \left(3 \times \left(C\left(T(7) - \sqrt{9}, T(6)\right) + (5)\right)\right) \\
 38112 &:= \left(-3 + \left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C(11, T(2))\right)\right) \\
 38118 &:= \left(3 - \left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times (-C(11, 8))\right)\right) \\
 38199 &:= \left(-T((-3) + T(8)) + C\left((-1) + T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \\
 38289 &:= \left(-T(3) + \left(\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(T(2))\right) + T(8)\right) \times T(T(9))\right)\right) \\
 38298 &:= \left(-T(3) + \left(T(C(8, T(2))) \times (\sqrt{9} \times 8)\right)\right) \\
 38319 &:= \left(\left(-T(T(3)) \times T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)) - 1, T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right)\right) \\
 38339 &:= -\left(\left(T(T(T(3))) - (8 + T(T(3))) \times C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 38346 &:= \left(\left(3 \times C(8, 3) - \sqrt{4}\right) \times T(T(6))\right) \\
 38388 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) + T(C(8, 3))\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \\
 38396 &:= \left(T(T(3)) + 8\right) \times \left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}\right) - (6)\right) \\
 38429 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) \times T\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(4)\right)\right)\right) - C\left(T(2), \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 38483 &:= \left(\left(3 - C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times (-8 - T(T(3)))\right) \\
 38483 &:= \left(\left(3 - C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times (-8 - T(T(3)))\right) \\
 38523 &:= -\left(\left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - C\left(T(T(5)) / T(T(2)), T(3)\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 38574 &:= \left(T(3) \times (-8) + \left(C(T(5), 7) + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 38584 &:= \left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - \left(\left(5\sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T(T(4))\right)\right) \\
 38589 &:= \left(-3 + \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times \left(C(T(5), 8) - \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 38648 &:= \left(\left(T(3)\sqrt{T(8)}\right) - C\left((6 + T(4)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38679 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{3^8} - \left(C(T(6), 7) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 38683 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), (6+8) \right) \right) / (-3) \right) \\
 38683 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), (6+8) \right) \right) / (-3) \right) \\
 38722 &:= \left(- (38) + C \left(\sqrt{T(T(7)) - T(T(2))}, T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 38732 &:= \left(- (T(T(3))) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 7 \right) - (T(T(3))) \right) / T(2) \right) \right) \\
 38738 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (3) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 7 \right) \right) / 3 \right) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 38742 &:= \left(3 + \left(C \left((- (8) + T(7)), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \\
 38747 &:= \left(- (T(3)) + \left(C \left((- (8) + T(7)), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - 7 \right) \right) \\
 38749 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (T(3)) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 7 \right) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 9 \right) \\
 38753 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(7) \right) \right) - T(C(5,3)) \right) \\
 38754 &:= \left(- (T(3)) + C \left((- (8) + T(7)), T \left(\sqrt{5+4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 38757 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(3)) - \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (T(7) + C(T(5), 7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38758 &:= \left(\left(- (T(3)) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 7 \right) \right) / (- (5-8)) \right) \\
 38759 &:= \left(- (T(3)) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 7 \right) + T(5) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 38772 &:= \left(- (T(3)) \times \left(\sqrt{T(8)} - (T(7) \times T(C(7,2))) \right) \right) \\
 38773 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(7) \right) \right) - C(7,3) \right) \\
 38778 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(- ((3-8)) \right), 7 \right) + T(7) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 38781 &:= \left(T(T(3)) - \left(C \left((- (8) + T(7)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times (-1) \right) \right) \\
 38783 &:= \left(T(T(3)) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 7 \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / 3 \right) \right) \\
 38783 &:= \left(T(T(3)) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 7 \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / 3 \right) \right) \\
 38784 &:= \left(T(T(3)) + \left(C \left((- (8) + T(7)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 38787 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(7) \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) \right) \\
 38789 &:= \left((T(T(3)) + 8) + C \left((T(7) - 8), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38794 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(3)) - \left(C((-8) + T(7)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 38823 &:= \left(\left(3 \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) + \left(C\left(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2)), T(3)\right) \right) \right) \\
 38991 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + C\left(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{C(9,1)})\right) \right) \\
 38999 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(8 + C\left(C(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \right) \\
 39166 &:= \left(T\left(T\left(\left(T(T(3)) / \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) + \left(C((-1) + T(6)), 6\right) \right) \\
 39187 &:= \left(T(T(3)) + \left(C\left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 1\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + \left(T(T(7))\right) \right) \right) \\
 39225 &:= \left(C\left(C(T(3), \sqrt{9}), T(T(2))\right) + T(2 \times T(5)) \right) \\
 39269 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(T(3)) - \left(T(C(9, T(2))) \times T(T(6)) \right) \right) / T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 39284 &:= \left(- \left(C(T(3), \sqrt{9}) \right) + \left((-2) + T(8) \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \\
 39292 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) / T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times \left(2 + T(C(9, T(2))) \right) \right) \\
 39348 &:= - \left(\left(T(3) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(C(3, \sqrt{4})^8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39359 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(3))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \left(C((3 + T(5)), 9) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39386 &:= \left(C(T(3), \sqrt{9}) + \left(\left(3^8 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 39387 &:= \left(T(T(3)) + \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(3^{C(8,7)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 39397 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(C\left(C(T(\sqrt{9}), 3), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 39414 &:= \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + \left(- \left(T(4) \times T((-1) + T(T(4))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39428 &:= \left(C\left(C(T(3), \sqrt{9}), T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right) + \left(2 + T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 39473 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times T\left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right)\right) \right) - T(C(7, T(3))) \right) \\
 39492 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) + \left(9^4 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) \\
 39537 &:= \left(- \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) - \left(T(5) \right) \right) + \left(T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39585 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(3)) \times \left(T(\sqrt{9}) - \left(T((5 + C(8,5))) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39669 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(3)) - \left(\left(9 \times T(6) \right) \times T\left(C(6, \sqrt{9})\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39732 &:= \left(T(T(3)) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(C(7,3)) \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 39794 &:= - \left(\left(T(T((3+9))) - \left(C(7, \sqrt{9})^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \right) \right) \\
 39885 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(T(8) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left(T(5) \right) \right) \\
 39895 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(T(8) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - \left(5 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39900 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{900} \\
 39997 &:= \left(T \left(\left(C \left(3, \sqrt{9} \right) + T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(9 + T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 40656 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(C \left(T \left(06 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(6 \right) \right) \\
 40698 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times C \left(T \left(06 \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 8 \right) \right) \\
 41245 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) + \left(T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) + T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 41388 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(3 \right) + T \left(\left(T \left(8 \right) + T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 41667 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 41775 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 - \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 41847 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-7 \right) \\
 41987 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(4 - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) / \left(-7 \right) \\
 41994 &:= \left(4 + \left(C \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) / 4 \\
 41997 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) / \left(-7 \right) \\
 42259 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(2 \times C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 42291 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(2 \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(C \left(9, 1 \right) \right) \\
 42294 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T \left(C \left(4, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 42334 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(C \left(4, 2 \right) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 42339 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(C \left(4, 2 \right) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \\
 42351 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(2 \right) \times T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(C \left(5, 1 \right) \right) \\
 42391 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{C \left(9, 1 \right)} \right) \\
 42414 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 41 \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 42468 &:= \left(C \left(\left(4 \times T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4 + T \left(6 \right)} - T \left(8 \right) \\
 42485 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 42495 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(4 \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 42498 &:= \left(C \left(\left(4 \times T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(4 - 9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \\
 42515 &:= C \left(4 \times T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{1 + T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right)} \\
 42519 &:= \left(C \left(\left(4 \times T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42525 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4})^{T(2)} \right) \times (C(T(5), 2) \times T(5)) \right) \\
 42539 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) - \left((2^5) \times C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 42546 &:= \left(C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + (\sqrt{4} \times T(6)) \right) \\
 42559 &:= \left(C((4 \times T(T(2))), 5) + T(C(5, \sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 42562 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((2^5) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 42563 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + \left((2^5) \times C(T(6), 3) \right) \right) \\
 42688 &:= \left((4^{T(2)}) \times \left(C(6, \sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 42739 &:= - \left(\left(T(4^2) \right) - \left(C(7, 3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 42749 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(T(2))) \right) - \left(C(7, 4)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 42855 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + C\left(T(2) \times \sqrt{T(8)}, 5\right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 42946 &:= \left(T(T((T(4) + T(2)))) + \left(C(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})), 6) \right) \right) \\
 42959 &:= \left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(2))) \right) \times \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 5) / 9 \right) \right) \\
 42964 &:= \left(\left((T(T(C(4, 2))) - T(9)) \times T(T(6)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 42969 &:= \left(\left((T(T(C(4, 2))) - T(9)) \times T(T(6)) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 42995 &:= \left(\left(C((4 + T(2)), \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + T(T(5)) \right) \\
 42998 &:= \left(-T(4) + \left((2^9) \times C(9, \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \\
 43243 &:= \left(\left((C(T(4), T(3)) - 2)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - T(T(3)) \right) \\
 43344 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times T(T(3)) \right) \times \left(-3 + T(C(T(4), \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 43374 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4}))^{T(3)} \right) - \left(T(3) + C(T(7), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 43428 &:= \left(\left((C(T(4), T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} - T(T(2))) - T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 43434 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} - T((T(3))^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \\
 43434 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} - T((T(3))^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \\
 43454 &:= \left(\left(T((T(T(4)) - 3) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 5)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 43463 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) + \left((T(T(3))^{T(\sqrt{4})}) - C(T(6), T(3)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43482 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((T(T(3)) \times T(C(T(4), 8))) + T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 43484 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + (3 + T(4)) \right) \times C(8, \sqrt{4})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43485 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times T(T(3)) \right) \times T(C(T(4), 8)) \right) + T(5) \right) \\
 43524 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) + C((T(5) + T(2)), T(4)) \right) \\
 43527 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) - C((3 + T(5)), (T(2) + (7))) \right) \right) \\
 43548 &:= \left(- (C(T(4), T(3))) + C \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 8 \right) \right) \\
 43639 &:= - \left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{4})), 3) - ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) \times 9) \right) \right) \\
 43681 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{C(4,3)^6} \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 43685 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{C(4,3)^6} \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + 5 \right) \\
 43694 &:= \left(- \left(4^3 \right) + C \left(\left(T(6) - \sqrt{9} \right), T(4) \right) \right) \\
 43698 &:= - \left(\left((T(4) \times T(3)) - C \left(\left(T(6) - \sqrt{9} \right), 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 43758 &:= C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(3^{7-5} \right) \right), 8 \right) \\
 43779 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), T((T(7)/7)) \right) + T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 43794 &:= \left(\left(T(T(C(4,3))) - \left(T(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times \left(-\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43799 &:= \left(4 \times T(T(T(3))) + \left(C(7, \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 43813 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + T(T((1+3))) \right) \\
 43814 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + 1 \right) + T(T(4)) \right) \\
 43822 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + \left(2^{T(T(2))} \right) \right) \\
 43834 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + T(T(3)) \right) + T(T(4)) \right) \\
 43834 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + T(T(3)) \right) + T(T(4)) \right) \\
 43836 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + T((T(3) + (6))) \right) \\
 43849 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + T((4+9)) \right) \\
 43862 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(T(T(3)) - \left(C(8, 6)^{T(2)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43869 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 3 \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (T(T(6)) \times T(9)) \right) \\
 43878 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + T((7+8)) \right) \\
 43893 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + (T(9) \times 3) \right) \\
 43894 &:= \left(T((T(4) + T(3))) + C \left(\sqrt{T(8) \times 9}, T(4) \right) \right) \\
 43914 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right), T(3) \right) - (T(T(9)) \times T((1 \times 4))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43925 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(4)) - \left(\left(T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \right)^2 \right) - T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 43934 &:= \left((-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))) \right) + C\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(3), T(4)\right) \\
 43934 &:= \left((-T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))) \right) + C\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(3), T(4)\right) \\
 43968 &:= \left(C(T(4), T(3)) + C\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6, 8\right) \right) \\
 43986 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) - C\left(T(3) \times \sqrt{9}, 8\right) \right) - T(T(6)) \right) \\
 43996 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{4}) \times C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}\right) + \left(T(\sqrt{9})^6\right) \right) \\
 44094 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) - \left(C(T(4), T(\sqrt{09})) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 44187 &:= \left(T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) + \left(T((T(4) + 1)) \times T(T(C(8,7))) \right) \\
 44220 &:= \left(T(C(\sqrt{4} + T(4), 2)) \right) \times 20 \\
 44284 &:= \left(\left(C\left(4 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right), T(T(2)) \right) + T(8) \right) / 4 \\
 44285 &:= \left(-\left(T(4)^4\right) + T(T(T(2))) \right) + C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(5)\right) \\
 44289 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(C(4,2)) \right) \times T((-8) + T(9)) \\
 44325 &:= - \left(\left(T(C(T(4), \sqrt{4})) - \left(T\left(3^{T(2)}\right) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44329 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(C(T(4), T(3))^2 \right) \right) + T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 44358 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) - \left(C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 44424 &:= \left(T(T((4+4))) + C\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(2)), T(4)\right) \right) \\
 44425 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + T(25) \right) \\
 44444 &:= \left(\left(\left(C\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 4\right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \times T(4) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 44444 &:= \left(\left(\left(C\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 4\right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \times T(4) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 44497 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(4), 4)^{\sqrt{4}} - 9 \right) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 44499 &:= \left(\left(T(C(T(4), \sqrt{4})) \times \left(-(\sqrt{4} - T(9)) \right) \right) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 44521 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(4)\right) + T(T(5)) \right)^{C(2,1)} \right) \\
 44528 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) / \sqrt{4} \right) + C\left(T(5) + T(2), 8\right) \right) \\
 44584 &:= \left(C\left(4 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})), 5\right) + \left(T(\sqrt{8^4})\right) \right) \\
 44631 &:= \left(T\left(\sqrt{4} + T(T(4))\right) \right) \times \left(T(6) + T(C(3,1)) \right) \\
 44632 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right)^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))} - C\left(T(6) + 3, T(2)\right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44649 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{T(4)} \right) - C(T(6), 4) \right) \times (-9) \right) \\
 44681 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (T(6) + C(8, 1))) \right) \\
 44694 &:= \left(((- (T(T(4))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 6) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44827 &:= \left(T(T(4)) + \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + T(C(8, T(2))) \right) \times T(7) \right) \right) \\
 44844 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} - C((T(8) - T(4)), 4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44844 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} - C((T(8) - T(4)), 4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44845 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times C(-((T(4) - T(8))), 4) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 44849 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + 8 \right) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} - T(9) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44854 &:= \left(4 + \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 5 \right), 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 44923 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + C \left(T(4), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 - T(T(3)) \right) \\
 44928 &:= \left(\left(4^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \times (T(C(9, 2)) + T(8)) \right) \\
 44969 &:= \left(- (T(T(4))) + \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) \times \left(-T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T(6), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44998 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(T(4)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times T(C(9, 8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45024 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) - (T(T(02)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\
 45039 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - (C(T(5), T(03)) \times 9) \right) \right) \\
 45087 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + (C(T(5), 08)) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 45099 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + (C(T(5), 09)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 45135 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + C(T(5), T((1+3))) \right) \times T(5) \right) \\
 45215 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) / T(T(2)) \right) - 1 \right) \times 5 \\
 45224 &:= \left(4 + \left(5 \times \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T(T(2)) \right) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45234 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times \left((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T(T(3))) \times T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 45235 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) / T(T(2)) \right) + 3 \right) \times 5 \\
 45294 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) - (T(T(2)) \times (- (T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 45345 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(T(C(5, 3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \times T(5) \right) \\
 45397 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - (C(T(5), T(3))) \right) \times (-9) \right) + (T(T(7))) \right) \\
 45457 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + ((C(T(5), T(4)) \times T(5)) + T(T(7))) \right) \\
 45464 &:= \left(\left((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(5)))) / T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T(6), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 45494 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(9 \right) + T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45539 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(- \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) + 3 \right), 9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45657 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(\left(5^{C(6,5)} \right) - T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45672 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(- \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45673 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(- \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45679 &:= \left(4 + \left(- \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45722 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), 2 \right) + T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45723 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), 2 \right) + 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 45724 &:= \left(4 + \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), 2 \right) + T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45738 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4+5} \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 45743 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(4 \right)^5 \right) + 7 \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 45982 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 46189 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(1 \right) + T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)}, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 46212 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(- \left(C \left(6, 2 \right) \times T \left(T \left(12 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 46271 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)^6 + T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(C \left(7, 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 46344 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(3, \sqrt{4} \right) \right)^{T(4)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 46423 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(C \left(4, 2 \right) \right)^{T(3)} \right) \right) \\
 46428 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(4, 2 \right) \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 46431 &:= \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 64 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(C \left(3, 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 46437 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(T \left(6 \right) \times T \left(T \left(\left(C \left(4, 3 \right) + 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 46443 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)^6 - \left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), 4 \right) + 3 \right) \right) \\
 46444 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)^6 - \left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), 4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 46448 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)^6 - \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + C \left(T \left(4 \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 46512 &:= \left(C \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T \left(6 \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) \times \left(1 + T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 46524 &:= \left(\left(C \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T \left(6 \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) + T \left(2 \right) \right) \times 4 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46552 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} + T(6)) \times C((T(T(5))/5), T(2)) \right) \\
 46650 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4}))^6 \right) - (C(6,5) + 0) \right) \\
 46686 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((6^6) + C(8,6) \right) \right) \\
 46692 &:= \left(T((\sqrt{4} + (6))) + \left(6^{\sqrt{C(9,2)}} \right) \right) \\
 46734 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4}))^6 \right) + C((7 + T(3)), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 46754 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4}))^6 \right) + (-7) + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 46832 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + ((T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(C(T(3), T(2)))) \right) \\
 46833 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + ((T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(C(T(3), 3))) \right) \\
 46839 &:= \left(C((T(\sqrt{4}) \times 6), 8) + T(T((3 + 9))) \right) \\
 46869 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + \left((6^{\sqrt{T(8)}}) + T(C(6, \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 46971 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4}))^6 \right) + (T(9) \times C(7,1)) \right) \\
 46984 &:= \left(4 \times \left((T(6)^{\sqrt{9}}) + T(C(8,4)) \right) \right) \\
 47253 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) - (C(T(7), 2) \times (-5^3)) \right) \\
 47256 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + (C(T(7), 2) \times \sqrt{5^6}) \right) \\
 47284 &:= \left((-\sqrt{4}) + T(C(7, T(2))) + (T(8)^{T(\sqrt{4})}) \right) \\
 47289 &:= \left((T(\sqrt{4}) + T(C(7, T(2)))) + (T(8)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 47475 &:= \left((T(\sqrt{4}) + (T(C(7,4)))) \times 75 \right) \\
 47492 &:= \left(-(T(4)) + (T(T(7)) \times (C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) - T(2))) \right) \\
 47789 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times (-T(7)) \right) - \left(7 - C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 47849 &:= \left(-((T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7))) + (T(8) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), \sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 47869 &:= \left(-((4 + 7)) + (T(8) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 47954 &:= \left(C(-((T(4) - T(7))), 9) - T(T((5 + T(\sqrt{4})))) \right) \\
 47957 &:= \left((T(\sqrt{4}) - T(T(7))) \times (-C(9,5) - 7) \right) \\
 47979 &:= \left((-C(T(4), 7) \times (T(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(7)))) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 47986 &:= \left(C((T(\sqrt{4}) \times 7), \sqrt{9}) + (\sqrt{T(8)^6}) \right) \\
 47992 &:= \left(4 \times (T(7) + (9 \times C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(2)))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47993 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(4)) - \left(C(7+9), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(3) \right) \right) \\
 48104 &:= \left(C \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (T(T(10)) \times 4) \right) \\
 48141 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right)^{\sqrt{T(8)}} + T((-1) + T(T(C(4,1)))) \right) \\
 48242 &:= \left((-T(4)) + T(C(8, T(2))) \right) + \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right)^{T(T(2))} \\
 48248 &:= \left((-4) + T(C(8, T(2))) \right) + \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right)^{\sqrt{T(8)}} \\
 48264 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(4)\sqrt{T(8)}} \times (-T(T(2))) \right) + C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 48272 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(T(T(2))) \right) - 7 \right) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) \\
 48286 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)})^2 \right) + T(T((-8) + T(6))) \right) \\
 48321 &:= \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + \left(T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3)) \times (T(T(T(2))) - 1) \right) \right) \\
 48324 &:= \left((T(T(4)) \times (T(8) \times (-3))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 48352 &:= \left(-4 + \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) - (C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \right) \right) \\
 48354 &:= \left(- \left(\left((T(\sqrt{4}) - T(C(8, T(3)))) \times T(T(5)) \right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 48358 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) - \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48359 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) - (C(T(5), 9)) \right) \right) \\
 48372 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right)^{\sqrt{T(8)}} + C((T(3) + 7), T(T(2))) \right) \\
 48384 &:= \left((4+8)^3 \times C(8, \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 48384 &:= \left((4+8)^3 \times C(8, \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 48393 &:= \left(\left(4 + C \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times 3 \right), 9 \right) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \\
 48432 &:= - \left(\left((T(4) + 8)^{T(\sqrt{4})} - C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) \right) \right) \\
 48445 &:= \left(\left(T(4) \times C \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 4 \right) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 48446 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{T(8)}} + (-C(T(4), 4) \times T(T(6))) \right) \right) \\
 48447 &:= \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times \left(T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(T(\sqrt{4})^7 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48464 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(T(T(6)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 48485 &:= \left(- (T(4)) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - T(5) \right) \right) \\
 48486 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times (-8) \right) + \left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 48493 &:= \left(\left(4 - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left(- \left(C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 48526 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(8 - \left(- \left(C(T(5), 2) \right) \times T(T(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48538 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) + \left(T(T((8+5))) - C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48539 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})}^8 - C((T(5)+3), 9) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48548 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(T(8) - C \left((T(5) + \sqrt{4}), 8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48638 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + C(T(6), 3) \right) \times (-T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 48646 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(6)) \right) + T((T(4) + (6))) \right) \\
 48659 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(4)) + \left(- \left(T(C(8,6)) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 48663 &:= \left(T \left(\left(- (4) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - \left(T(T(6)) \times (-T(C(6,3))) \right) \right) \\
 48696 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(6)) \right) - T(9) \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \\
 48734 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(8 + \left(T(T(7)) \times T \left(C \left(T(3), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48743 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left(T(T(7)) \times (-C(T(4), 3)) \right) \right) \\
 48747 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})}^{\sqrt{T(8)}} - \left(T(T(7)) \times (-C(T(4), 7)) \right) \right) \\
 48749 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(8 - \left(T(T(7)) \times \left(-C \left(T(4), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48834 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(T(T(8)) + C((8+T(T(3))), 4) \right) \right) \\
 48843 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{T(8)}} \times \left(C(8,4) - 3 \right) \right) \\
 48854 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(T(8) \times \left(8 - C(T(5), 4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48899 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8)) \right) \times C(8, \sqrt{9}) \right) - T(9) \\
 48916 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) + T(T((1+6))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48917 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) + (1 + T(T(7))) \right) \\
 48960 &:= \left(C \left((T(4) + 8), \sqrt{9} \right) \times 60 \right) \\
 48968 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (4) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \right) / (-6) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 48979 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(4) \right) \right) + T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T(7) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48982 &:= \left(\left(- (\sqrt{4}) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) - T(8) \right) \right) / T(T(2)) \right) \\
 48983 &:= \left(- (4) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) - 8 \right) / T(3) \right) \right) \\
 48985 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (T(4)) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \right) / \left(-\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 48990 &:= \left(\left(- (T(4)) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \right) / \left(-T \left(\sqrt{9+0} \right) \right) \right) \\
 48991 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (T(4)) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \right) / \left(-T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 48992 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (4) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \right) / \left(-T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + T(2) \right) \\
 49152 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{C(9,1)+5} \right) \times T(2) \right) \\
 49163 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (1 + T(C(6,3))) \right) \\
 49189 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times (1 + T(8)) - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49195 &:= \left(T(T(4)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T(5) \right) \right) \\
 49247 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (T(4)) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + (T(T(7))) \right) \\
 49253 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(T(2)) \right) - \left(C \left(T(5), T(3) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49257 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{9} \right) - T(2) \right) \times (T(5) + T(T(7))) \right) \\
 49259 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{4 \times 9} \right), T(T(2)) \right) - C \left(T(5), 9 \right) \right) \\
 49268 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) \times (-T(68)) \right) \right) \\
 49314 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(- \left(T(3) - T(14) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49332 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right), T(3) \right) / T(3) - T(2) \right) \right) \\
 49333 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(C \left((9 \times 3), T(3) \right) / T(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49334 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right), T(3) \right) - (T(3)) \right) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49335 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right), T(3) \right) / C(T(3), 5) \right) \\
 49336 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right), T(3) \right) + (T(3)) \right) / 6 \right) \\
 49338 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) - \left(- (C((9 \times 3), T(3))) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 49339 &:= \left(4 - \left(- (C((9 \times 3), T(3))) / T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 49345 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(T(3))) + 4) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 49347 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + ((T(T(9)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(4)) / (-7)))) \right) \right) \\
 49349 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4})^{T(\sqrt{9})} \right) + C \left((T(3) \times T(\sqrt{4})), 9 \right) \right) \\
 49359 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(\sqrt{9})) - T(-((T(T(3)) - T(T(5)))))) \right) + T(9) \right) \\
 49371 &:= \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times ((C(9, 3) \times T(7)) - 1) \right) \\
 49374 &:= \left(T((4 \times \sqrt{9})) \times (3 + T(C(7, 4))) \right) \\
 49416 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (1 + T(T(6))) \right) \\
 49432 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})) + 4 \right) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 49434 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{4 \times 9})) \times (C(T(4), T(3)) + (4)) \right) \\
 49444 &:= \left(T(4) + \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times (C(T(4), 4) + (4)) \right) \right) \\
 49468 &:= \left(4 \times \left(- (9) + C \left((- (4) + T(6)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49483 &:= \left(\left(4 \times C \left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - (T(T(3))) \right) \\
 49528 &:= \left(4 \times \left(T(\sqrt{9}) + C \left((T(5) + 2), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49546 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 9) / 5 \right) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (-6)) \right) \\
 49560 &:= \left(C(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})) \times (5 + T(T((6 + 0)))) \right) \\
 49598 &:= \left(- (T(4)) + \left(T \left((- (\sqrt{9}) + T(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \times T(8) \right) \\
 49623 &:= \left(\left((- (\sqrt{4}) + T(T(9))) + C(T(6), T(2)) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \\
 49634 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) \times (-\sqrt{9}) \right) + ((C(T(6), T(3)) - T(4))) \right) \\
 49642 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) \times (-\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 49643 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) - \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 6) - T(T((4 \times 3))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49649 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) - \left(T(T(9)) + C \left((T(6) - T(\sqrt{4})), 9 \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49655 &:= \left(- (4) + \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9})^6 \right) + C(T(5), 5) \right) \right) \\
 49666 &:= \left(\left(T(T(4)) \times T \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(6) \right) \right) \right) + C(6, 6) \right) \\
 49672 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(6)) \right) + \left(T(7)^{T(2)} \right) \right) \\
 49729 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(C(9, 7)) \right)^2 \right) / 9 \right) \\
 49744 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(7)) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4}^{T(4)} \right) \right) \\
 49763 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{4} \times T(9)) \right) + T(T(7)) \right) - C(T(6), T(3)) \right) \\
 49794 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) \times (T(T(7)) + 9) \right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 49794 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) \times (T(T(7)) + 9) \right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 49799 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T(4) + (\sqrt{9} \times T(7)) \right) \right) + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 49893 &:= \left(C \left(T(\sqrt{4 \times 9}), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(93) \right) \\
 49923 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) + 9 \right)^2 \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 49974 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(7 \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \right) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 49976 &:= \left(- (4) + \left(C(9, \sqrt{9}) \times T((T(7) + (6))) \right) \right) \\
 49977 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + \left(T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \times -(7+7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49978 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + \left(C(9, \sqrt{9}) \times T \left(\left(T(7) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49983 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) - \left(T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \times -(8) - T(3) \right) \right) \\
 49984 &:= \left(4 - \left(- \left(C(9, \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T \left(\left(T(8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49994 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(4)^{T(\sqrt{9})} \right) / C(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9}) \right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 49994 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(4)^{T(\sqrt{9})} \right) / C(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9}) \right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 50439 &:= \left(\left(- (T(50)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 51183 &:= - \left(\left(T(T((T(5) - T((1+1)))) \right) - C \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(3) \right) \right) \\
 51239 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T((5-1)))^2 \right) - C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 51338 &:= - \left(\left(T(-((T(5) - T(13))) \right) - \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 51448 &:= \left(\left(C(T(5), (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) - 4 \right) \times 8 \\
 51474 &:= \left(T(5) \times C(14, 7) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 51489 &:= \left(C \left(T \left((5+1) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T \left((T \left(T \left(8 \right) / 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 51624 &:= \left((T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times (-1) - T \left(6 \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 51647 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(T \left(5 \right) + 1 \right)} \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - (T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right)) \right) \right) \\
 51648 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), (1+6) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \\
 51689 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left((5-1) \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) - T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 51795 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T \left(5 \right) - 1), 7 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(5 \right) \\
 51822 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(T \left(5 \right) + 1 \right)} \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) - (C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52184 &:= -T \left(\sqrt{T \left(T \left(5 \right) \times T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) + 1 \right)} + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 52239 &:= \left(- \left((T \left(5 \right) \times T \left(2 \right) \right)^2 \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 52243 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - T \left((T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right)) \right) \right) \\
 52245 &:= \left((5 + T \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right)^5 \right) \\
 52389 &:= - \left(\left(T \left((T \left(T \left(5 \right) / 2 \right) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) - T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52424 &:= - \left(\left((T \left((T \left(T \left(5 \right) / 2 \right) \right) + T \left(4 \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52427 &:= \left(- (T \left((T \left(T \left(5 \right) / 2 \right) \right)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - 7 \right) \right) \\
 52428 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(C \left(5, 2 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(- (2) + T \left(8 \right) \right) \\
 52429 &:= \left((- (5) - T \left((T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \times T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 52434 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left((5-2) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - (T \left((T \left(3 \right) \times T \left(4 \right) \right)) \right) \\
 52438 &:= - \left(\left(T \left((T \left(T \left(5 \right) / 2 \right) \right) + \left(- (4) - C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52439 &:= \left((5 - T \left((T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \times T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52441 &:= \left(\left((T \left(5 \right)^2 + (4) \right)^{\sqrt{C \left(4, 1 \right)}} \right) \\
 52449 &:= \left(T \left(5 \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T \left((T \left(4 \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right)) \right) \right) \\
 52464 &:= \left(- \left((T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times T \left((T \left(2 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(6 \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52479 &:= \left(C \left((T \left(5 \right) + T \left(2 \right)), \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 52492 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(5, 2 \right) \right) + \left((- (4) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52498 &:= \left((5 - T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 52499 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T(5)^2 \right) \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 52624 &:= \left((5 + T(T(T(2)))) \times C \left((T(6) + T(2)), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 52688 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(C(5,2))) - \left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52694 &:= \left(\left((T(5) \times (-2)) + C \left(T(6), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \\
 52724 &:= \left(C \left(T(T((5-2))), T \left(\sqrt{7+2} \right) \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \\
 52729 &:= \left((5 - T(T((T(2) + (7)))) \right) + C \left(T(T(T(2))), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 52739 &:= \left((T(5) - T(T((T(2) + (7)))) \right) + \left(C \left(T(T(3)), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 52788 &:= \left((T(T(5)) - T((2 \times T(7)))) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 52824 &:= \left(\left((T(T(5)) / T(2)) \times (-T(8)) \right) + C \left(T(T(T(2))), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52844 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), (8 - \sqrt{4}) \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 52863 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + (T(T(6)) \times (-T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 52865 &:= \left(\left(- (T(52)) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\
 52883 &:= \left(- (T(52)) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \\
 52886 &:= \left(- (T(52)) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), (T(8) / 6) \right) \right) \\
 52889 &:= \left(- (T(52)) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 52906 &:= \left(- (C(T(5), T(2))) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(06)) \right) \right) \\
 52933 &:= - \left(\left((5 + T(T(2)))^{\sqrt{9}} - C(T(T(3)), T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 52934 &:= \left(C \left(T(T((5-2))), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - C \left(T(T(3)), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 52939 &:= \left(5 + \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52953 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - (T(53)) \right) \right) \\
 52968 &:= - \left(\left((T(T(5)) + T((T(2) + T(9)))) - C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 52993 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T(T(9)) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 53145 &:= \left(T(5) + C \left(\left((T(3) - 1)^{\sqrt{4}} \right), 5 \right) \right) \\
 53183 &:= \left(- (T((T(5) + (31)))) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(3) \right) \\
 53224 &:= \left((- (5) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) - T \left(T \left((T(2))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53234 &:= \left((5 + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{3^4}\right)\right) \right) \\
 53238 &:= - \left(\left((T((T(5) + 3)) \times T(T(2))) - C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) \\
 53242 &:= \left(- (T(T(5))) + \left((T(T(T(3)))^2) + C(\sqrt{4}, 2) \right) \right) \\
 53243 &:= \left(- (T(T(5))) + \left((T(T(T(3)))^2) + \sqrt{C(4,3)} \right) \right) \\
 53244 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - T\left(C\left(T(4), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 53249 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - \left((T(4)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53298 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times T\left(T(2)\sqrt{C(9,8)}\right) \\
 53349 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), (3 \times \sqrt{4})\right) - T(T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 53387 &:= \left(5 + \left((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T\left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))}\right) \right) \right) \\
 53389 &:= \left((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C\left(8, T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 53423 &:= \left(\left(- (T((T(T(5)) / 3)) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3))) \right) \\
 53438 &:= - \left(\left(\left((T((T(T(5)) / 3)) + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) - \left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53444 &:= \left(C\left((T(5) + T(3)), T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) - (T((4 \times T(4)))) \right) \\
 53454 &:= \left(\left(C(T(5), 3) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(T(T(5)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 53459 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) - (T((-5) + T(9))) \right) \right) \\
 53489 &:= \left(5 + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) - \left(T\left((T(8) + \sqrt{9})\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53539 &:= \left(((T(T(5)) \times (-T(3))) - (5)) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 53549 &:= \left(- ((T(T(5)) - C(T(T(3)), T(5))) - T\left((T(T(4)) - T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right))\right)) \right) \\
 53559 &:= \left((T(5) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) - \left(T(T(5)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 53564 &:= - \left(\left((T((T(T(5)) / 3)) - (T(T(5)))) - C\left(T(6), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 53584 &:= \left((-5) \times T((T(T(3)) - (5))) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\
 53585 &:= \left(C(T(5), 3) + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}, 5\right) \right) \\
 53593 &:= \left((-5) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T\left((T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(3))\right) \right) \\
 53669 &:= - \left(\left(T((T(C(5,3)) - T(6))) - C\left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \right) \\
 53682 &:= \left(((- (T(T(5))) - T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(6))) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(T(2))\right) \right) \\
 53684 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C(T(T(3)), 6) - T\left((T(8) - \sqrt{4})\right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53687 &:= - \left(\left(T((T(5) + 3)) - \left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53688 &:= \left((T(5) \times T(3)) + \left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 53698 &:= \left((-5) + C(T(T(3)), 6) - T \left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - T(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53738 &:= \left((-T((5 \times 3))) - T(T(7)) + C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 53744 &:= \left(- \left((T(T(5)) - (T(3))) + T(T(7)) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53746 &:= \left((T(C(5,3)) \times 7) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 53754 &:= \left(((C(T(5), 3) - 7) \times T(T(5))) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 53768 &:= \left((-((T(5) \times T(3))) - T(T(7))) + C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 53783 &:= \left((T(5) - T((3 + T(7)))) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(3) \right) \right) \\
 53787 &:= \left(\left(T((T(5) + T(3))) - C \left(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / (-7) \right) \\
 53789 &:= \left((T(T(5)) - T((T(3) + T(7)))) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 53792 &:= \left(- \left((T((5 + T(3))) + T(T(7))) \right) + C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 53795 &:= \left(\left((T(T(C(5,3))) \times 7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 53809 &:= \left(- (C(T(5), 3) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(\sqrt{09}) \right) \right) \\
 53814 &:= \left(- (C(5,3)) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + 1 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 53816 &:= C(T(5), 3) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}} \\
 53827 &:= \left(- (T((5 \times T(3)))) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(T(2)) \right) + (T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 53828 &:= \left(\left(5 + C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left(T(T(T(2))) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 53829 &:= \left(C \left((T(5) + T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(29) \right) \\
 53837 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T(5) + T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(3)) \right) - T(T(7)) \right) \\
 53838 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(\left(- (T(T(3))) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53843 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T((4 + 3))) \right) \right) \\
 53845 &:= \left(- ((C(T(5), 3) - T(8))) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53847 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 4 \right) - T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 53849 &:= \left((5 - T(T(3))) - \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 4 \right) \times (-9) \right) \right) \\
 53854 &:= \left(- (T((5 \times T(3)))) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) + (T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 53857 &:= \left((5 - T(3)) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) - (T(T(7))) \right) \right) \\
 53858 &:= \left(C \left((T(5) + T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T((T(5) - 8))) \right) \\
 53863 &:= \left(\left(5 + C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - T(T((T(6) / 3))) \right) \\
 53864 &:= \left(- (C(T(5), 3)) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 6 \right) + (T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 53867 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (6) \right) - T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 53868 &:= \left(((-5) - T(3)) \times T(8) + C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 53871 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T((T(7) - 1)) \right) \right) \\
 53873 &:= \left(\left(T(5) + C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - T(T(C(7, T(3)))) \right) \\
 53879 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(7)) \right) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 53883 &:= \left((T(T(5)) \times (-3)) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 53886 &:= \left(C \left((T(5) + T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + (T(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53889 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + (-8) \times T(9) \right) \right) \\
 53891 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(T(5)) - C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - T \left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 1) \right) \right) \\
 53894 &:= \left(\left((T(T(C(5, 3))) \times T(8)) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \\
 53896 &:= \left(((T(T(5)) \times (-3)) - 8) + C \left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 6 \right) \right) \\
 53897 &:= \left((T(T(5)) \times (-3)) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - 7 \right) \right) \\
 53898 &:= \left((T(T(5)) \times (-3)) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 53904 &:= \left((T(T(5)) \times (-3)) + C \left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(\sqrt{04})) \right) \right) \\
 53912 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(T(5)) - \left(C \left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) \\
 53913 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(T(5)) - C \left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) - T(T(T((1 \times 3)))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53925 &:= \left(\left((T(T(5)) \times (-3)) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \right) \\
 53934 &:= \left(C(T(5) + T(3), T(\sqrt{9})) + (-T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \right) \\
 53939 &:= - \left(\left(T(5^{T(3)/\sqrt{9}}) - C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 53954 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) - T(\sqrt{5^4}) \right) \right) \\
 53957 &:= \left((T(T(5)) - T(T(3))) + \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(5)) - (T(T(7))) \right) \right) \\
 53959 &:= \left(-(5) + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) - T((T(5) + 9)) \right) \right) \\
 53969 &:= \left(5 + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) - T((T(6) + \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 53972 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(7)) \right) - T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 53974 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(7)) \right) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 53978 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) - T \left(T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53983 &:= \left(\left((-5) - T(T(T(3))) \right) - T(9) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(3) \right) \right) \\
 53988 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(\left(5 + (T(3) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 53989 &:= \left(\left(-5 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (-T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 53993 &:= \left(\left(5 + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) - T(9) \right) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \\
 53997 &:= \left(-T(5) + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + (-9) \times T(7) \right) \right) \\
 53999 &:= \left(\left(5 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times (-T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 54024 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times (-\sqrt{4}) \right) + C(T(T(T(02))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 54028 &:= \left(-5 + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(02))) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54033 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{5+4})), T(03)) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \\
 54038 &:= \left(5 + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(03)) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54039 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(5)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + C(T(T(03)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 54044 &:= - \left(\left(C(T(5), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - \left(T(\sqrt{04})^{T(4)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 54048 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{04}))) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54054 &:= \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times C(T(05), T(4)) \right) \\
 54064 &:= \left(-((5 \times 40)) + C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54089 &:= \left(-((T(T(5)) + T(T(4)))) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(08)}\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 54093 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{09})\right), T(3)\right) \right) \\
 54099 &:= \left(-T(T(5)) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(\sqrt{09})\right) - T(9) \right) \right) \\
 54122 &:= \left(\left(-T(T(5)) - T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) - \left(1 - C\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right), T\left(T(2)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54124 &:= \left(\left(-T(T(5)) - T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) - \left(-1 - C\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54128 &:= \left(-T\left(\left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{4}\right) - 1\right)\right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 54129 &:= \left(-((T(5) \times (T(4) - 1))) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 54138 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T(5)\right) - \left(C\left(T\left(T\left((4-1)\right)\right), T(3)\right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 54139 &:= \left(-\left(5^{4-1}\right) + C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 54142 &:= \left(-T\left(T(5)\right) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left((4-1)\right)\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 54143 &:= \left(-\left(T\left(T(5)\right) + \left(\sqrt{4} - 1\right) \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(3)\right) \right) \\
 54145 &:= \left(C\left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(-1 + T\left(T(4) + (5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54145 &:= \left(C\left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times \left(-1 + T\left(T(4) + (5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54146 &:= \left(-\left(T\left(T(5)\right) - \sqrt{4} \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(-((1-4))\right)\right), 6\right) \right) \\
 54148 &:= \left(-\left(T\left(T(5)\right) - 4 \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(-((1-4))\right)\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 54149 &:= \left(\left(5 - T\left(T\left((4+1)\right)\right) \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 54159 &:= \left(-\left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) + C\left(T\left((1+5)\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 54164 &:= \left(\left(-T\left(T(5)\right) + T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) - \left(1 - C\left(T(6), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54166 &:= \left(\left(-T\left(T(5)\right) + T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) + \left(1 + C\left(T(6), 6\right) \right) \right) \\
 54173 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(\left(T(5) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) - C\left(T\left(-((1-7))\right), T(3)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54174 &:= \left(\left(-T(5) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) + C\left(T\left(-((1-7))\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\
 54183 &:= \left(\left(-T(5) - T\left(T(4) + 1\right) \right) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(3)\right) \right) \\
 54185 &:= \left(-\left(T\left(T(5)\right) - 41 \right) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54186 &:= \left(-T\left(T(5) - (4-1)\right) \right) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 6\right) \\
 54193 &:= \left(-\left(5 - T\left(T(4) + 1\right) \right) + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(3)\right) \right) \\
 54194 &:= \left(-T(5) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left((4-1)\right)\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) - T\left(T(4)\right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54195 &:= \left(((- (T(5)) - T(T(4))) + 1) + C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54198 &:= \left(- (T((T(5) - (4)))) + C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{1 \times 9}\right)\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 54199 &:= \left(- ((T(T(5)) - T(T(4)))) + C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{1 \times 9}\right)\right), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \\
 54204 &:= \left((T(5) \times (-4)) + C\left(T(T(T(2))), T\left(T\left(\sqrt{04}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54209 &:= \left(- \left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) + C\left(T(T(T(2))), T\left(\sqrt{09}\right)\right) \right) \\
 54219 &:= \left(- (T((5 + 4))) + C\left(21, T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \\
 54221 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(T(2))\right) - T((T(T(2)) + 1))\right) \right) \\
 54226 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - (T(6))) \right) \\
 54229 &:= \left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - T(9))\right) \\
 54231 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(T(2))\right) - T((T(3) + 1))\right)\right) \\
 54232 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{4}\right) + 2\right)\right) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) \right) \\
 54234 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{5+4}\right)\right), T(T(2))\right) - (3 \times T(4))\right) \\
 54238 &:= \left((- (5) - T(C(4, 2))) + C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \\
 54239 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{5^4}\right) + C\left(T((2 \times 3)), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 54241 &:= \left(5 + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(T(2))\right) - T\left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + 1\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54242 &:= \left(- \left(T\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(T(2))), T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) + T(T(2))\right)\right) \\
 54244 &:= \left((C((T(5) + (4)), T(T(2))) - T(4)) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 54246 &:= \left((- (T(5)) - T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + C(T((2 + 4)), 6) \right) \\
 54247 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{5+4}\right)\right), T(T(2))\right) - (T(4) + (7))\right) \\
 54248 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{5+4}\right)\right), T(T(2))\right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times 8\right)\right) \\
 54249 &:= - \left(\left(T(5) - C\left(T(C(4, 2)), \sqrt{4 \times 9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 54251 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(5) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) - (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \times (-1))\right) \\
 54255 &:= \left(\left(\left(C\left(T(5), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) - T(2)\right) \times T(T(5))\right) + (T(5))\right) \\
 54256 &:= \left((- (5) - T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + C((T(T(2)) + (T(5))), 6) \right) \\
 54258 &:= \left(C\left(\left(5 + (4^2)\right), T(5)\right) - \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \\
 54260 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{-5 + T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)}\right) - (C(T(T(T(2))), (6 + 0)))\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54261 &:= \left((-5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - 1 \right) \\
 54267 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{5+4})), T(T(2))) \right) + (T(6)/7) \\
 54268 &:= \left(((5-4) + T(2)) + C(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 54271 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{5+4})), T(T(2))) \right) + C(7, 1) \\
 54272 &:= \left((5 + T(\sqrt{4})) + C((T(2) \times 7), T(T(2))) \right) \\
 54277 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(2))) - \sqrt{T(7)/7} \right) \right) \\
 54278 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{5+4})), T(T(2))) - 7 \right) + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 54279 &:= \left(T(5) + C(T((42/7)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 54280 &:= \left((-5) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8+0)}) \right) \\
 54281 &:= \left((T(5) + \sqrt{4}) - \left(C(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)}) \times (-1) \right) \right) \\
 54282 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C(T(C(4,2)), \sqrt{T(8)}) + T(2) \right) \right) \\
 54284 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{5+4})), T(T(2))) + C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 54286 &:= \left((5-4) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)}) + (T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 54287 &:= \left((-5) + \left(C(T(C(4,2)), \sqrt{T(8)}) + T(7) \right) \right) \\
 54289 &:= \left(\sqrt{5^4} + C(T(-((2-8))), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 54290 &:= \left((5 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9+0})) \right) \right) \\
 54291 &:= \left(T((5 + \sqrt{4})) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) - 1 \right) \right) \\
 54292 &:= \left(T((5 + \sqrt{4})) + C(T((2 \times \sqrt{9})), T(T(2))) \right) \\
 54293 &:= \left((5 + T(\sqrt{4})) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) + (T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 54294 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{5+4})), T(T(2))) + (\sqrt{9} \times T(4)) \right) \\
 54296 &:= \left((T(5) - 4) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) + (T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 54297 &:= \left(5 + \left(C(T(C(4,2)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(7) \right) \right) \\
 54298 &:= \left((T(5) - \sqrt{4}) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \\
 54299 &:= \left((-5) \times \sqrt{4} + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(9) \right) \right) \\
 54307 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(3)) - (0 - T(7)) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54309 &:= \left(T((5+4)) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{09})\right) \right) \\ 54318 &:= \left(54 + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{1+8})\right) \right) \\ 54319 &:= \left(T\left(C(5, \sqrt{4})\right) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{1 \times 9})\right) \right) \\ 54322 &:= \left(T\left(C(5, \sqrt{4})\right) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + T(2)) \right) \\ 54328 &:= \left(T\left((5 + \sqrt{4})\right) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + T(8)) \right) \\ 54334 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{4} \times 3\right), T(3)\right) + T(T(4))\right) \right) \\ 54339 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{4} \times 3\right), T(3)\right) - T(9)\right) \right) \\ 54341 &:= \left(T\left(\frac{T(T(5))}{T(4)}\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - 1\right) \right) \\ 54347 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), T(3)\right) + (T(T(4)) + T(7)) \right) \\ 54352 &:= \left(T\left((T(5) - \sqrt{4})\right) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(2)) \right) \\ 54354 &:= \left(\left(T(5) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{5+4})\right)\right) \right) \\ 54355 &:= \left(T\left((T(5) - \sqrt{4})\right) + (C((T(3) + T(5)), T(5))) \right) \\ 54363 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{4}\right) - T(3)\right) + C(T(6), T(3)) \right) \\ 54365 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4}\right) - T(T(3))\right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\ 54366 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{4}\right) \times T(3)\right) + C(T(6), 6) \right) \\ 54368 &:= \left((T(T(5)) - T(4)) + \left(C(T(T(3)), 6) - \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\ 54377 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(3)\right) - \sqrt{7 \times 7}\right) \right) \\ 54378 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) - T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(7)+8}\right)\right) \right) \\ 54390 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9+0})\right)\right) \right) \\ 54391 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + 1\right)\right) \right) \\ 54392 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) + \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + T(T(2))\right) \right) \\ 54393 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) + T(\sqrt{4})\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + (T(3))\right) \right) \\ 54394 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{4} \times 3\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + T(4)\right) \right) \\ 54395 &:= \left((T(5) - (4)) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + T(T(5))\right) \right) \\ 54396 &:= \left(T\left((T(5) + \sqrt{4})\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) - (T(6))\right) \right) \\ 54397 &:= \left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + T(7)\right) \right) \\ 54398 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) + T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + 8\right)\right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54399 &:= \left((T(5) \times T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(9)) \right) \\
 54412 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + (C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T((1 + T(T(2)))) \right) \\
 54414 &:= \left((T(5) \times T(4)) + C(T(T((4-1))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 54415 &:= \left(T(5) + (C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T((1 + T(5)))) \right) \\
 54423 &:= \left((T((T(5) + \sqrt{4})) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) \right) \\
 54428 &:= \left((T(T(5)) + 44) + C(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 54433 &:= \left(\left((T(5) - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) \right) \\
 54436 &:= \left(\left((T(T(5)) - T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(4)) \right) + C(T(T(3)), 6) \right) \\
 54438 &:= \left(T((T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}))) + \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \\
 54439 &:= \left((T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) + C(T((\sqrt{4} \times 3)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 54443 &:= \left(((T(T(5)) + 4) + T(T(4))) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(3)) \right) \\
 54445 &:= \left((T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) \times T(44)) - (5) \right) \\
 54445 &:= \left((T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) \times T(44)) - (5) \right) \\
 54446 &:= \left((T((T(5) - \sqrt{4})) \times \sqrt{4}) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) \right) \\
 54467 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{5+4})), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + (T(T(6)) - T(7)) \right) \\
 54468 &:= \left((T((5 \times 4)) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + (C(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)})) \right) \\
 54469 &:= \left((-5) + C(T(4), 4) + C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 54472 &:= \left(5 + (C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + (T(T(7))/2)) \right) \\
 54473 &:= \left(-(T(5)) + (C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + (-7) + T(T(T(3)))) \right) \\
 54474 &:= \left((C((T(5) + T(\sqrt{4})), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (T(T(7)))) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 54475 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + (C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T((T(7) - T(5)))) \right) \\
 54481 &:= \left(-(T(5)) + \left((C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 54482 &:= \left(-(T(5)) + \left((C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 54483 &:= \left(\left((T(5)^{\sqrt{4}} - T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 54484 &:= \left((5 \times 44) + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54485 &:= \left(\left((T(5)^{\sqrt{4}}) - (4) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54487 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + 7 \right) \right) \\
 54490 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9+0} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54491 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \\
 54492 &:= \left(\left((T(5)^{\sqrt{4}}) + T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54493 &:= \left(\left((T(5)^{\sqrt{4}}) + (4) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(3) \right) \right) \\
 54497 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) + 7 \right) \right) \\
 54498 &:= \left(\left((T(T(5)) - T(\sqrt{4})) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 54499 &:= \left(\left((T(5)^{\sqrt{4}}) + T(4) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 54512 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) + T \left((1 + T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54522 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T(5) \right) \right) - T \left((T \left(T(2) \right) + T \left(T(2) \right)) \right) \right) \\
 54524 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T(5) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) - (T \left(T(4) \right)) \right) \\
 54526 &:= \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) - ((5 + T \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right)) \times (-T \left(T(6) \right)) \right) \\
 54528 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T(5) \right) \right) + (- (2) \times T \left(8 \right)) \right) \\
 54529 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) - (T \left(T(2) \right) \times (-T \left(9 \right))) \right) \right) \\
 54531 &:= \left(T(5) - \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (- (5) - T \left(T \left(T \left(C(3,1) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54534 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T(5) \right) \right) - T \left((T \left(T(3) \right) - T \left(4 \right)) \right) \right) \\
 54539 &:= \left((5 \times T \left(T(4) \right)) + C \left((T(5) + T(3)), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 54542 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T(5) \right) \right) - T \left(T(4) \right) \right) - T \left(2 \right) \right) \\
 54544 &:= \left(((5 \times T \left(T(4) \right)) + (5)) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54545 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T(5) \right) \right) - T \left((\sqrt{4} \times 5) \right) \right) \\
 54545 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T(5) \right) \right) - T \left((\sqrt{4} \times 5) \right) \right) \\
 54547 &:= \left(- (T \left(T(5) \right)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) - (T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - T \left(T(7) \right)) \right) \right) \\
 54548 &:= \left(((T \left(T(5) \right) - T \left(T \left(T(4) \right) \right)) / (-5)) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 54550 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T(5) \right) \right) - (50) \right) \\
 54554 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) - (- (5) \times T \left(T(4) \right)) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54557 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (T(5) + T(7)) \right) \\ 54559 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), T(5) \right) + (T((T(5) + 9))) \right) \right) \\ 54564 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - \sqrt{6^4} \right) \\ 54567 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (T(T(6)) / 7) \right) \\ 54569 &:= \left(\left((- (T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) / 5 \right) + \left(C \left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\ 54571 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (T(7) + 1) \right) \\ 54572 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - T(\sqrt{7^2}) \right) \\ 54574 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (T(7) - \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 54578 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - T(7) \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\ 54579 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (7 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 54582 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (T(8) / 2) \right) \\ 54584 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (8 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 54586 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (8 + 6) \right) \\ 54587 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (7) \right) \\ 54588 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\ 54589 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (8 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 54591 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - C(9,1) \right) \\ 54592 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - 2 \right) \\ 54593 &:= \left(\left((C(T(5), 4) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) / 3 \right) \\ 54594 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - \sqrt{9 \times 4} \right) \\ 54596 &:= \left(\left((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) / 5 \right) + C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), 6 \right) \right) \\ 54597 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - T((9 - 7)) \right) \\ 54598 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - 8 \right) \\ 54599 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - C(9,9) \right) \\ 54614 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) - 1 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 54615 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T((6 - 1))) \right) + (T(5)) \right) \\ 54616 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) - (- (1) - T(T(6))) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54622 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + (C(T(6), T(T(2)))) - 2 \right) \\
 54624 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + C(T(6), (2+4)) \right) \\
 54634 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + ((C(T(6), T(3)) + T(4))) \right) \\
 54635 &:= \left(\left(T(T(C(5, \sqrt{4}))) \right) + (T(6)) \right) \times 35 \\
 54637 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + (T(-((T(3) - T(7)))) \right) \right) \\
 54647 &:= \left(5 + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + (T((T(T(4)) - T(7))) \right) \right) \\
 54655 &:= \left(T(T((5 + \sqrt{4}))) + ((C(T(6), T(5)) - T(5))) \right) \\
 54658 &:= \left(\left((5^4) + C(T(6), T(5)) \right) - T\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)})\right) \right) \\
 54664 &:= \left(\left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) + (C(T(6), 6)) \right) - T(T(4)) \right) \\
 54665 &:= \left(T(T((5 + \sqrt{4}))) + ((C(T(6), 6) - (5))) \right) \\
 54666 &:= \left(T\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) - (- (C(T(6), 6) - T(T(6)))) \\
 54669 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + ((C(T(6), 6) + T(9))) \right) \\
 54682 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(C(5, \sqrt{4}))) \right) - (T(6)) \right) \times T(8) \right) - 2 \\
 54685 &:= \left(T(T((5 + \sqrt{4}))) + \left(\left(C(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}) + (T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54687 &:= \left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(C(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 54692 &:= \left(- \left(T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) - \left(- \left(\left(T(T(6)) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) \\
 54698 &:= \left(\left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) + C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) - T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \\
 54722 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \right) - (7) \right) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) \\
 54724 &:= \left(\left(- (5) + T\left(\sqrt{4} + T(7)\right) \right) \right) + C\left(T(T(T(2))), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \\
 54729 &:= \left(T\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \right) + C\left(C(7, 2), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \\
 54734 &:= \left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{4} + T(7)\right) \right) + C\left(T(T(3)), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \\
 54739 &:= \left(\left(- (T(T(5))) + T\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + (T(7))\right) \right) \right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 54744 &:= \left((T(T(5)) \times 4) + C\left(C(7, \sqrt{4}), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\
 54745 &:= \left(\left(- (T(5)) + T\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7)\right) \right) \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(5)\right) \\
 54745 &:= \left(\left(- (T(5)) + T\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7)\right) \right) \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(5)\right) \\
 54747 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(5), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) - (T(7)) \right) \times (4+7) \\
 54755 &:= - \left(\left(T\left(C(5, \sqrt{4})\right) \right) + (T(T(7)) \times (- (T(5)) - T(T(5)))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54768 &:= \left(\left((T(5) + T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(7) \right) + C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 54769 &:= \left((T(T(5)) - (T(T(4)) \times (-7))) + C\left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 54786 &:= \left(((T(T(5)) - 4) + T(T(7))) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 6\right) \right) \\
 54788 &:= \left(\left((T(T(5)) - \sqrt{4}) + T(T(7)) \right) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 54794 &:= \left(((T(T(5)) + 4) + T(T(7))) + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\
 54839 &:= - \left(\left((T\left(T(5) - \sqrt{4}\right)) - T(T(8)) \right) - C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 54840 &:= \left(\left(- (C(T(5), 4) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \times (-40) \right) \\
 54853 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(T(5)) / T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 54883 &:= \left((5^4) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T(3) \right) \right) \\
 54922 &:= \left(T\left(T\left(C(5, \sqrt{4})\right)\right) + \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \right)^2 + (T(T(T(2)))) \right) \right) \\
 54928 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{5+4})\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + (-2) + T(T(8)) \right) \\
 54931 &:= \left(T\left(T\left((5 + T(\sqrt{4}))\right)\right) + \left((C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(3)\right) + 1) \right) \right) \\
 54933 &:= \left(T\left(T\left((5 + T(\sqrt{4}))\right)\right) - \left(-(\sqrt{9}) - C\left(T(T(3)), T(3)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54934 &:= \left(\left((5^4) + T(9) \right) + C\left(T(T(3)), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\
 54937 &:= \left(T\left(T\left((5 + T(\sqrt{4}))\right)\right) + \left((C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(3)\right) + 7) \right) \right) \\
 54938 &:= \left((5 + T(\sqrt{4})) + \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(3)\right) + (T(T(8))) \right) \right) \\
 54939 &:= \left((T(C(5, 4)) \times T(9)) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 54944 &:= \left((5^4) + \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + (T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 54946 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(C(5, \sqrt{4})\right)\right) + T(9) \right) + \left(T\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \times T(T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 54954 &:= \left(\left((C\left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(5)) \right) - T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) \\
 54955 &:= \left(\left((C\left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})\right) + \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 54958 &:= \left(T\left((5 + \sqrt{4})\right) + \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(5)\right) + (T(T(8))) \right) \right) \\
 54962 &:= \left(5 + \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \right) + (C\left(T(6), T(T(2)))) \right) \right) \\
 54963 &:= \left(\left((T(T(5)) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)) - T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) + (C\left(T(6), T(3)\right)) \right) \\
 54966 &:= \left(\left((T(T(5)) - T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (C\left(T(6), 6\right)) \right) \\
 54969 &:= \left((T(5) \times (\sqrt{4} + T(9))) + C\left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54973 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + T(7) \right) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 54979 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(T \left(\left(T(7) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54982 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 54985 &:= \left(- \left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54989 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times \left(8 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 54994 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + T(4) \right) \right) \\
 55239 &:= \left(T((5 \times 5)) \times T(2) + C \left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 55245 &:= \left(T(T(5)) - \left(\left(C \left(T(5), 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times (-5) \right) \right) \\
 55248 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(5)) + \left(\left(T(T(C(5,2))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-T(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 55264 &:= \left(\left((5+5)^{T(2)} \right) + C \left(T(6), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 55289 &:= \left(- \left((5+5) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 55294 &:= \left(- (5) + T \left(T(5) \times T(2) \right) + C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 55299 &:= \left(C \left(T(5) + T((5-2)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + T(T(9)) \right) \\
 55384 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) \right) \times T(T(T(3))) - C \left(8, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 55439 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T(5) \right) / T(5) \right) \times T(T(T(4))) - C \left(3, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 55469 &:= \left((5 + T(T(5)) \times T(4)) + C \left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 55539 &:= \left(T \left((5+5) \times 5 \right) + C \left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 55594 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(5), 5 \right) \times \left(T(5) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T(T(T(4))) \right) \\
 55698 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), 5 \right) + \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) - T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 55804 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(5) / 5 \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(T(T(04))) \right) \\
 55839 &:= \left(\left(\left((5 \times T(5)) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 55899 &:= \left(\left(C(5,5) + \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(9)) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 55929 &:= \left(T(5) \times (T(T(5)) - 9) + C \left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 55942 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T(5) \right) / T(5) \right) \right) \right) \times C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 55984 &:= \left(C \left((5 + T(5)), 9 \right) - 8 \right) / T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 55985 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(5) + T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T(8) + 5 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55986 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 55987 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(5) + T(T(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \times T(8) + 7 \right) \\
 55988 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(5) + T(T(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \times T(8) + 8 \right) \\
 56089 &:= \left((-5) + T(60) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 56094 &:= \left(T((T(T(5)) - 60)) + C\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right) \right) \\
 56099 &:= \left((5 + T(60)) + C\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 56285 &:= \left((5 + T((T(6) \times T(2)))) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 56294 &:= \left(5 + \left(C(T(6), T(T(2))) + \left((T(9))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 56349 &:= \left((5 + C(T(6), T(3))) + T\left(4^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \right) \\
 56447 &:= \left(T(T((5+6))) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - T(7) \right) \right) \\
 56454 &:= \left(T(T((5+6))) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(5)\right) - T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 56464 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C\left(T(6), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + T(64) \right) \right) \\
 56485 &:= \left((T(T((5+6))) + T(4)) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 56744 &:= \left(-T((5+6)) - \left(-C(T(7), T(4)) / T\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 56839 &:= \left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{-5+T(6)}\right)\right)\right) + \left(\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(3)\right) + T(T(9)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 56882 &:= \left(\left((T(5) + T(T(6))) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) + C(8, T(2)) \right) \\
 56975 &:= \left((-5) + C\left(T(6), \sqrt{9}\right) \right) \times (T(7) + T(5)) \\
 56987 &:= \left(\left(T(5) \times \left(T(T(6)) + T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) \right) - T(7) \right) \\
 57239 &:= \left((5 \times T((T(7) + T(T(2)))) \right) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 57264 &:= \left((T(T(5)) \times (T(7) - T(2))) + C\left(T(6), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\
 57324 &:= \left((T(T((5+7))) - T(T(3))) + C\left(T(T(T(2))), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\
 57339 &:= \left(T(T((5+7))) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(3)\right) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 57344 &:= \left(C((T(5) - 7), 3) \times \left(\sqrt{4}^{T(4)} \right) \right) \\
 57389 &:= 5\sqrt{T(7)-3} + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \\
 57393 &:= \left(\left((T(T(5)) \times T(7)) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$57498 := \left((T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{C(9,8)}\right)\right) \right)$$

$$57574 := \left(- (C(T(5), 7)) + (T((T(5) + (7)))^{\sqrt{4}}) \right)$$

$$57594 := \left((5 \times T(T((-7) + T(5)))) + C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \right)$$

$$57699 := \left(((C(T(5), 7) - T(6)) - \sqrt{9}) \times 9 \right)$$

$$57789 := \left(\left(- ((C(T(5), 7) + (7))) + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \times (-9) \right)$$

$$57795 := \left((C(T(5), \sqrt{7 \times 7}) \times 9) - T(T(5)) \right)$$

$$57835 := \left((T(5) + T(7)) \times (C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 3\right) + T(5)) \right)$$

$$57837 := \left(\left(- (T((T(5) + (7)))) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), 7) \right)$$

$$57843 := \left((-((C(T(5), 7) - 8)) \times T(\sqrt{4})) \times (-3) \right)$$

$$57849 := \left(C\left((5 + 7), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(9))) \right)$$

$$57909 := \left((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - T(\sqrt{09}) \right)$$

$$57913 := \left((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - \sqrt{1+3} \right)$$

$$57918 := \left((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + \sqrt{1+8} \right)$$

$$57919 := \left(((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + 1) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$57924 := \left((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + (T(2))^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$57933 := \left(\left((C(T(5), 7) \times \sqrt{9}) + T(3) \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$57934 := \left(((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + T(T(3))) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$57936 := \left(\left((C(T(5), 7) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \right) + T(6) \right)$$

$$57939 := \left(((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + T(T(3))) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$57945 := \left((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) + (\sqrt{4} \times T(5)) \right)$$

$$57948 := \left(((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - T(\sqrt{4})) + T(8) \right)$$

$$57994 := \left(((C(T(5), 7) + 9) \times 9) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$57996 := \left((C(T(5), 7) + 9) \times (\sqrt{9} + (6)) \right)$$

$$57997 := \left(\left((- (C(T(5), 7)) - T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times (-9) \right) + T(7)$$

$$57999 := \left(((C(T(5), 7) + 9) \times 9) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$58269 := \left(T((T((5 + 8)) - 2)) + C\left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 58338 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left(\left(T(T(3)) - C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58354 &:= \left(\left(- (5) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(3) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(T(5) \times T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58359 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (C(T(T(3)), (T(5) - 9))) \right) \\
 58362 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - (- (3) - C(T(6), T(T(2)))) \right) \\
 58363 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(6))) - 3) \right) \\
 58369 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(6)))) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 58387 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58389 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(3) \right) + (T(89)) \right) \right) \\
 58429 &:= \left(\left(T(T((5+8))) - T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58445 &:= \left(\left(- (5) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(- \left((\sqrt{4} - T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58446 &:= \left((T(T((5+8))) - 4) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) \right) \\
 58484 &:= \left((5 + (T(C(8, \sqrt{4})) \times T(8))) \times 4 \right) \\
 58542 &:= \left(T((T(T(5)) - T((-8) + T(5)))) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 58557 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) + T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) \right) \right) \\
 58666 &:= \left(- (T(T(5))) - \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), (T(T(6)) / T(6)) \right) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 58674 &:= \left(((T(5) + 8) + T(T(6))) \times T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 58729 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (T(7)) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58844 &:= \left(58 + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(4) \right) / T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58897 &:= \left(- (T(T(5))) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(97) \right) \right) \\
 58973 &:= \left(5 - \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \times C \left(T(7), 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 59049 &:= \left(T \left(\left(5 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{C(T(04), 9)} \right) \\
 59235 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(T(5)) - T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) + ((T(T(T(2))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)))) \right) \\
 59236 &:= \left((5 + T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right)) \times (C(T(T(2)), 3) + T(T(6))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 59248 &:= \left(C(T(5), 9) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \\
 59254 &:= \left((-T(5) + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(2)))) + C(T(5), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 59259 &:= \left(T\left(\frac{T(T(5))}{T(\sqrt{9})}\right) + \left(T(2)^{C(5, \sqrt{9})}\right) \right) \\
 59269 &:= \left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{C(9, 2)}\right) + C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 59276 &:= \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{9}}) + T(T(T(2))) \right) \times T(T(C(7, 6))) \right) \\
 59290 &:= \left(\left(T(T(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) / T(\sqrt{9+0}) \\
 59291 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) / T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + 1 \\
 59296 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) / T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + 6 \\
 59384 &:= \left((5 \times T(T(9))) + \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}) - T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 59494 &:= \left(\left(C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) - T(4) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9}^{T(4)} \right) \right) \\
 59545 &:= \left(-(5) + \left(\left(-T(T(9)) + C(T(5), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) \times T(5) \right) \\
 59559 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(5)) + (5 \times T(T(9))) \right) \right) \\
 59598 &:= \left((T(T(5)) + 9) \times C\left((5 + T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 59624 &:= \left((5 + (T(9) \times C(T(6), T(2)))) - T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \right) \\
 59658 &:= \left(((T(T(5)) \times T(9)) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 59659 &:= \left(-(5) + \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 6) - (T(T(5)) \times (-T(9))) \right) \right) \\
 59682 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right) \times T(C(8, 2)) \right) \\
 59785 &:= \left(T(C(5, \sqrt{9})) \times ((T(T(7)) + T(T(8))) + (T(5))) \right) \\
 59787 &:= \left((C(T(5), 9) - T(T(7))) \times \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + (7) \right) \right) \\
 59839 &:= \left(\left(-(5) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 3\right) \times T(9) \right) \right) \\
 59868 &:= \left(\left(C(5, \sqrt{9}) + T((T(8) + T(6))) \right) \times T(8) \right) \\
 59884 &:= \left(\left((T(5) \times T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times T(T(8)) - C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 59885 &:= - \left(\left(T(C(5, \sqrt{9})) + \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(8)) \right) \times (-T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 59945 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(C(5, \sqrt{9})) + T(T(9)) \right) \right) \times T(T(4)) - (5) \right) \\
 59955 &:= \left((T(5) \times T((C(9, \sqrt{9}) + (5)))) - T(T(5)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 59964 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - \left(- (T(9)) \times C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 59975 &:= \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) + \left(T(\sqrt{9} + T(7)) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 60354 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(6)) - C(T(T(03)), 5) \right) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 61434 &:= \left(C(T((6+1)), 4) + 3 \right) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 61453 &:= \left(T(T((6+1))) + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 5) \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 61584 &:= \left((61 \times T(T(5))) + C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right) \right) \\
 62247 &:= \left(T(T(6)) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) \right) + C\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 7\right) \\
 62264 &:= \left(C(6, T(2))^{T(2)} + C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 62495 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(2)) \times (\sqrt{4} + T(9)) \right) - T(5) \\
 62728 &:= \left(- (62) + \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 62768 &:= \left(- (T(6)) - \left((T(T(2)) - C(T(7), 6)) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 62782 &:= \left(- ((6+2)) + \left(C(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)}) / T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 62783 &:= \left(- ((T(6) / T(2))) - \left(C(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)}) / (-T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 62784 &:= \left(\left(- ((6^2)) + C(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) / T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 62785 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(T(2))) + \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 62786 &:= \left(- ((6-2)) - \left(C(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)}) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62788 &:= \left((-6) / T(2) + \left(C(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)}) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 62789 &:= \left((-6) / T(T(2)) + \left(C(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)}) / T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 62790 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(T(2))) - \left(- (T(T(7))) \times T(T(\sqrt{9+0})) \right) \right) \\
 62791 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(T(2))) + \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \\
 62792 &:= \left(\sqrt{6-2} + \left(C(T(7), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 62793 &:= \left((6/2) - \left(C(T(7), T(\sqrt{9})) / (-T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 62794 &:= \left(\left((T(6) + T(2)) + C(T(7), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) / T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 62795 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(T(2))) + \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) + 5 \right) \right) \\
 62796 &:= \left(T((6/2)) - \left(C(T(7), T(\sqrt{9})) / (-6) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 62797 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(T(2))) + \left((T(T(7)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 7 \right) \right) \\
 62798 &:= \left((6+2) + \left(C(T(7), T(\sqrt{9})) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 62799 &:= \left((6+T(2)) + \left(C(T(7), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 62919 &:= \left(- \left((T(T(6))^2) \right) + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), (1+T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 62943 &:= \left((T((T(T(6)) / T(2))) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - C(T(4), 3) \right) \\
 62974 &:= \left(- \left((T(T(6))^2) \right) + \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 7) + (T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 62982 &:= \left((-6) + C(C(T(T(2)), \sqrt{9}), 8) / 2 \right) \\
 62985 &:= \left((C(T(6), 2) \times T(\sqrt{9} \times 8)) - (T(5)) \right) \\
 62995 &:= \left((T((T(6) + T(2))) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9}))) - 5 \right) \\
 63287 &:= \left(- (T(6)) - \left((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) / \sqrt{T(8)}) \times (-7) \right) \right) \\
 63379 &:= \left(- ((C(T(6), T(3)) + T(3))) + (7^{T(\sqrt{9})}) \right) \\
 63385 &:= \left(((T(6) / 3)^{T(3)}) - C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(5)) \right) \\
 63444 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(3)) - ((T(4) - T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 63476 &:= \left(((T(T(6)) + T(T(3)))^{\sqrt{4}}) - T(C(7, 6)) \right) \\
 63484 &:= \left(((T(T(6)) + T(T(3)))^{\sqrt{4}}) - C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 63486 &:= \left((6 \times (-3) + T(T(T(4)))) + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 6) \right) \\
 63498 &:= \left(((T(T(6)) + T(T(3)))^{\sqrt{4}}) - T(\sqrt{C(9, 8)}) \right) \\
 63569 &:= - \left((T(T((T(T(6)) / T(T(3)))))) - C((5+T(6)), T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 63834 &:= \left(- (6) - ((T(3) \times (-8)) \times C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 63888 &:= \left(\left((C(T(6), 3) \times \sqrt{T(8)}) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 63944 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(3)) + \left((T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - (T(T(4)))) \times T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 63984 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(3)) + (\sqrt{9} \times T((8 \times T(4)))) \right) \\
 63985 &:= \left(((C(6, 3)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 8) - T(5) \right) \\
 64185 &:= \left(T(T(6)) - (C((T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + 1), 8) / (-5)) \right) \\
 64288 &:= \left(\left((C(6, T(\sqrt{4}))^{T(2)}) + T(8) \right) \times 8 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64296 &:= \left((T(6) - T(\sqrt{4})) \times (2 + T(C(9,6))) \right) \\
 64344 &:= \left(T(6) \times (C((T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3)), 4) + 4) \right) \\
 64379 &:= \left((C((T(6) + (4)), 3) \times T(7)) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 64380 &:= - \left((C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(80)))) \right) \\
 64393 &:= \left((T((T(T(6)) / T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(T(3))) + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 3) \right) \\
 64435 &:= \left((- (6) + T(T(4))) \times (C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3) - T(5)) \right) \\
 64515 &:= (C(T(6), 4) - T(T(5))) \times \sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} \\
 64673 &:= \left((T(6) \times T(T(\sqrt{4} \times 6))) - T(C(7, T(3))) \right) \\
 64698 &:= \left((T(6) \times T(T(\sqrt{4} \times 6))) - \sqrt{C(9, 8)} \right) \\
 64739 &:= \left(- (6) + (C(-((\sqrt{4} - T(7))), T(T(3))) - T(T(9))) \right) \\
 64778 &:= \left(((T(6)^{T(\sqrt{4})}) - (7)) \times C(7, \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 64847 &:= \left(C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) - \left((T(\sqrt{T(8)})^{T(\sqrt{4})}) \times (-7) \right) \right) \\
 64856 &:= \left((T(T(6)) \times (-4)) + C((T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5), T(6)) \right) \\
 64876 &:= \left((C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4})) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \times (T(7) + T(6)) \right) \\
 64912 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + ((T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 1)^{T(2)}) \right) \\
 64939 &:= - \left((T(T(6)) - (49 \times C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 64947 &:= \left(((T(6)^4) / \sqrt{9}) + C(T(4), 7) \right) \\
 64954 &:= \left(T((6 + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times C(T(5), T(4))) \right) \\
 64980 &:= (C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \times (9 + T(80))) \\
 64996 &:= \left((C(T(6), T(4)) / T(\sqrt{9})) + (T(T(9)) \times 6) \right) \\
 65244 &:= (C(T(6), T(5)) + (T((T(T(2)) \times T(4))) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \\
 65284 &:= \left(C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(T(2)))) - T((T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(4))) \right) \\
 65339 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(3))) + (- (T(T(3))) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \\
 65450 &:= \left((- (T(T(6))) + T(T(C(5, \sqrt{4})))) \times 50 \right) \\
 65455 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - T((5 \times 5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65465 &:= \left(C \left((T(6) + (5)), T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) - ((T(6) \times T(5))) \right) \\
 65499 &:= - \left(\left(T(6) - \left(C(T(5), 4) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + T(9) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 65543 &:= \left(\left(C((T(6) + (5)), 5) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \\
 65546 &:= \left(\left(C((T(6) + (5)), 5) - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - T(T(6)) \right) \\
 65549 &:= \left(C((T(6) + (5)), 5) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4 \times 9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 65554 &:= \left((C((T(6) + (5)), 5) + (5)) - T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 65654 &:= \left((C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) - T(T(5))) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 65689 &:= \left(C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) - T \left((-8) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 65725 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(6) - 5} \right) \right) - C((T(7) - 2), 5) \right) \right) \\
 65744 &:= \left(-((T(6) + T(5))) + C \left((T(7) - \sqrt{4}), T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 65759 &:= \left(C((T(6) + (5)), C(7, 5)) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 65765 &:= \left(C \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{T(6) - 5} - (T(7))} \right) \right), T(6) \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 65774 &:= \left(C((T(6) + (5)), (-7) + T(7)) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 65795 &:= \left(C \left((T(6) + (5)), (7 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) + T(5) \right) \\
 65822 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T(6) + (5)), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + T(T(T(2))) \right) + T(T(T(2))) \right) \\
 65825 &:= \left(C \left((T(6) + (5)), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (T(2) \times T(5)) \right) \\
 65828 &:= \left(C \left((T(6) + (5)), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (T(T(2)) \times 8) \right) \\
 65844 &:= \left(C \left((T(6) + (5)), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (4^{T(\sqrt{4})}) \right) \\
 65855 &:= \left(C \left((T(6) + (5)), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - (-5) \times T(5) \right) \\
 65928 &:= \left(((-T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times T(C(9, 2)) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 65948 &:= \left(C \left((T(6) + (5)), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times (-8) \right) \right) \\
 65969 &:= \left(C \left((T(6) + (5)), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + (T(6) \times 9) \right) \\
 65996 &:= C \left(T(6) + 5, T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{T \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^6} \\
 66179 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(T(61) \times C(7, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 66759 &:= \left(T(6) \times \left(- (6) - \left(- (7) \times C \left(T(5), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66914 &:= \left(C(T(6), 6) - \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 1 \right) \times (-T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 66948 &:= \left(C(T(6), 6) + \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(T(4)) \right) - \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 67256 &:= \left((T(6) \times C(T(7), T(2))) - T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{-5+T(6)}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 67284 &:= \left(T(6) \times \left(C(T(7), T(2)) - \left(T(8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 67774 &:= - \left(\left(\left((T(T(6)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(7)) \right) + C(T(7), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 67823 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(7)+T(8)}\right) \right) + T(T(T(2))) \right) / (-3) \right) \\
 67824 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(7)+T(8)}\right) / T(2) \right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 67825 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(7)+T(8)}\right) / T(2) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 67829 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(7)+T(8)}\right) - T(2) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 67864 &:= \left((6 + T(7)) \times \left(T(T(8)) + C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 67984 &:= \left(\left(- (T(6)) \times \left(T(T(7)) - T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) \right) + T(T(T(4))) \right) \\
 67992 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(6) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{9}) \right) - T(T(9)) \right) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) \\
 67995 &:= \left(- (C(T(6), 7)) + \left(T(9) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(5)\right) \right) \right) \\
 68039 &:= \left(T(6) \times T(80) - C(3, \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 68043 &:= \left(T(6) \times T(80) + T\left(\sqrt{C(4,3)}\right) \right) \\
 68244 &:= \left(T(6) \times T(T(8)) + \left(C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 68245 &:= \left(T(6) \times T(T(8)) + \left(C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 68248 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - 2 \right) - \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times (-T(T(8))) \right) \right) \\
 68467 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(6), 8) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T(T(6)) \right) + T(T(7)) \right) \\
 68488 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(6), 8) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T(T(8)) \right) - 8 \right) \\
 68496 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), 8) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times 6\right) \right) \\
 68498 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (C(T(6), 8)) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) / (-\sqrt{9}) \right) + T(T(8)) \\
 68664 &:= \left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + \left(T((-6 + T(6))^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \\
 68728 &:= \left(- (68) + \left(C(T(7), T(2)) \times T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68875 &:= \left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + ((T(8) \times T(T(7))) - (5)) \right) \\
 68921 &:= \left(\left(T(6) + C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{2+1} \right) \\
 68924 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(6) + C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{T(2)} \right) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 68979 &:= \left(- (6) - \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times \left(- (9) - C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 69291 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \right) - C(9,1) \right) \\
 69299 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \right) - C(9,9) \right) \\
 69315 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(6)) \times C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3 \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times T(5) \right) \\
 69327 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(6, \sqrt{9}) + T(T(3)) \right)^{T(2)} \right) + T(T(7)) \right) \\
 69426 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(6) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T(C((4 \times 2), 6)) \right) \\
 69427 &:= \left(C(6, T(\sqrt{9})) + \left(T \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(2)) \right) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 69534 &:= \left(T(T(6)) - \left(- (T(9)) \times T(T(C(5,3))) \right) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 69544 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(5)) \right) + \left(T(4) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 69549 &:= \left(- (T(6)) - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + T \left(T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \times (-T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 69557 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(\left(T(6) - \sqrt{9} \right), 5 \right) - \left(5^7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 69579 &:= \left(\left(- (T(6)) - \left(C \left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(5) \right) / (-7) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 69624 &:= - \left(\left(\left(6^{T(\sqrt{9})} \right) - \left(C(T(6), (T(2) + (4))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 69658 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(6)) \right) + \left(5^{\sqrt{T(8)}} \right) \right) \\
 69853 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) - \left(T(8) - \left(5^{T(3)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 38639 &:= \left(- \left(\left(- \left((3-8)^6 \right) \right) + C \left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 69985 &:= \left(C(6, T(\sqrt{9})) - \left(- (9) \times \left(\sqrt{T(8)}^5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 71442 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), \sqrt{1 \times 4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / 2 \right) \\
 71484 &:= \left(\left(T(71) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times C(8, \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 71589 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) + \left(C \left(- (1) + T(5), 8 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 71849 &:= \left(\left(T(7) + 1 \right) - \left(T \left(C \left(8, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \times (-T(9)) \right) \\
 72296 &:= \left(- (T(7)) \times \left(2 - \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) / T(6) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$72344 := \left(\left(T(7) \times \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) / T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right)$$

$$72346 := \left(\left((T(7) \times C(T(T(T(2))), T(3))) / T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) - 6 \right)$$

$$72348 := \left(\left(T(7) \times \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) / T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right)$$

$$72744 := \left(T(7) \times \left(C((-2) + T(7), T(\sqrt{4})) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$72794 := \left(\left(T(7) \times C((-2) + T(7), \sqrt{9}) \right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right)$$

$$72795 := \left(\left(T(7) \times C((-2) + T(7), \sqrt{9}) \right) - (5) \right)$$

$$72854 := - \left(\left(T(T(7)) - \left((2 \times T(T(8))) \times T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$72954 := \left(- (C(T(7), 2)) \times \left(- (\sqrt{9}) - T((T(5) + (4))) \right) \right)$$

$$72968 := \left((C(T(7), T(T(T(2)))) / T(9)) + \left(6\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right)$$

$$72999 := \left(\left(\left(T(T(7)) \times C(T(T(2)), \sqrt{9}) \right) - 9 \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$73199 := \left(- (7) + \left(T(T(3)) \times T((-1) + C(9, \sqrt{9})) \right) \right)$$

$$73283 := \left(C((T(7) - T(3)), T(T(2))) - C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 3\right) \right)$$

$$73359 := \left((T(C(7, 3)) - 3) \times \left(T(T(5)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$73425 := \left(T((7 + 3)) \times \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(2)) + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$73435 := \left((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - \left(\sqrt{4} + C(T(T(3)), 5) \right) \right)$$

$$73437 := \left((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - C\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), \sqrt{-3 + T(7)}\right) \right)$$

$$73437 := \left((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - C\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), \sqrt{-3 + T(7)}\right) \right)$$

$$73441 := \left(\left(T(7) + \sqrt{3^{T(4)}} \right)^{\sqrt{C(4,1)}} \right)$$

$$73464 := \left(- ((T(T(7)) - C((T(T(3)) + 4), T(6))) \times T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right)$$

$$73647 := \left(\left((C(T(7), 3) + T(T(6))) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$73976 := \left(\left(C((T(7) - T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(7)) \right) - T(T(6)) \right)$$

$$74186 := \left(\left(- (T(T(7))) - T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) + C\left(\left(1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})\right), 6\right) \right)$$

$$74207 := \left(C\left(\left(T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right), T(T(2))\right) + (0 - T(T(7))) \right)$$

$$74213 := \left(\left(- (T(T(7))) + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) + C((T(T(T(2))) + 1), T(3)) \right)$$

$$74228 := \left((-7) \times T(T(4)) + C\left(22, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74238 &:= \left((C((7 + T(4)), T(T(2))) - 3) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\ 74244 &:= \left((C((T(7) - T(4)), T(T(2))) - T(\sqrt{4})) \times 4 \right) \\ 74249 &:= \left(- (7) + (4 \times C((T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4})), T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\ 74284 &:= \left(T(7) + (C((T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 4) \right) \\ 74289 &:= - \left((T(C(7, \sqrt{4})) - ((2 \times T(8)) \times T(T(9)))) \right) \\ 74292 &:= \left((C((7 + T(4)), T(T(2))) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(2)) \right) \\ 74423 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - T((-2) + T(T(3))) \right) \\ 74425 &:= \left((T(C(7, \sqrt{4})) - \sqrt{4}) \times T(25) \right) \\ 74448 &:= \left(T((7 + 4)) \times T((\sqrt{4} + C(T(4), 8))) \right) \\ 74493 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - T((9 + T(3))) \right) \\ 74495 &:= \left(((T(7) \times \sqrt{4}) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), \sqrt{9})) + T(5) \right) \\ 74578 &:= \left(- (C(7, 4)) + C((T(5) + (7)), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\ 74579 &:= \left((- (T(7)) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + C((T(5) + (7)), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\ 74611 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) - (1 + 1) \right) \\ 74612 &:= \left((- (7) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + C((T(6) + 1), T(T(2))) \right) \\ 74614 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + (1^4) \right) \\ 74615 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + \sqrt{-1 + 5} \right) \\ 74618 &:= \left((7 - \sqrt{4}) + C((T(6) + 1), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\ 74619 &:= \left(T((7 - 4)) + C((T(6) + 1), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\ 74622 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + (T(2)^2) \right) \\ 74623 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + T((-2) + T(3)) \right) \\ 74624 &:= \left((C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + T(T(T(2)))) - T(4) \right) \\ 74625 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) - ((T(2) - T(5))) \right) \\ 74632 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + (T(T(3)) - 2) \right) \\ 74633 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + C(T(3), 3) \right) \\ 74641 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + T((T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + 1) \right) \\ 74643 &:= \left(C((T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) + (T(4) \times 3) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74644 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T(7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) + T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + T(4) \right) \\
 74645 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) + \sqrt{4^5} \right) \\
 74647 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T(7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + (T(7)) \right) \\
 74647 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T(7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + (T(7)) \right) \\
 74649 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) + (4 \times 9) \right) \\
 74653 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) + (T(T(5)) / 3) \right) \\
 74658 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) + T \left(\left(T(5) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 74679 &:= \left(T((7+4)) + C \left((-6 + T(7)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 74684 &:= \left(C(T(7), 4) + \left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 74733 &:= \left(T \left(T \left((7 - \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + C \left((T(7) - T(3)), T(3) \right) \right) \\
 74739 &:= \left(C(T(7), 4) + C \left((7 \times 3), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 74754 &:= \left(((T(C(7,4)) - (7)) \times T(T(5))) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 74798 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - C \left((T(7) - 9), 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 74844 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(\left(T(8)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / 4 \right) \right) \\
 74896 &:= \left(-(74) + \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(C(9,6)) \right) \right) \\
 74913 &:= \left(T \left((T(7) - (4)) \right) + C \left(\left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + 1 \right), T(3) \right) \right) \\
 74935 &:= \left(-(7) \times \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times (-T(C(9,3))) \right) + (5) \right) \right) \\
 74936 &:= \left(\left(-(T(7)) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + \left((T(C(9,3)) \times T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 74939 &:= \left(\left(-(T(7)) - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(T(C(9,3)) \times T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74941 &:= \left(-(T(7)) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 74943 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - \left(T(T(4)) \times (-T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 74944 &:= \left(-(T(7)) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 74948 &:= \left(\left(-(T(7)) + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 74949 &:= \left((T(7) + T(T(4))) \times T \left(\left(C(9,4) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 74955 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left((7 - \sqrt{4}) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times T(5) \right) - T(T(5)) \\
 74963 &:= \left(-(7) + \left(T \left(\left(C \left(4, \sqrt{9} \right) \times T(6) \right) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 74965 &:= \left(\left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(C(9,6)) \right) - (5) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74966 &:= \left((-7) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left((T(C(9,6)) \times T(6)) \right) \\
 74969 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T(7) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - C \left(6, T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 74982 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(T(T(9)) \times (-T(8)) \right) \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 74985 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left((7 - \sqrt{4}) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(5) \right) \\
 74989 &:= \left(T(7) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - 9 \right) \\
 74991 &:= \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \\
 74992 &:= \left(\left(T(7) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, T(2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74996 &:= \left(\left(T(7) - \sqrt{4} \right) - \left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times (-T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 75139 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) + T(T(5)) \right) + C \left((1 + T(T(3))), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 75279 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(7) - 5 \right) \times \left(T(2) - C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 75342 &:= \left(C \left((7 + T(5)), T(3) \right) + \left(T(\sqrt{4})^{T(T(2))} \right) \right) \\
 75354 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T \left(T \left((5 - 3) \right) \right) \right) / 5 \right) + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 75432 &:= \left(T(7) \times \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - T(3) \right) \times T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 75467 &:= \left(7 - \left(T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(T(6) + T(7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 75475 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 \times T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) + T(5) \right) \\
 75488 &:= \left(\left(7 + C \left(T(5), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(8 + T \left(T(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 75494 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T(7) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(\sqrt{5^4}, T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 75495 &:= \left(\left(T(7) + C \left(T(5), \sqrt{4 \times 9} \right) \right) \times T(5) \right) \\
 75496 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T(7) \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 75782 &:= \left(- \left(T(7) \right) - \left(- \left(57 \right) \times C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 75893 &:= \left(- \left(7 \right) - \left(C \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}, T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times \left(-T(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 75936 &:= \left(T(7) \times \left(\left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{9} \right) - 3 \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 75939 &:= \left(C \left((7 + T(5)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + T \left((T(3) + T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 75947 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), 5 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(T \left(T(4) \right) \times T \left(T(7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 75988 &:= \left(T \left(T(7) \right) + C \left(\left(- \left(5 \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right) \right), 8 \right) \right) \\
 76524 &:= \left(T(7) \times \left(\left(6 \times C \left(T(5), T(2) \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76979 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(7)) - \left(T((T(6) + T(9))) \times C(7, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 77324 &:= \left(\left((T(T(7)) + (C(T(7), 3))) \times T(T(T(2))) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 77328 &:= \left(\left((T(T(7)) + (C(T(7), 3))) \times T(T(T(2))) \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 77464 &:= \left(\left(- (T(7)) + C \left(\sqrt{T(T(7)) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))}, 6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 77597 &:= \left(77 + C \left(\left(T(T(5)) / T(\sqrt{9}) \right), 7 \right) \right) \\
 77988 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(7)) + (C(T(7), \sqrt{9})) \right) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) + (T(T(8))) \right) \\
 78332 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) + C \left(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3), T(3) \right) \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 78351 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) + T \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \times (3 + T(T(C(5, 1)))) \right) \\
 78474 &:= \left((T(7) - T(T(8))) \times \left(- (C(T(4), 7) - T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 78496 &:= \left(\left(T(7) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times \left(- (\sqrt{4} - T(C(9, 6))) \right) \right) \\
 78527 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) / T(5) \right) + (- (T(2) - T(T(7)))) \\
 78531 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + \left(5^{T(3)+1} \right) \right) \\
 78561 &:= \left(T \left(\left(\left(- (T(7)) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \times T(C(6, 1)) \right) \\
 78583 &:= \left((- (7) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(5)))) - C \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 3 \right) \right) \\
 78799 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\left(7 + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(T(7) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 78924 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(T(T(2))^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))} \right) \\
 78928 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) / (T(9) / T(2)) \right) - 8 \\
 78933 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) - T(9) \right) / (- (T(3) + T(T(3)))) \\
 78934 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) / (9 + T(3)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 78935 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) - (9 + T(3)) \right) / T(5) \\
 78936 &:= \left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) / (9 + \sqrt{36}) \\
 78939 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) + T(9) \right) / (T(3) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78942 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / T(9) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(2) \right) \\
 78954 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - T(9) \right) / T(5) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78999 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / T(9) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 79137 &:= \left(\left(7 \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + (C((-1) + T(T(3)), 7)) \\
 79243 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + T(C(4, 3)) \\
 79254 &:= \left(7 \times T(C(9, 2)) \right) \times \left(T(5) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 79394 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(7)) + \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-T(4)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79457 &:= \left(- (7) + \left(C \left(9, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left((T(5) + T(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79492 &:= \left(T(7) + \left(C \left(9, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left((T(9) - 2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79573 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(7), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) / T(5) \right) + \left(T(T(7)) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T(3) \right) \right) \\
 79738 &:= \left(\left((7 + C(9, 7))^3 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 79885 &:= \left(- \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T(8) \right) \times (8 \times T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 79892 &:= \left(- (T(7)) + \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(T(8) \right) \right) \times C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79955 &:= \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-T(T(5))) \right) \\
 79975 &:= \left(T \left((7 + \sqrt{9}) \right) - \left(- (T(C(9, 7))) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 80586 &:= \left(T(T(8)) \times \left(T(T(05)) + C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 81081 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times T \left((-10) + T(C(8, 1)) \right) \right) \\
 81697 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + C(16, 9) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 81759 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - C((-1) + T(7), 5) \right) \right) - T(T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 81984 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left((-1) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 82274 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(2) \right) - T(2) \right) \times (7 + T(T(4))) \right) \\
 82329 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(T \left((T(2) \times C(T(3), T(2))) \right) \right) \times (-T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 82348 &:= \left(\left((C(8, T(2)) + T(T(T(3))))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 82349 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(T(2)) \right) - \left(T \left((T(3) \times T(4)) \right) \times T(9) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 82369 &:= \left((C(8, T(2)) + T(T(T(3))))^{6/\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 82418 &:= \left(\left(T(C(8,2)) / \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(T(-((1-8)))) \right) \\
 82424 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(C(8,2))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / 2 \right) + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 82434 &:= \left(\left((T(T(8)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times C(T(4), 3) \right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 82460 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(2)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + (60)\right) \right) \\
 82467 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(8) - C\left(T(2), \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \times (T(6) \times 7) \right) \\
 82560 &:= \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(T(2)))\right), 5\right) + T(60) \right) \\
 82824 &:= \left(-\left(T(C(8,2))\right) \times \left(\sqrt{T(8)} - T((2 \times T(4)))\right) \right) \\
 82848 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(C(T(T(T(2))), 8) / T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) + (T(T(8)))\right) \right) \\
 83329 &:= -\left(\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) + \left(\left(T(T(3))^{T(2)}\right) \times (-9)\right)\right) \right) \\
 83489 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T\left(\left(T(T(4)) + T(8)\right)\right) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 83499 &:= \left(-\left(T(C(8,3))\right) + \left(T\left(\left(T(T(4)) + T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \times T(9)\right) \right) \\
 83699 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(-8 + T(T(3))\right)\right)\right) \times C\left(6, \sqrt{9}\right) - \left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 83735 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \times T\left(T\left(7 + T(3)\right)\right)\right) + T(5) \right) \\
 83775 &:= \left(\left(T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) \times \left(-7 + T(T(7))\right)\right) - T(5) \right) \\
 83896 &:= -\left(\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) - \left(\left(T(T(8)) \times T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T(6)\right)\right) \right) \\
 83969 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C\left(T(T(3)), 9\right) - T(T(6))\right) / T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 83974 &:= -\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), 9\right) / (-7) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \\
 83980 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C\left(T(T(3)), 9\right) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8+0)}\right)\right) \right) \\
 83981 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C\left(T(T(3)), 9\right) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 1\right) \right) \\
 83983 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C\left(T(T(3)), 9\right) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + 3\right) \right) \\
 83984 &:= \left(\left(C\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right), 9\right) + 8\right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 83986 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} - \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), 9\right) \times \sqrt{T(8)}\right) / (-T(6))\right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 83989 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C(T(T(3)), 9) \right) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) + 9 \right) \\
 83995 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C(T(T(3)), 9) \right) / T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) + T(5) \right) \\
 84234 &:= \left((T(T(8)) \times C(T(4), 2)) + C\left(T(T(3)), T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 84294 &:= \left((T(T(8)) + T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)) \times C\left((T(2) \times \sqrt{9}), 4\right) \right) \\
 84375 &:= \left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right) + (T(37) \times T(T(5))) \right) \\
 84381 &:= \left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) - (-C(T(4), 3) \times T((T(8) + 1))) \right) \\
 84386 &:= \left(T(T(8)) + (C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right), 3\right) \times T(T((-8) + T(6)))) \right) \\
 84420 &:= \left((T(C(8, \sqrt{4})) - 4) \times T(20) \right) \\
 84429 &:= \left(\left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) + C(T(4), T(2)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 84445 &:= \left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 5)) \right) \\
 84449 &:= \left(\left(-C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \right) - T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 84476 &:= \left((-8) + (T(T(4))^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \times T(C(7, 6)) \\
 84485 &:= -\left((T(C(8, 4)) \times (\sqrt{4} - T(8))) + (5) \right) \\
 84490 &:= \left(-T(C(8, 4)) \times (-T(T(4)) + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9+0}\right)\right)) \right) \\
 84491 &:= \left((-T(C(8, 4)) \times (-T(T(4)) + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right))) + 1 \right) \\
 84494 &:= \left((-T(C(8, 4)) \times (-T(T(4)) + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right))) + 4 \right) \\
 84497 &:= \left((T(C(8, 4)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) - (T(7)) \\
 84524 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) - ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(C(5, 2)))) + T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 84529 &:= -\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(C(5, 2))) - \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 84543 &:= \left(8 - (-T(T(4)) \times (T(T(C(5, \sqrt{4}))) - 3)) \right) \\
 84546 &:= \left((\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(4))) \times (C(T(5), 4) + T(6)) \right) \\
 84644 &:= -\left((C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) - (T(T((6+4))) \times T(T(4)))) \right) \\
 84665 &:= -\left(\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (-T(6) \times T((6 \times T(5)))) \right) \right) \\
 84679 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) + (T(T(4)) \times (-C((-6) + T(7), \sqrt{9}))) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 84748 &:= - \left(\left(\left(8^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) - \left(T(T(7)) \times C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84748 &:= - \left(\left(\left(8^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) - \left(T(T(7)) \times C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84833 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \times (-C(8,3)) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \\
 84843 &:= \left(C((-T(8)) + T(T(4))), 8 \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)^3 \right) \\
 84864 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^4} \times T((T(8) + C(6,4))) \right) \\
 84889 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times (8 \times 8) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84928 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(2^{\sqrt{T(8)}} \right) \right) \\
 84974 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(4), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) - T(T(4)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84984 &:= \left(-(8) \times \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right), 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 84995 &:= \left(- \left(T(C(8,4)) \right) - \left(- \left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 85264 &:= \left(C((8+5), T(2)) + (6)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 85442 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + C \left(T(5), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-(4) + T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \\
 85484 &:= \left(C(8,5) \times T(T(T(4))) - \left(T(8) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 85875 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T \left(\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) \right) \right) - \left(T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 85885 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - 5} \right)^8 + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 85934 &:= \left(T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + C \left(T(3), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 85987 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T \left(\left(T(5) \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) - C(8,7) \right) \\
 85998 &:= \left(T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + 9) + C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 86234 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - \left(- \left(C((6+2), 3) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86324 &:= \left(C(8,6) \times \left(T(T((T(3) \times 2))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 86349 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 6 \right) + \left(\left(T(T(3)) + T(4) \right) \times T(T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 86424 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times \left(\left(T(C(6,4))^2 \right) + (4) \right) \right) \\
 86445 &:= \left(T(T(8)) - \left(C(T(6), 4) \times T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times (-5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86448 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times \left(\left(T(C(6,4))^{\sqrt{4}} + 8 \right) \right) \right) \\ 86464 &:= \left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) + \left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \times 64 \right) \\ 86478 &:= \left(T(C(8,6)) \times \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T((T(7) - 8)) \right) \right) \\ 86604 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 6\right) - \left(-T(6) \times T(T(T(04))) \right) \right) \\ 86649 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 6\right) - \left(\left(-T(6) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) - T(9) \right) \right) \\ 86884 &:= \left(-T(C(8,6)) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (-T(8)) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\ 86939 &:= \left(T(8) \times T(69) - C(3, \sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 86943 &:= \left(T(8) \times T(69) + T\left(\sqrt{C(4,3)}\right) \right) \\ 86949 &:= \left(\left(-C(8,6) \times T(T(9)) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (-\sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 86968 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \times 8 \right) \\ 86968 &:= \left(\left(\left(8 \times C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \times 8 \right) \\ 87227 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C(T(7), 2) \right) - T((T(T(2)) + (7))) \right) \\ 87252 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C(T(7), 2) \right) - T((5 + T(T(2)))) \right) \\ 87259 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C(T(7), 2) \right) - 59 \right) \\ 87279 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 7\right) - T(T(T(2))) \right) + \left(-T(7) \times T(T(9)) \right) \right) \\ 87281 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C(T(7), 2) \right) - (T(8) + 1) \right) \\ 87288 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C(T(7), 2) \right) - \left(T(8) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\ 87289 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C(T(7), 2) \right) - \left(8 + T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \right) \\ 87295 &:= \left(-8 - \left(\left(-C(T(7), 2) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \right) + T(5) \right) \\ 87312 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C(T(7), (3-1)) \right) - T(T(2)) \right) \\ 87314 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C(T(7), (3-1)) \right) - 4 \right) \\ 87344 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(7)) \right) \times \left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{4}\right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\ 87357 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} - \left(\left(-T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) + C(T(5), 7) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87378 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (T(7) + (C(T(T(3)), 7) / 8)) \right) \\
 87378 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (T(7) + (C(T(T(3)), 7) / 8)) \right) \\
 87379 &:= \left((C(8, 7)^{T(3)} - 7) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 87384 &:= \left((C(8, 7)^{T(3)} + 8) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 87444 &:= - \left((T(8) - C((T(7) - T(4)), T(4))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 87584 &:= \left(((8 \times T(T(7))) - T(T(5))) \times C(8, \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 87591 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{T(C(8, 7))}) \times (-T(5) - T(91)) \right) \\
 87738 &:= \left(((T(8) \times T(T(7))) + C(7, T(3))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 87757 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(T(7)) \right) + (T(T(7)) - C(T(5), 7)) \right) \\
 87878 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(T(7 + \sqrt{T(8)})) \right) - T(C(7, \sqrt{T(8)})) \right) \\
 87878 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(T(7 + \sqrt{T(8)})) \right) - T(C(7, \sqrt{T(8)})) \right) \\
 88144 &:= \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), \sqrt{T(8)}) - ((1 + T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times (-T(T(T(4)))) \right) \\
 88326 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(8))) + T(C(T(3), T(2))) \right) \times T(6) \right) \\
 88443 &:= \left(T(T(8)) + ((T(C(8, T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(T(4))) - 3) \right) \\
 88444 &:= \left(T(T(8)) - ((T(C(8, T(\sqrt{4}))) \times (-T(T(4)))) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 88449 &:= \left(T(T(8)) + ((T(C(8, T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(T(4))) + \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 88487 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + \left((-8 - C(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(T(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 88488 &:= \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{T(8)} - T(C(8, 4))) \right) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \times T(8) \right) \\
 88488 &:= \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{T(8)} - T(C(8, 4))) \right) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \times T(8) \right) \\
 88644 &:= \left(T(T(8) - \sqrt{T(8)}) - (C(T(6), T(4)) / (-4)) \right) \\
 88794 &:= - \left((T(T(8)) - (T(8) \times T((C(7, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{4})))) \right) \\
 88899 &:= \left(- (T(8)) - \left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times (- (T(C(8, T(\sqrt{9}))) - T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \right) \right) \\
 88927 &:= \left(- (8) - \left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times \left(T(\sqrt{C(9, 2)}) - T(T(7)) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 88948 &:= \left(- (8) - \left(\left(- (T(T(8))) - T(C(9, T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 88962 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times (T(T(8)) + (T(C(9,6)))) \right) + T(T(2)) \right) \\
 88964 &:= \left(8 + \left((T(T(8)) + (T(C(9,6)))) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) \\
 88971 &:= \left(T(8) - \left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(C(7,1)))) \right) \right) \\
 89166 &:= - \left(\left(\left(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}) - T(T((1+6))) \right) \times T(T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 89258 &:= \left(8 + \left(T(C(9, T(2))) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) \right) \\
 89285 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) - T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 89294 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + (C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(2)) \times (-T(94))) \right) \right) \\
 89480 &:= \left((C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(80)) \right) \\
 89529 &:= - \left((T(C(8, \sqrt{9})) - ((T(5) \times T(2))^{\sqrt{9}})) \right) \\
 89594 &:= - \left((T(C(8, T(\sqrt{9}))) - ((T((T(5) + 9))^{\sqrt{4}})) \right) \\
 89746 &:= \left(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(4) - T(T(6)))) \right) \\
 89754 &:= - \left((T(C(8, \sqrt{9})) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(5)^{\sqrt{4}}))) \right) \\
 89824 &:= \left(C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times ((8^2) + T(T(T(4)))) \right) \\
 89828 &:= \left(8 - \left(- (T(9)) \times \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(2)) + (T(T(8))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89832 &:= \left(T((C(8, \sqrt{9}) + T(8))) \times T(T(3)) - T(T(2)) \right) \\
 89834 &:= \left(T((C(8, \sqrt{9}) + T(8))) \times T(T(3)) - 4 \right) \\
 89869 &:= \left((- (8) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \times (T(C(8,6)) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 89910 &:= \left(T(T(8)) \times (\sqrt{9} \times T((C(9,1) + 0))) \right) \\
 89911 &:= \left((T(T(8)) \times (\sqrt{9} \times T(9))) + C(1,1) \right) \\
 89931 &:= \left((T(T(8)) \times (\sqrt{9} \times T(9))) + T(T(C(3,1))) \right) \\
 89938 &:= \left(C(8, T(\sqrt{9})) - ((T(9) \times (-3)) \times T(T(8))) \right) \\
 89944 &:= - \left((C(8, \sqrt{9}) + (- (9) \times (T(4)^4))) \right) \\
 89958 &:= \left((T(C(8, \sqrt{9})) - T(9)) \times 58 \right) \\
 89994 &:= \left((T(T(8)) \times (\sqrt{9} \times T(9))) + C(9, T(\sqrt{4})) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 91344 &:= - \left(\left((T(T(9)) - 1) - C \left((T(T(3)) - \sqrt{4}), T(4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 91497 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left((1 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-T(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 91722 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \right) \times C(T(7), T(2)) \right) - T(T(2)) \right) \\
 91724 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \right) \times C(T(7), T(2)) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 91734 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \right) \times C(T(7), 3) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 91747 &:= \left(- (9) - \left(\left(- (1) - C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times T(7) \right) \right) \\
 91749 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \right) \times C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 91774 &:= \left((T(9) + 1) + \left(T(7) \times C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 91938 &:= \left((T(91) \times 9) + C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 92147 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + (C((T(T(T(2))) + 1), T(4)) / (-7)) \right) \right) \\
 92169 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)^2 \times \left(- (1) + T \left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 92294 &:= \left(- (C(9, T(2))) + C \left(\left(- (2) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T(4) \right) \right) \\
 92344 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + ((C((- (2) + T(T(3))), T(4)) - T(T(4)))) \right) \\
 92347 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + (C((- (2) + T(T(3))), T(4)) - T(7)) \right) \\
 92348 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + (C((- (2) + T(T(3))), T(4)) - T(8)) \right) \\
 92358 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times C(C(T(T(2)), 3), 5) \right) - T(T(8)) \right) \\
 92369 &:= \left(- (9) + C \left((- (2) + T(T(3))), \left(6 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 92372 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - C((- (2) + T(T(3))), (7 + 2)) \right) \right) \\
 92374 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), (3 + 7) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 92378 &:= C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), \sqrt{3 + 78} \right) \\
 92381 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + C((- (2) + T(T(3))), (8 + 1)) \right) \\
 92384 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + C \left(\left(\left(T(2)^3 \right) - 8 \right), T(4) \right) \right) \\
 92396 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + (C((- (2) + T(T(3))), 9) + (T(6))) \right) \\
 92399 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(C \left(\left(\left(2^{T(3)} \right) - T(9) \right), 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 92400 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9, 2)} \right) \right) \right) \times 400 \\
 92423 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), T(4) \right) + T((T(2) \times 3)) \right) \\
 92427 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), T(4) \right) + T(T(T(2))) \right) + (T(7)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 92429 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), T(4) \right) + (T(T(2)) + T(9)) \right) \\
 92429 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), T(4) \right) + (T(T(2)) + T(9)) \right) \\
 92451 &:= T(9)^{C(T(2), \sqrt{4})} + T(51) \\
 92456 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(2) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 92463 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), T(2) \right) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) + (T(6)) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 92470 &:= \left(\left(9 - C \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times (-70) \right) \\
 92483 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), T(4) \right) + T((8 + T(3))) \right) \\
 92489 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), T(4) \right) + \left(T(T(8)) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 92495 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), T(4) \right) + \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 92496 &:= \left(T((T(9) + 2)) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} - (C(9,6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 92498 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), T(4) \right) + T \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 92568 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 2 \right), 5 \right) \times T((T(6) + T(8))) \right) \\
 92589 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times T((-2) + T(5))) - T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 92609 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + C((-2) + T(6), 09) \right) \\
 92631 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(C(6,3))) + 1) \right) \\
 92659 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(9)^{T(2)} \right) - (6) \right) + T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 92694 &:= \left(C(9, T(2)) + \left(\left(T(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times T(4) \right) \right) \\
 92748 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) + T(C(T(4), 8))) \right) \\
 92749 &:= \left(\left(T(9)^{T(2)} \right) + \left(T(T(7)) \times C \left(4, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 92779 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) + (T(7) - T(T(9))) \\
 92815 &:= \left(\left(C \left((9 \times 2), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - 1 \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 92892 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{T(T(2))} \right) - T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 92973 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) + (T((T(7) + T(3)))) \right) \\
 92983 &:= \left(9 - \left(\left(- (2) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-T(C(8, T(3)))) \right) \\
 93170 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 3 \right) + 1 \right) \times 70 \right) \\
 93247 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) \times (-T(4))) \right) \times 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 93284 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9})^{T(3)} \right) \times 2 \right) - C(8, \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 93291 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9})^{T(3)} \right) \times 2 \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 93292 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9})^{T(3)} \right) \times 2 \right) - C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 93332 &:= \left(C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3 \right) + \left(\left(T(3)^{T(3)} \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 93342 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9})^{T(3)} \right) + C \left(T(3), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 93413 &:= \left(T(T(9)) + C \left(\left(T(T(3)) - \sqrt{4} \right), T((1+3)) \right) \right) \\
 93644 &:= \left(\left(T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3))) \right) + C \left(\left(T(6) - \sqrt{4} \right), T(4) \right) \right) \\
 93660 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), 3 \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \times 60 \right) \\
 93747 &:= \left(- \left(T(9) - T(3) \right) + \left(T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 93766 &:= \left(C \left(\sqrt{9}, 3 \right) + \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times T(T(6)) \right) - T(6) \right) \right) \\
 93769 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3 \right) - \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times T(T(6)) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 93779 &:= \left(\left(T(T((9-3))) \times T(T(7)) \right) - C \left(7, T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 93792 &:= \left(\left(T(T((9-3))) \times T(T(7)) \right) + \sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) \\
 93796 &:= \left(9 - \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(7))) \right) - C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), 6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 93822 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(3) \right) + \left(T(C(8,2)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) \right) \\
 93841 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) / 3 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + T(T(C(4,1))) \right) \\
 93863 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) / 3 + \left(T(C(8,6)) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 93888 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3 \right) - T \left(T(8) + T(8) \right) \right) \times (-T(8)) \right) \\
 93987 &:= \left(\left(-9 + T \left(C \left(T(3), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 94122 &:= \left(T \left(\left(C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \times \left(T(2)^{T(2)} \right) \right) \\
 94171 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times T(T(C(7,1))) \right) \right) \\
 94183 &:= \left(-9 - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times (-T(C(8, T(3)))) \right) \right) \\
 94276 &:= \left(\left(T(T(9)) + C \left(\sqrt{4}, 2 \right) \right) \times T((7+6)) \right) \\
 94282 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + T(4) \right) \right) + \left(T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(C(8,2)) \right) \right) \\
 94374 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + \left(-C \left((T(4)+3), 7 \right) \right) \times T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 94377 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(T(T(4)) \times \left(-C \left((T(3)+7), 7 \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94383 &:= (\sqrt{9} + (T(T(4)) \times C((T(T(3)) - 8), T(3)))) \\ 94386 &:= (T(\sqrt{9}) + (T(T(4)) \times C((T(T(3)) - 8), 6))) \\ 94389 &:= (9 + (T(T(4)) \times C((T(T(3)) - 8), T(\sqrt{9})))) \\ 94398 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) + (T(T(8)))))) \\ 94437 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (T(\sqrt{4}) \times C((T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3)), 7)))) \\ 94479 &:= (T(C((9 - \sqrt{4}), \sqrt{4})) \times (T(T(7)) + \sqrt{9})) \\ 94482 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times (-C(T(4), \sqrt{4}))) - T(T(8))) \times (-2)) \\ 94495 &:= (((T(9) \times T(4)) \times C(T(4), T(\sqrt{9}))) - (5)) \\ 94549 &:= ((T(T(9)) + 4) \times T((C(5, \sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{9}))) \\ 94549 &:= ((T(T(9)) + 4) \times T((C(5, \sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{9}))) \\ 94564 &:= ((C(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})), 5) \times 6) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 94642 &:= (C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(\sqrt{4})) + ((6^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))}) \times 2)) \\ 94710 &:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times (4 + T(T((C(7, 1) + 0)))) \\ 94711 &:= ((T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times (4 + T(T(7)))) + C(1, 1)) \\ 94731 &:= ((T(T(9)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T((7 + T(C(3, 1)))) \\ 94823 &:= ((T(T(9)) + \sqrt{4}) + (T(C(8, 2)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 94829 &:= (((T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(C(8, 2))) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \\ 94831 &:= ((T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + \sqrt{4}) \times (T(C(8, T(3))) + 1)) \\ 94855 &:= ((T((- (\sqrt{9}) + T(T(4)))) - C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 5)) \times (-5)) \\ 94864 &:= (((9 + \sqrt{4}) \times C(8, 6))^{\sqrt{4}}) \\ 94926 &:= (((T(9)^{T(\sqrt{4})}) + T(C(9, T(2)))) + T(T(6))) \\ 94962 &:= ((C(9 + T(4)), T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(6)) / T(T(2)) \\ 94976 &:= ((T(C(9, T(\sqrt{4}))) / \sqrt{9}) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 95284 &:= (T((- (9) + T((T(5) - 2)))) \times C(8, \sqrt{4})) \\ 95292 &:= (((C(9, 5)^2) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(2))) \\ 95326 &:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - (C(T(5), T(3)) \times (2 - T(6)))) \\ 95457 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times (- (5) + C((T(\sqrt{4}) + (T(5))), 7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 95459 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - T(5) \right) \right) \right) \right) + C((4 + T(5)), 9) \right) \\
 95459 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - T(5) \right) \right) \right) \right) + C((4 + T(5)), 9) \right) \\
 95471 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times C \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 7 \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 95474 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times C \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 95478 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times C \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 7 \right) \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 95487 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times (5 + C((T(4) + 8), 7)) \right) \\
 95553 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - (T((5 + T(5))) \times (-C(T(5), 3))) \right) \\
 95559 &:= \left(9 - \left(T((5 + T(5))) \times \left(-C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 95559 &:= \left(9 - \left(T((5 + T(5))) \times \left(-C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 95664 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 5 \right) \times \left(-(6) + C(T(6), 4) \right) \right) \\
 95745 &:= \left(\left(T(95) \times C(7, \sqrt{4}) \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 95754 &:= \left(\left(T(95) \times C(7, 5) \right) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 95816 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 5 \right) \times T(C(C(8, 1), 6)) \right) \\
 95822 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 5 \right) \times T(C(8, 2)) \right) + T(T(2)) \right) \\
 95899 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - \left(\left(C(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}) + \left((T(9)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 95931 &:= - \left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 5) - C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), (T(3) + 1)) \right) \right) \\
 95977 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 5) + (T((T(9) + T(7))) \times T(7)) \right) \\
 95991 &:= \left(\left(T(95) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9, 1)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 96222 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(6)) \right) \times T \left(C \left(\left(2^{T(2)} \right), 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 96244 &:= \left(- \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - \left(\left(C(T(6), 2) + T(T(T(4))) \right) \times \left(-T(T(4)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 96294 &:= \left(\left(T(9) \times T((C(6, T(2)) + T(9))) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 96369 &:= \left(\left(T(C(9, 6)) \times \sqrt{36} \right) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 96369 &:= \left(\left(T(C(9, 6)) \times \sqrt{36} \right) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 96385 &:= \left(\left(T(C(9, 6)) \times \left(T(T(3)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 96495 &:= \left(\left((T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) \times C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) \right) + (T(5)) \right) \\
 96577 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(6) \right), (5 + 7) \right) / T(7) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 96597 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{-6+T(5)} \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 7 \right) \right) \\
 96852 &:= \left(C(9,6) \times \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times 5 \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 96894 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(T(T(6)) - C \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 96999 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(T(T(6)) \times C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97242 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(C(7,2)^4 \right) \right) / 2 \right) \\
 97257 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(T(C(7,2)) \times \left(- \left(T(5) - T(T(7)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97434 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(T(T(7)) \times \left(-C(T(4),3) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 97475 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(T(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - C(T(7),5) \right) \right) \\
 97542 &:= \left(\left(- (9) + C(T(7),5) \right) - \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right)^{T(T(2))} \right) \right) \\
 97548 &:= \left(\left(9 + C(T(7),5) \right) - T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97554 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - C(T(7),5) \right) \right) - \left(T(T(5)) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97569 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(9) - C(T(7),5) \right) \right) - T \left(\left(6 \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97584 &:= \left(\left(T(9) + C(T(7),5) \right) - T \left(\left(T(8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97596 &:= \left(T(9) + \left(C(T(7),5) - \sqrt{9^6} \right) \right) \\
 97598 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(- \left(C(T(7),5) + T((T(9) - 8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97719 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) / 7 \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T(7), \left(- (1) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97728 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) + \left(C(T(7),T(2)) + T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 97784 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(7) \right) \right) - C \left(T(7), \left(8 - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97852 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(- \left(T(T(7)) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + C(5,2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97881 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(\left(C \left(7, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(8)) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \\
 97882 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(7 \times T(T(8)) \right) \right) - C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2) \right) \right) \\
 97895 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(T(T(7)) - C \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 97902 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(7 \times T(C(9,02)) \right) \right) \\
 97979 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7 \right), 9 \right) + (7) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97979 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7 \right), 9 \right) + (7) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97992 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(T(7) + T(9) \right) \right) \right) \times C(9,2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 97993 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(7) \right) + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) \right) / 3 \right) \\ 97994 &:= \left(\left((T(9) + (7)) + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) \right) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 98175 &:= - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times (T(8) - 1)) - C(T(7), 5) \right) \right) \\ 98256 &:= - \left(\left((\sqrt{9} - (C(C(8, 2), 5))) + T(6) \right) \right) \\ 98283 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + (C(C(8, 2), (8 - 3))) \right) \\ 98285 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - (8 + C(28, 5)) \right) \right) \\ 98289 &:= \left(9 + C(C(8, 2), (8 - \sqrt{9})) \right) \\ 98289 &:= \left(9 + C(C(8, 2), (8 - \sqrt{9})) \right) \\ 98399 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + \left((T(T(8)) \times C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9})) / (-9) \right) \right) \right) \\ 98424 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 8) / \sqrt{4} - T(T(2)^4) \right) \right) \\ 98429 &:= \left(9 + \left((T(T(8)) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(2))) / 9 \right) \right) \\ 98448 &:= \left(C(9, \sqrt{T(8)}) \times (-4 + T(48)) \right) \\ 98460 &:= \left((T(9) + T(C(8, T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 60 \right) \\ 98468 &:= \left((T(\sqrt{9}) + T(C(8, \sqrt{4}))) \times (T(T(6)) + 8) \right) \\ 98475 &:= \left((T((\sqrt{9} + T(8))) / 4) + C(T(7), 5) \right) \\ 98571 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + (T(T(8)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(C(7, 1)))) \right) \\ 98575 &:= \left(T((\sqrt{9} \times 8)) - (5 - C(T(7), 5)) \right) \\ 98634 &:= \left(\left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(C(8, 6))) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 98646 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9}^8) \times C(6, 4) + T(T(6)) \right) \right) \\ 98649 &:= \left(\left(C((-9) + T(8), T(6)) / T(\sqrt{4}) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\ 98664 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) - \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(6) \right), T(6) \right) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\ 98669 &:= \left(\left(-(\sqrt{9}) + C\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(6) \right), T(6) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\ 98679 &:= \left(9 + \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(6) \right), 7 \right) / 9 \right) \right) \\ 98715 &:= \left(T\left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 8) \right) + C(T(7), (1 \times 5)) \right) \\ 98721 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) + (C(T(7), (T(T(2)) - 1))) \right) \\ 98769 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times (T(8) + (7))) + C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98778 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times (T(8) + (C(T(7), 7) / T(8)))) \\
 98826 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \times (-26) \\
 98835 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9}^8 \right) + C(8, T(3)) \right) \times T(5) \right) \\
 98838 &:= \left(- (T((9+8))) \times \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3 \right) - T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 98874 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(8)) \right) - (C(T(7), 4)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 98875 &:= \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) + (-8) + T(8) \right) \right) + (C(T(7), 5)) \\
 98889 &:= \left(\left((-\sqrt{9}) + T(T(8)) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98889 &:= \left(\left((-\sqrt{9}) + T(T(8)) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98895 &:= \left(\left(T(T(C(9, 8))) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times 95 \right) \\
 98945 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(9)) + \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right) - (T(4)^5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 98949 &:= \left((-\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(8)) \right) + C \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + \sqrt{4} \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98952 &:= \left(\left((-\sqrt{9}) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - (C(T(5), T(2))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 98997 &:= \left(T(9) + \left((-T(8)) + T \left(C(9, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times T(7) \right) \\
 99249 &:= \left((T(9) \times (T(C(9, 2)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 99371 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(C(9, \sqrt{9}) \right) - T(T(3)) \right) \times T(7) - 1 \right) \right) \\
 99374 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(C(9, \sqrt{9}) \right) - T(T(3)) \right) \times T(7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 99378 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(C(9, 3)) \right) \times T(7) - T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 99474 &:= \left(\left(T(9) \times T \left(T \left((9 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) - C(7, \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 99475 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(9)) / (-\sqrt{9}) \right) + T(T(T(4))) \right) + (C(T(7), 5)) \right) \\
 99487 &:= \left(\left(T(9) \times T \left(T \left((9 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) - C(8, 7) \right) \\
 99492 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left((9 + \sqrt{9}), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(9) - T(2) \right) \right) \\
 99496 &:= \left(\left(T(9) \times T \left(T \left((9 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + C(T(\sqrt{9}), 6) \right) \\
 99588 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) - C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), T(5) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 99595 &:= \left(\left(T(9) \times (-9) \right) + \left(C(5, \sqrt{9})^5 \right) \right) \\
 99723 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(C(9, \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(7) - T(T(2)) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99732 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T(7) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) + T(2) \right) \\
 99774 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - (7) \right) \times T(7) \right) + T(4) \right) \\
 99775 &:= \left(\left(- (T(9)) + T \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (7) \right) \right) \right) \right) + (C(T(7), 5)) \right) \\
 99793 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T(97) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), 3 \right) \right) \\
 99795 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T(7) \right) - T(9) \right) - T(T(5)) \right) \\
 99837 &:= \left(T(9) - \left(\left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - T(3) \right) \times (-T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 99874 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T(8) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 99879 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T(8) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 99939 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(- \left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(T(T(3)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 99948 &:= \left(- (T(T(9))) + \left(C \left((T(T(9)) / T(9)), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T(8) \right) \right) \\
 99954 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T \left((5 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 99972 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T(7) \right) + T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 99974 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times 74 \right) \\
 99977 &:= \left(T(9) + \left(\left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T(7) \right) - T(7) \right) \right) \\
 99978 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T(7) \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 99981 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(T \left((T(9) + T(9)) \right) + T \left(T \left(C \left(8, 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 99987 &:= \left(T(T(9)) + \left(\left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T(8) \right) \times T(7) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

2 Binomial-Coefficient-Triangular-Square-Root-Type Selfie Numbers - Reverse Order of Digits

This section brings **selfie numbers** written in reverse order of Digits. The results are up to 5-digits numbers. It is divided in three subsections. One with symmetric and consecutive. Second symmetric and nonconsecutive and third general values.

2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned}
 3780 &:= 0 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3)) & 3785 &:= 5 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3)) \\
 3781 &:= 1 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3)) & 3786 &:= 6 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3)) \\
 3782 &:= 2 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3)) & 3787 &:= 7 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3)) \\
 3783 &:= 3 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3)) & 3788 &:= 8 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3)) \\
 3784 &:= 4 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3)) & 3789 &:= 9 + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(7,3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3990 &:= 0 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 3991 &:= 1 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 3992 &:= 2 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 3993 &:= 3 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 3994 &:= 4 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 3995 &:= 5 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 3996 &:= 6 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 3997 &:= 7 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 3998 &:= 8 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 3999 &:= 9 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9990 &:= 0 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\ 9991 &:= 1 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\ 9992 &:= 2 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\ 9993 &:= 3 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\ 9994 &:= 4 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\ 9995 &:= 5 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\ 9996 &:= 6 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\ 9997 &:= 7 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\ 9998 &:= 8 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\ 9999 &:= 9 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 09450 &:= 0 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \\ 09451 &:= 1 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \\ 09452 &:= 2 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \\ 09453 &:= 3 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \\ 09454 &:= 4 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \\ 09455 &:= 5 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \\ 09456 &:= 6 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \\ 09457 &:= 7 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \\ 09458 &:= 8 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \\ 09459 &:= 9 + C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 90 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19880 &:= 0 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \\ 19881 &:= 1 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \\ 19882 &:= 2 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \\ 19883 &:= 3 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \\ 19884 &:= 4 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \\ 19885 &:= 5 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \\ 19886 &:= 6 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \\ 19887 &:= 7 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \\ 19888 &:= 8 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \\ 19889 &:= 9 + 8 \times T(C(8, \sqrt{9} + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20580 &:= 0 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \\ 20581 &:= 1 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \\ 20582 &:= 2 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \\ 20583 &:= 3 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \\ 20584 &:= 4 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \\ 20585 &:= 5 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \\ 20586 &:= 6 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \\ 20587 &:= 7 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \\ 20588 &:= 8 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \\ 20589 &:= 9 + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, 5) + T(T(T(T(02)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24570 &:= 0 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24571 &:= 1 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24572 &:= 2 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24573 &:= 3 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24574 &:= 4 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24575 &:= 5 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24576 &:= 6 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24577 &:= 7 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24578 &:= 8 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$24579 := 9 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2)$$

$$25480 := 0 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$25481 := 1 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$25482 := 2 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$25483 := 3 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$25484 := 4 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$25485 := 5 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$25486 := 6 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$25487 := 7 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$25488 := 8 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$25489 := 9 + C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(T(5), T(2))$$

$$27930 := 0 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$27931 := 1 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$27932 := 2 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$27933 := 3 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$27934 := 4 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$27935 := 5 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$27936 := 6 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$27937 := 7 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$27938 := 8 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$27939 := 9 + T(T(3)) \times C(\sqrt{9} \times 7, T(2))$$

$$34580 := 0 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$34581 := 1 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$34582 := 2 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$34583 := 3 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$34584 := 4 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$34585 := 5 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$34586 := 6 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$34587 := 7 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$34588 := 8 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$34589 := 9 + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 5 \right) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3)$$

$$35490 := 0 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$35491 := 1 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$35492 := 2 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$35493 := 3 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$35494 := 4 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$35495 := 5 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$35496 := 6 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$35497 := 7 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$35498 := 8 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$35499 := 9 + T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \times C(T(5), 3)$$

$$41990 := 0 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$41991 := 1 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$41992 := 2 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$41993 := 3 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$41994 := 4 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$41995 := 5 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$41996 := 6 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$41997 := 7 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$41998 := 8 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$41999 := 9 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) / (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$43740 := 0 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$43741 := 1 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$43742 := 2 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$43743 := 3 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$43744 := 4 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$43745 := 5 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$43746 := 6 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$43747 := 7 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$43748 := 8 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$43749 := 9 + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$44850 := 0 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$44851 := 1 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$44852 := 2 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$44853 := 3 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$44854 := 4 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$44855 := 5 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$44856 := 6 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$44857 := 7 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$44858 := 8 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$44859 := 9 + C(5 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$48510 := 0 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48511 := 1 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48512 := 2 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48513 := 3 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48514 := 4 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48515 := 5 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48516 := 6 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48517 := 7 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48518 := 8 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48519 := 9 + T(T(1+5)) \times T(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$48930 := 0 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$48931 := 1 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$48932 := 2 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$48933 := 3 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$48934 := 4 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$48935 := 5 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$48936 := 6 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$48937 := 7 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$48938 := 8 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$48939 := 9 + T(C(T(3), \sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$49560 := 0 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$49561 := 1 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$49562 := 2 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$49563 := 3 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$49564 := 4 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$49565 := 5 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$49566 := 6 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$49567 := 7 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$49568 := 8 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$49569 := 9 + (T(T(6)) + 5) \times T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$54930 := 0 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$54931 := 1 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$54932 := 2 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$54933 := 3 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$54934 := 4 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$54935 := 5 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$54936 := 6 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$54937 := 7 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$54938 := 8 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$54939 := 9 + C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + 5))$$

$$56280 := 0 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(2)) + C(T(6), T(5))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 56281 &:= 1 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56282 &:= 2 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56283 &:= 3 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56284 &:= 4 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56285 &:= 5 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56286 &:= 6 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56287 &:= 7 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56288 &:= 8 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56289 &:= 9 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(2) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65780 &:= 0 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \\ 65781 &:= 1 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \\ 65782 &:= 2 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \\ 65783 &:= 3 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \\ 65784 &:= 4 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \\ 65785 &:= 5 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \\ 65786 &:= 6 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \\ 65787 &:= 7 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \\ 65788 &:= 8 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \\ 65789 &:= 9 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(C(8,7))} \right) + 5, T(6) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76440 &:= 0 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \\ 76441 &:= 1 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \\ 76442 &:= 2 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \\ 76443 &:= 3 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \\ 76444 &:= 4 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \\ 76445 &:= 5 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \\ 76446 &:= 6 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 76447 &:= 7 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \\ 76448 &:= 8 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \\ 76449 &:= 9 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7))) \\ 79920 &:= 0 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \\ 79921 &:= 1 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \\ 79922 &:= 2 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \\ 79923 &:= 3 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \\ 79924 &:= 4 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \\ 79925 &:= 5 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \\ 79926 &:= 6 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \\ 79927 &:= 7 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \\ 79928 &:= 8 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \\ 79929 &:= 9 + T \left(T(2 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 82440 &:= 0 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 82441 &:= 1 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 82442 &:= 2 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 82443 &:= 3 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 82444 &:= 4 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 82445 &:= 5 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 82446 &:= 6 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 82447 &:= 7 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 82448 &:= 8 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \\ 82449 &:= 9 + C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 83980 &:= 0 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \times T(3) / T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\ 83981 &:= 1 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \times T(3) / T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\ 83982 &:= 2 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \times T(3) / T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\ 83983 &:= 3 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \times T(3) / T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\ 83984 &:= 4 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \times T(3) / T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\ 83985 &:= 5 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \times T(3) / T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\ 83986 &:= 6 + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) \times T(3) / T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$83987 := 7 + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 9\right) \times T(3) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)$$

$$83988 := 8 + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 9\right) \times T(3) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)$$

$$83989 := 9 + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 9\right) \times T(3) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)$$

$$89250 := 0 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$89251 := 1 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$89252 := 2 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$89253 := 3 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$89254 := 4 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$89255 := 5 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$89256 := 6 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$89257 := 7 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$89258 := 8 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$89259 := 9 + 5^2 \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)$$

$$95550 := 0 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$95551 := 1 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$95552 := 2 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$95553 := 3 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$95554 := 4 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$95555 := 5 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$95556 := 6 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$95557 := 7 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$95558 := 8 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$95559 := 9 + T(5 + T(5)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$96390 := 0 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96391 := 1 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96392 := 2 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96393 := 3 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96394 := 4 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96395 := 5 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96396 := 6 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96397 := 7 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96398 := 8 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96399 := 9 + T(C(9,3)) \times (T(6) + T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$96480 := 0 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$96481 := 1 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$96482 := 2 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$96483 := 3 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$96484 := 4 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$96485 := 5 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$96486 := 6 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$96487 := 7 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$96488 := 8 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$96489 := 9 - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))$$

$$98280 := 0 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98281 := 1 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98282 := 2 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98283 := 3 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98284 := 4 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98285 := 5 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98286 := 6 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98287 := 7 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98288 := 8 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98289 := 9 + C\left(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98420 := 0 + C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times T(T(8)) / 9$$

$$98421 := 1 + C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times T(T(8)) / 9$$

$$98422 := 2 + C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times T(T(8)) / 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98423 &:= 3 + C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(8)) / 9 \\ 98424 &:= 4 + C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(8)) / 9 \\ 98425 &:= 5 + C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(8)) / 9 \\ 98426 &:= 6 + C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(8)) / 9 \\ 98427 &:= 7 + C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(8)) / 9 \\ 98428 &:= 8 + C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(8)) / 9 \\ 98429 &:= 9 + C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(8)) / 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98670 &:= 0 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 98671 &:= 1 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 98672 &:= 2 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 98673 &:= 3 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 98674 &:= 4 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 98675 &:= 5 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 98676 &:= 6 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 98677 &:= 7 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98678 &:= 8 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 98679 &:= 9 + C(T(7), T(6)) / T(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ 99960 &:= 0 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\ 99961 &:= 1 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\ 99962 &:= 2 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\ 99963 &:= 3 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\ 99964 &:= 4 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\ 99965 &:= 5 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\ 99966 &:= 6 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\ 99967 &:= 7 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\ 99968 &:= 8 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \\ 99969 &:= 9 + T(T(6) / \sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.1. Most of the *selfie numbers* appearing in the subsection below are with lot of extra brackets "(...)". These can be removed easily after making simplifications.

2.2 General Representations

$$\begin{aligned} 354 &:= \left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(5)) \right) \times 3 \right) \\ 452 &:= \left(-T(2) + C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\ 455 &:= C(T(5), \sqrt{5+4}) \\ 495 &:= C\left(\left(T(5) - \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) \\ 924 &:= C\left(\left(4 \times T(2) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 945 &:= \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times 9 \right) \\ 0429 &:= -T(\sqrt{9}) + T\left(\sqrt{T(T(T(2))) + T(40)} \right) \\ 0452 &:= \left(-T(2) + C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4+0})) \right) \\ 0455 &:= C\left(T(5), \sqrt{5+4+0} \right) \\ 0495 &:= C\left(\left(T(5) - \sqrt{9} \right), (4+0) \right) \\ 0748 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + (7+0) \right) \\ 0794 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-9 + T(T((7+0))) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0924 &:= C\left((4 \times T(2)), T(\sqrt{9+0})\right) \\ 0945 &:= \left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{4}\right) \times (9+0)\right) \\ 1287 &:= C\left(\left(7 + \sqrt{T(8)}\right), (T(T(2)) - 1)\right) \\ 1329 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{C(9,2)}\right), 3\right) - 1\right) \\ 1344 &:= \left(\left(4^{T(\sqrt{4})}\right) \times T(T(C(3,1)))\right) \\ 1383 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - C(3,1)\right) \\ 1473 &:= \left(3 - \left(- (7) \times T\left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - 1\right)\right)\right)\right) \\ 1478 &:= \left(T(T(8)) + \left(T(T(7)) \times \sqrt{C(4,1)}\right)\right) \\ 1479 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{C(9,7)}\right) + T((T(T(4)) - 1))\right) \\ 1489 &:= \left(T\left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + C(4,1)\right) \\ 1495 &:= \left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right) + T((T(T(4)) - 1))\right) \\ 1589 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) - ((T(C(8,5)) - 1))\right)\right) \\ 1595 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9}\right), 5\right)\right) - 1\right) \\ 1598 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(8, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) + \sqrt{5-1}\right) \\ 1792 &:= \left(\left(2^{T(\sqrt{9})}\right) \times T(C(7,1))\right) \\ 1842 &:= \left(- (T(T(2))) + \left(T\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \times C(8,1)\right)\right) \\ 1864 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(T(6))\right) \times C(8,1)\right) \\ 1869 &:= \left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) - (T(T(6)) \times (-C(8,1)))\right) \\ 1899 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{9} + T((T(8) - 1))\right)\right) \\ 1996 &:= \left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{9}\right) + T(T((9 - 1)))\right) \\ 2214 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(C(12,2))\right) \\ 2292 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(2) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right)\right) + T((2 + T(T(T(2))))))\right) \\ 2297 &:= \left(C\left(\left(T(7) - \sqrt{9}\right), T(2)\right) - T(2)\right) \\ 2436 &:= \left(6 \times T\left(C\left(\left(T(3) + \sqrt{4}\right), 2\right)\right)\right) \\ 2437 &:= \left((T(T(7)) \times T(3)) + C(\sqrt{4}, 2)\right) \\ 2482 &:= \left(- (T(2)) + T\left(\sqrt{C(8,4)^2}\right)\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2489 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{9}) + (T(C(8,4)) - 2) \right) \\ 2529 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(2))) \right) \\ 2548 &:= \left(C(8, \sqrt{4}) \times T((T(5) - 2)) \right) \\ 2582 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) / T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \\ 2643 &:= \left(\left((T(T(3))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 6 \right) - T(2) \right) \\ 2648 &:= \left(T \left((T(8) \times \sqrt{4}) \right) + C(6, T(2)) \right) \\ 2674 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times (7 + C(T(6), T(2))) \right) \\ 2849 &:= - \left(\left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(T(4)))) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\ 2864 &:= \left((T(T(T(4))) - 6) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(2) \right) \right) \\ 2922 &:= \left(C \left((T(2)^{T(2)}), \sqrt{9} \right) - T(2) \right) \\ 2923 &:= \left(C \left((3^{T(2)}), \sqrt{9} \right) - 2 \right) \\ 2946 &:= \left(C \left((T(2) \times 9), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + (T(6)) \right) \\ 2975 &:= \left(5 \times T \left(\left(T(7) + \sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) \right) \right) \\ 2983 &:= \left(T((T(T(3)) + T(8))) + C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), T(2) \right) \right) \\ 2993 &:= \left(T \left((T(T(T(3))) / \sqrt{9}) \right) - T \left((T(\sqrt{9}) - 2) \right) \right) \\ 3279 &:= \left(C(3,2) + C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\ 3297 &:= \left(C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right) + T((2 \times 3)) \right) \\ 3346 &:= \left(C \left(T(6), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T((3 \times T(T(3)))) \right) \\ 3395 &:= \left((T(5)^{\sqrt{9}}) + C(T(3), 3) \right) \\ 3447 &:= \left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T \left((T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3)) \right) \right) \\ 3454 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4^5}) + T((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) \right) \\ 3468 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times C(6,4) \right) + 3 \right) \\ 3484 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + T(((8 \times T(4)) + 3)) \right) \\ 3495 &:= \left((T(5)^{\sqrt{9}}) + C(T(4), 3) \right) \\ 3798 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (\sqrt{9} + T(C(7,3))) \right) \\ 3945 &:= \left((- (T(5)) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right)) \times 3 \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3974 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + T(T(7)) \right) + (T(C(9,3))) \right) \\ 3979 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(T(7)) \right) + (T(C(9,3))) \right) \\ 4144 &:= \left(\left(T(C(T(4), \sqrt{4})) + 1 \right) \times 4 \right) \\ 4244 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left((T(T(4)) - T(2))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\ 4248 &:= \left(T(8) \times \left(C(T(4), T(2)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\ 4275 &:= \left(T((T(T(5)) - T(7))) - C(T(2), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 4333 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), 3) + T\left(\left(T(T(T(3))) / T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \\ 4359 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(T((5 + T(3))^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \\ 4414 &:= \left((-4) + T(T((1 + T(4)))) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 4422 &:= \left(2 \times T\left(C\left(2 + T(4), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \\ 4428 &:= \left(T(8) \times \left(T(2) + C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) \right) \\ 4429 &:= \left(\left(\left(9^{T(2)} \right) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) + (T(T(4))) \right) \\ 4439 &:= \left(-\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) - C(T(T(3)), 4) \right) \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \\ 4443 &:= \left((C(T(T(3)), 4) - T(T(T(4)))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\ 4445 &:= \left(\left(T(54) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - T(4) \right) \\ 4448 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 4\right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 4454 &:= \left(T\left(-\left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (T(T(5))))\right)\right) - T\left(\left(T(4) + T\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})))\right)\right) \right) \\ 4482 &:= \left(T(T(2)) \times \left(T(T(8)) + \left(T(\sqrt{4})^4 \right) \right) \right) \\ 4485 &:= \left((T(T(5)) \times T(8)) + \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\ 4544 &:= -\left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + \left(-T(4) \times C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \right) \\ 4545 &:= \left(-5 - \left(-T(4) \times C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\ 4549 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(4))) \right) + (C(T(5), T(4))) \right) \\ 4593 &:= \left(3 \times \left(-9 + T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\ 4622 &:= \left((C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(6))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\ 4623 &:= \left((C(T(3), T(2)) \times T(T(6))) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 4686 &:= \left(((T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(6)) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 4689 &:= \left(T(T(9)) + C\left((8 + T(6)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4695 &:= \left(5 \times \left((T(9) \times T(6)) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\ 4722 &:= \left(T(T(2)) \times \left(T(2) + \left(T(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\ 4725 &:= \left(\left(T(5)^2 \right) \times C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\ 4817 &:= \left(-\left(T(7)\right) + C\left(\left(-1 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right), 4\right) \right) \\ 4823 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(2))) \right) - C\left(8, \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\ 4824 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right)\right) \right) - \left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\ 4836 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times T(T(3)) \right) - C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\ 4842 &:= \left(\left(T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) + \left(T(T(8)) / T\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \right) \right) \\ 4844 &:= -\left(\left(T(T(T(4))) + \left(-4 \times T\left(C\left(8, T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 4852 &:= \left(T\left(T\left(\left(-2 + T(5)\right)\right)\right) + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)^{\sqrt{4}}}\right) \right) \\ 4885 &:= \left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \\ 4929 &:= \left(\left(-\left(T(T(9))\right) - T(T(T(2))) \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), 4\right) \right) \\ 4932 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) + \sqrt{9^4} \right) \\ 4943 &:= \left(T\left(\left(\left(T(T(3)) + T(T(4))\right) + T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) + T(T(T(4))) \right) \\ 4944 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(T(T(4)) \times T(9) \right) - T\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \right) \right) \\ 4995 &:= \left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9 \times 9}\right) - T(4) \right) \\ 5245 &:= \left(C\left(T(5), T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) + \left(2 \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\ 5349 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left(3^5 \right) \right) \right) \\ 5449 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) + \left(-4 \times \left(T(T(T(4))) - T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 5484 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) - T(5) \right) \right) \\ 5485 &:= \left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - \left(-4 \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\ 5493 &:= \left(3 - \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times T\left(4 \times T(5)\right) \right) \right) \\ 5559 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \times \left(T(T(5)) / 5 \right) \right) + T(5) \right) \\ 5592 &:= \left(\left(-2 - T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \right) \times \left(T(T(5)) / (-5) \right) \right) \\ 5844 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), 4\right) - \left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5849 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 4 \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - 5 \right) \right) \right) \\ 6462 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) / T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 6489 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(4 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 6492 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-T \left(46 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 6545 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), 6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 6639 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(- \left(3 \right) \times T \left(66 \right) \right) \right) \\ 6748 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + T \left(4 \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(7, 6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 6783 &:= \left(\left(\left(3\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(6 \right) \right) \\ 6792 &:= \left(\left(T \left(2 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9}^7 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 6874 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(7 \right) + \left(T \left(C \left(8, 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 6945 &:= \left(\left(T \left(5 \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) + \left(T \left(C \left(9, 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 6984 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + 9 \right) \times 6 \right) \\ 7448 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(8, 4 \right) \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(7 \right) \right) \\ 7524 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(5 + T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\ 7693 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) - T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\ 7724 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) / 7 - \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\ 7752 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) / \sqrt{7 \times 7} \right) \\ 7759 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) / 7 + 7 \right) \right) \\ 7884 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(8 \right) + T \left(C \left(8, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 7975 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), 7 \right) + T \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 7983 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) / \left(-7 \right) \right) \right) \\ 8235 &:= \left(T \left(5 \right) \times \left(T \left(32 \right) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\ 8244 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(T \left(C \left(4, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(8 \right) \right) \\ 8281 &:= \left(1 + \left(8 \times T \left(T \left(\left(T \left(2 \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 8424 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(\left(2 + T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(8 \right) \right) \\ 8475 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8562 &:= \left(C((T(2) \times 6), 5) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\8646 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4})) \times 6 \right) + T(T(8)) \right) \\8757 &:= \left(T(C(7, 5)) - \left(- (T(T(7))) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \\8967 &:= \left((T(T(7)) + (T(6))) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{C(9, 8)})\right) \right) \\8999 &:= \left(- (T(9)) + \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(\sqrt{9})) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\9044 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) / T(\sqrt{09}) \right) \\9252 &:= \left((2 + T(T(C(5, 2)))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\9254 &:= \left(- \left((\sqrt{4} + (5)) \right) + \left(T(T(T(2)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\9255 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(T(T(C(5, 2))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\9261 &:= \left(C((1 + 6), 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\9262 &:= \left(- (2) + \left((T(6)^{T(2)}) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\9317 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(- (1) - C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\9366 &:= \left((T(T(6)) + C(T(6), 3)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\9465 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) \right) \right) \\9527 &:= \left(- (T(7)) + \left(T(T(T(2))) \times C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\9534 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T((T(3) \times 5)) \right) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\9555 &:= \left(T(T((T(5) / 5))) \times C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \\9576 &:= \left(6 \times T\left(C((-7) + T(5), \sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\9582 &:= \left((T(T(2)) \times T(C(8, 5))) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\9689 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 8) - (T(6)) \right) / T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\9723 &:= \left((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(2)) \times 7)) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\9745 &:= \left(\left(T(T(C(5, \sqrt{4}))) \times 7 \right) - T(T(9)) \right) \\9924 &:= \left(\left(T((T(T(4)) + 2)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\9993 &:= \left(((T(T(T(3))) - 9) \times T(9)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\00435 &:= \left(C(T(5), 3) - \sqrt{400} \right) \\01287 &:= C\left(\left(7 + \sqrt{T(8)}\right), -((2 - 10))\right)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}01343 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) , T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(3 + 10 \right) \right) \\01346 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(6 \right) , T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(T \left(3 \right) + 10 \right) \right) \\01398 &:= \left(C \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} , \sqrt{9} \right) + T \left(\left(- \left(3 \right) + T \left(10 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\01584 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T \left(C \left(8, 5 \right) \right) \right) + 10 \right) \right) \\01589 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(C \left(8, 5 \right) \right) \right) - 10 \right) \\01947 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(7 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) , 9 \right) - T \left(10 \right) \right) \\01969 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(6 \right) \right) , \sqrt{9} \right) - T \left(10 \right) \right) \\02457 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(7 \right) , 5 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) / 20 \right) \\02983 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(3 \right) + 8 \right) , T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(20 \right) \right) \\03968 &:= \left(8 \times T \left(\left(C \left(6, T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(30 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\04965 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right) , \left(6 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 40 \right) \\05145 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right) , \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(- \left(1 - 50 \right) \right) \right) \\05545 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(T \left(5 \right) , T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(-50 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\06475 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right) , 7 \right) + \sqrt{T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) + 60} \right) \\06495 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right) , \left(9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(60 \right) \right) \\06835 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right) , \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) + T \left(60 \right) \right) \\06856 &:= \left(T \left(6 \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right) , \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) + T \left(60 \right) \right) \right) \\07427 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(7 \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(2 \right) , \sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(70 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\09486 &:= \left(\left(6 \times T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(90 \right) \right) \\09842 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) , T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) / 90 \right) \\10389 &:= \left(\left(T \left(9 \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(C \left(3, 01 \right) \right) \right) \\11374 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(3 \right) + C \left(1, 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\11628 &:= C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) - 2 \right) , C \left(\left(6 - 1 \right) , 1 \right) \right) \\11629 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right) , \left(6 - 1 \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\11936 &:= \left(- \left(C \left(T \left(6 \right) , 3 \right) + \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(T \left(11 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\11969 &:= \left(\left(9 \times C \left(T \left(6 \right) , \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - C \left(1, 1 \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

- 11989 := $\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + C(1,1)$
- 12342 := $\left(\left(T(T(T(2)))^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) + T(T((T(3) \times C(2,1)))) \right)$
- 12354 := $\left(\left(C(\sqrt{4} + T(5), T(3)) - T(T(T(2))) \right) - 1 \right)$
- 12375 := $\left(C(T(5) + \sqrt{7-3}, T(T(2))) - 1 \right)$
- 12434 := $\left(\sqrt{4} \times ((C(T(T(3)), 4) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) + 1 \right)$
- 12468 := $\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (T(64) - C(2,1)) \right)$
- 12478 := $\left(\left(T((T(8) + T(7))) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) - C(2,1) \right)$
- 12482 := $\left(\left(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{8^4}) \right) + C(2,1) \right)$
- 12497 := $\left(\left(T(T(7) + T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) + C(2,1)$
- 12539 := $\left(\left(-(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(3))) \right) \times T(C(5,2)) \right) - 1$
- 12544 := $\left(\left(4 \times T(\sqrt{4} + (5)) \right) \right)^{C(2,1)}$
- 12549 := $\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T((T(5) - C(2,1)))) \right) \right)$
- 12598 := $\left(\left(T(8 + T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - C(2,1)$
- 12647 := $\left(C(T(7) - T(\sqrt{4}), T(6)) - (2 + 1) \right)$
- 12695 := $\left(\left(T(C(5, \sqrt{9})) \right) \times T(T(6)) - T((T(2) + 1)) \right)$
- 12739 := $\left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{9}), 3) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) \right) - 1$
- 12849 := $\left(C(T(\sqrt{9}) + T(4), 8) - (21) \right)$
- 12858 := $\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - C(T(5), 8) \right) \times (-C(2,1)) \right)$
- 12859 := $\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) - C(T(5), 8) \right) \times (-2) \right) + 1$
- 12878 := $\left(\left((T(T(8)) \times T(T(7))) / T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) + C(2,1) \right)$
- 12919 := $\left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 1, T(\sqrt{9})) / T(2) \right) - 1 \right)$
- 12938 := $\left(\left(C(8,3) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) + C(2,1)$
- 12958 := $\left(\left((-T(8)) \times T(T(5)) \right) \times (-\sqrt{9}) \right) - C(2,1)$
- 12989 := $\left(-(\sqrt{9}) + \left(C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \right) \right)$
- 13195 := $\left(-\left(C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \times (-1 - T((T(3) + 1))) \right)$
- 13298 := $\left(\left(T(T(8)) \times C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(2)) \right) - (T(T(3)) + 1) \right)$
- 13299 := $\left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9}) \times T((-2) + T(3)) \right) - 1 \right)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13348 &:= \left(\left(T(T(8)) \times C(T(T(\sqrt{4})), 3) \right) + T((T(3) + 1)) \right) \\
 13434 &:= \left((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + \left(T(\sqrt{4})^{T(C(3,1))} \right) \right) \\
 13449 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(4))) - T(C(3,1)) \right) \\
 13542 &:= \left((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times \sqrt{4}) \times T(5) - C(3,1) \right) \\
 13548 &:= \left((T(T(8) + T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times T(5) + C(3,1) \right) \\
 13564 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times ((C(T(6), 5) / 3) - 1) \right) \\
 13566 &:= \left(C(T(6), 6) / \sqrt{5 \times 3 + 1} \right) \\
 13569 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - (C(T(6), T(5)) / (- (3 + 1))) \right) \\
 13588 &:= \left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 8) / T(5) \right) + (T(T(3)) + 1) \right) \\
 13748 &:= \left((T(T(8)) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - (7 + T(T(T(C(3,1)))) \right) \\
 13799 &:= \left((T(\sqrt{9}) \times C(-((\sqrt{9} - T(7))), 3)) - 1 \right) \\
 13854 &:= \left((T(T(T(4))) \times (T(5) - \sqrt{T(8)})) - T(C(3,1)) \right) \\
 13881 &:= \left(\left((1 + T(T(8))) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(C(3,1))) \right) \\
 13944 &:= \left(\sqrt{4 \times 4} \times T((C(9,3) - 1)) \right) \\
 13965 &:= \left((T((T(5) + T(6))) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - T(T(C(3,1))) \right) \\
 13979 &:= \left((T(C(9,7)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - (T(3) + 1) \right) \\
 13984 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{4}) + (T(T(8)) \times T(C((9 - 3), 1))) \right) \\
 13997 &:= \left((7 + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9)) / T(T(C(3,1))) \right) \\
 13998 &:= \left((T(T(8)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + C((9 + 3), 1) \right) \\
 14076 &:= \left(6 \times T\left(\left(70 - \sqrt{C(4,1)}\right)\right) \right) \\
 14085 &:= \left((5\sqrt{T(8)}) - T(T(T(C(04,1)))) \right) \\
 14161 &:= \left((-1) + T(T((6 - 1))) \sqrt{C(4,1)} \right) \\
 14258 &:= \left((T((-8) + C(T(5), 2))) \times T(\sqrt{4}) - 1 \right) \\
 14343 &:= \left(- (T(T(3))) \times \left(- (T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) + T(C(4,1)) \right) \\
 14344 &:= - \left((T(T(4)) - \left((C(T(4), 3)^{\sqrt{4}} - 1 \right)) \right) \\
 14345 &:= \left((T(T(5))^{\sqrt{4}}) - T((T(3) + C(4,1))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14388 &:= \left(\left(8 + T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3 \right) \right) \right) \times T((T(4) + 1)) \right) \\
 14421 &:= \left(T((1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times (\sqrt{4} + T(T(C(4,1)))) \right) \\
 14465 &:= \left((-T(5) + C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4}))) \times (T(4) + 1) \right) \\
 14476 &:= \left((T(6) - 7) \times (T(C(T(4), \sqrt{4})) - 1) \right) \\
 14499 &:= \left(\left((T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) + T(T(4))) \times 4 \right) - 1 \right) \\
 14526 &:= \left((T(6) \times T(T(2))) + \left(T(T(5))^{\sqrt{C(4,1)}} \right) \right) \\
 14547 &:= \left((7 \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + \left(T(T(5))^{\sqrt{C(4,1)}} \right) \right) \\
 14618 &:= \left((T(8) \times T(T((1+6)))) + \sqrt{C(4,1)} \right) \\
 14629 &:= \left(((9+2) \times C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4}))) - 1 \right) \\
 14679 &:= \left((9 \times 7) \times \left(T(T(6)) + \sqrt{C(4,1)} \right) \right) \\
 14688 &:= \left(T(8) \times \left(T(C(8,6)) + \sqrt{C(4,1)} \right) \right) \\
 14696 &:= \left((C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) + 6) \times (T(4) + 1) \right) \\
 14786 &:= \left((T(T(6)) \times (T(8) + T(7))) + \sqrt{C(4,1)} \right) \\
 14798 &:= \left((T(T(8)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + \left(T(T(7)) \times \sqrt{C(4,1)} \right) \right) \\
 14818 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times T((1+T(8))) \right) + T(T(C(4,1))) \right) \\
 14847 &:= \left((C(7, \sqrt{4}) \times T(T(8))) + (T(41)) \right) \\
 14884 &:= \left(\left(-(4) + \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{C(4,1)}} \right) \\
 14887 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(7)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(8) \right) + T(T(C(4,1))) \right) \\
 14892 &:= \left(T(T(2)) \times \left((\sqrt{9} - T(C(8,4))) \times (-1) \right) \right) \\
 14893 &:= - \left(\left(T(3) \times (\sqrt{9} - T(C(8,4))) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 14894 &:= \left(-(T(4)) + \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times (T(C(8,4)) - 1) \right) \right) \\
 14897 &:= \left(-(7) + \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times (T(C(8,4)) - 1) \right) \right) \\
 14898 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times \left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - T(C(8,4))) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 14945 &:= \left((T(5) \times (T(4)^{\sqrt{9}})) - T(T(C(4,1))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14951 &:= \left(C \left(\sqrt{1 + T(5) \times T(9)}, 4 \right) + 1 \right) \\ 14953 &:= - \left(\left((T(T(3)) - C(T(5), 9)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - 1 \right) \\ 14956 &:= \left(6 + C \left(\left(5 + T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right), C(4, 1) \right) \right) \\ 14957 &:= \left(7 + C \left(\left(5 + T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right), C(4, 1) \right) \right) \\ 14959 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times C(T(5), 9)) - T(T(4)) \right) - 1 \right) \\ 14965 &:= \left(5 \times \left(T \left(\left(T(T(6)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T(C(4, 1)) \right) \right) \\ 14988 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(9))) \right) / \sqrt{C(4, 1)} \right) \right) \\ 14993 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) \right) / (-T(T(4))) \right) - 1 \right) \\ 15251 &:= T \left(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} \right) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + C(5, 1) \\ 15273 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) - C \left(\sqrt{T(T(7)) - T(T(2))}, 5 \right) \right) \times (-1) \right) \\ 15324 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right)^{T(T(2))} \times T(T(3)) \right) + T(C(5, 1)) \right) \\ 15385 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(5)) - \left(C \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3 \right), 5 \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\ 15386 &:= \left(\left(- (T(T(6))) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 3 \right) \right) \times (T(5) - 1) \right) \\ 15432 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(2)) \right)^{T(3)} / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - T(T(C(5, 1))) \right) \\ 15468 &:= \left(- (T(8)) - \left(C \left(C \left(6, T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 5 \right) \times (-1) \right) \right) \\ 15483 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) - C \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 5 \right) \right) \times (-1) \right) \\ 15497 &:= \left(- (7) + C \left(C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4}) \right), C(5, 1) \right) \right) \\ 15502 &:= \left(C(20, 5) - \sqrt{5 - 1} \right) \\ 15524 &:= \left(\left(T(C(T(4), 2)) \times T(\sqrt{5 \times 5}) \right) - 1 \right) \\ 15542 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right)^5 - C(5, 1) \right) \right) \\ 15582 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right)^5 + T(C(5, 1)) \right) \right) \\ 15624 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(2) \right)^{C(6, 5)} \right) - 1 \right) \\ 15648 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T(8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) - T(T(C(5, 1))) \right) \\ 15734 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(\sqrt{-T(3) + T(T(7))}, 5 \right) - 1 \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15888 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T((T(8) + T(8))) \right) + T(T(C(5,1))) \right) \\ 15936 &:= \left(6 \times \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}) + T(51) \right) \right) \\ 15945 &:= \left(\left(T\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right) + T(T(9)) \right) \times T(C(5,1)) \right) \\ 16192 &:= \left(\left(2^{T(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times T((1 + T(C(6,1)))) \right) \\ 16254 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(5) \right) \times T(2 \times T(C(6,1))) \right) \\ 16445 &:= \left(T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) \times (T(4 \times 6) - 1) \right) \\ 16449 &:= \left(\left(9 \times T\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(4)\right) \right) - T(C(6,1)) \right) \\ 16474 &:= \left(T(4) + \left(T(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \times T(C(6,1)) \right) \right) \\ 16494 &:= \left(\left(T(T(4)) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times 4\right) \right) - C(6,1) \right) \\ 16548 &:= \left(\left(T(T(8)) + \sqrt{4} \right) + T(T(5)) \right) \times T(C(6,1)) \\ 16574 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} - 7^5 \right) \right) - T(T(C(6,1))) \\ 16579 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7^5 \right) - T(T(C(6,1))) \right) \\ 16597 &:= \left(\left(C(7, T(\sqrt{9}))^5 \right) - T((T(6) - 1)) \right) \\ 16646 &:= \left(\left(C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) + T(6) \right) \times T(T((6 + 1))) \right) \\ 16758 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - T(T(5)) \right) \times (-7) \times T(C(6,1)) \right) \\ 16796 &:= \left(C(T(6), (\sqrt{9} + 7)) / T(C(6,1)) \right) \\ 16894 &:= \left(T(4) - \left(\left(-T(T(9)) + T\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)})\right) \right) \times T(C(6,1)) \right) \right) \\ 16934 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) / T(T(\sqrt{9})) - C(6,1) \right) \\ 16999 &:= - \left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9}) - 9 \times T(61) \right) \right) \\ 17396 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T(C(6, \sqrt{9})) / 3\right) \right) \times 7 \right) + 1 \\ 17422 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - T(T((7 + 1))) \right) \\ 17458 &:= \left(\left(T(8) + 5 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(T(C(7,1))) \\ 17549 &:= \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{T(\sqrt{4})}\right), (-5) + T(7)\right) - 1 \right) \\ 17642 &:= 2 + T\left(\sqrt{T(T(T(4)) - 6)}\right) \times T(C(7,1)) \\ 17654 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T(T(5)) \times (-T(6)) \right) \times C(7,1) \right) \\ 17668 &:= \left(C(8,6) \times \left(T\left(\sqrt{T(T(6) + T(7))}\right) + 1 \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17898 &:= \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8) \times 9}, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T((7+1))) \right) \\
 17924 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left((-2) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right)^{C(7,1)} \right) \\
 17947 &:= \left(\left(C(T(7), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) / T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) + C(7,1) \right) \\
 17948 &:= \left(\left((T(T(8)) - 4) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times T(C(7,1)) \right) \\
 17949 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 4) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (7-1) \right) \\
 17952 &:= \left(T(2^5) \times (T(\sqrt{9}) + T(C(7,1))) \right) \\
 17967 &:= \left(\left(C(T(7), 6) / T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) + (T(7) - 1) \right) \\
 17983 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(3)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(C(9,7)) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 17989 &:= \left(\left((-\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(8)) \right) \times (-9) + C(7,1) \right) \\
 17995 &:= \left(5 \times (T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) + (T(7) + 1)) \right) \\
 18088 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / \sqrt{08+1} \right) \\
 18332 &:= \left(\left(C((T(2) \times T(3)), T(3)) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 18334 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3)), T(3) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 18389 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + (-C(8, T(3))) \times (T(T(8)) - 1) \right) \right) \\
 18444 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times C((4+8), 1) \right) \\
 18448 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times T(4) \right) - 4 \right) \times C(8,1) \right) \\
 18458 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 5 \right) - T \left(\left(T(T(4)) + T(\sqrt{8+1}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 18488 &:= \left(\left(T((8+8))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - C(8,1) \right) \\
 18528 &:= \left(- (T(8)) + C \left((T(2) + T(5)), T(\sqrt{8+1}) \right) \right) \\
 18534 &:= \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (T(T((-3) + T(5))) + C(8,1)) \right) \\
 18543 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) - C \left((T(\sqrt{4}) + T(5)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times (-1) \right) \\
 18544 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - \left(C \left((T(\sqrt{4}) + T(5)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 18564 &:= \left(C((-4) + T(6), 5) \times \sqrt{8+1} \right) \\
 18565 &:= \left(C \left(((T(5) \times (-6)) / (-5)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 1 \right) \\
 18645 &:= \left(C \left((T(5) + T(\sqrt{4})), 6 \right) + (81) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18745 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{4} \right), 7 \right) - T \left(\left(T(8) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\ 18874 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(T(7) \times \left(- (8) - T \left(T \left(C(8,1) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 18878 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} - \left(T(7) \times \left(- (8) - T \left(T \left(C(8,1) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 18927 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(7 \times T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(C(8,1) \right) \right) \\ 18959 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(\left(- (5) + C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\ 18985 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (5) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \times C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\ 18996 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(6) - \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(C(8,1) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19227 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right), T \left(T(2) \right) \right) / (-7) \right) \right) \\ 19257 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(T \left(T(5) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19278 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times \left(- \left(T(7) \right) + T \left(\left(- (2) + T \left(C(9,1) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19285 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), 8 \right) \times T(2) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\ 19285 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(C \left(9, T(2) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19288 &:= \left(8 \times \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(2) \right) + T \left(\left(T(9) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19292 &:= \left(\left(2 + T \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), T(2) \right) \right) \right) \times 91 \right) \\ 19293 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T \left(T(3) \right) + T \left(T(9) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right), \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\ 19314 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\left(T(4) - 1 \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19319 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(C \left(9, 3 \right) \times \left(1 - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19349 &:= \left(\left(C \left(9, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T(3) \right) \right) \right) - T \left((9+1) \right) \right) \\ 19359 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 5 \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\ 19373 &:= \left(\left(- (1) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), 7 \right) / T(3) \right) \right) \\ 19373 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), 7 \right) / T(3) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\ 19376 &:= \left(\left(- (1) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), 7 \right) / 6 \right) \right) \\ 19376 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(6), 7 \right) / T(3) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) - 1 \right) \\ 19378 &:= \left(\left(1 - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), 7 \right) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\ 19379 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(- \left(C \left(T \left((9-3) \right), 7 \right) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19379 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), 7 \right) - T(3) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \\ 19383 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + C \left((9+3), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \\ 19384 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(- (1) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(3) \right) + 8 \right) / \sqrt{4} \\ 19389 &:= \left(\left(C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\ 19399 &:= \left(\left(1 - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(T(T(T(3))) \times C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\ 19399 &:= \left(\left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) - \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - 1 \right) \right) \\ 19403 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(C \left(9, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(T(T(03))) \right) \right) \\ 19404 &:= \left(\left(4 \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{04} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19427 &:= \left(\left(- (1) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(- (4) + T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), 7 \right) \right) \\ 19442 &:= \left(C \left(\left(19 - \sqrt{4} \right), T(4) \right) - T(T(2)) \right) \\ 19442 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - 4 \right), T(4) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \\ 19443 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) - 4 \right), T(4) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\ 19444 &:= \left(C \left(\left(19 - \sqrt{4} \right), T(4) \right) - (4) \right) \\ 19445 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{4} \right), T(4) \right) - \sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \\ 19446 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T(6) - (4) \right), T(4) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \\ 19447 &:= \left(C \left(\left(7 + T(4) \right), \sqrt{49} \right) - 1 \right) \\ 19448 &:= C \left(\left(\left(T(8) - \sqrt{4} \right) / \sqrt{4} \right), (9+1) \right) \\ 19448 &:= C \left(\left(19 - \sqrt{4} \right), \left(\sqrt{4} + 8 \right) \right) \\ 19449 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 4 \right), \sqrt{49} \right) + 1 \right) \\ 19452 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(2 + T(5) \right), T(4) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \\ 19454 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(5) \right), T(4) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \\ 19457 &:= \left((1 \times 9) + C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(5) \right), 7 \right) \right) \\ 19469 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(C \left(\left(T(6) - (4) \right), (9+1) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19477 &:= \left(1 + \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 4 \right), 7 \right) + \left(T(7) \right) \right) \right) \\ 19484 &:= \left(C \left(\left(- (4) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), T(4) \right) + T \left((9-1) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19485 &:= \left(T(5) \times \left(\left(T(8)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + \sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \\
 19497 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times \left(T(9) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + C(9,1) \right) \\
 19544 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(5) - T \left(T \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 19544 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\left(1 + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(T(5) \times C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 19546 &:= \left(T(T(6)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) - \left(T(T(9)) - 1 \right) \right) \\
 19558 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C(T(5), 5) \right) + T(T((9+1))) \right) \\
 19558 &:= \left(T(T((1+9))) - \left(- \left(C(T(5), 5) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 19569 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{1 \times 9} \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) - \left(T((-6) + T(9)) \right) \\
 19578 &:= \left(\left((8 \times T(T(7))) + T(5) \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \\
 19593 &:= \left(\left(3^9 \right) - \left(T(5) \times T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 19598 &:= \left(- (1) + T(T(9)) \right) + C \left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{9} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 19645 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) + T((T(9) + 1)) \\
 19647 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times 6 - C(9,1) \right) \\
 19658 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), 5 \right) - 691 \\
 19689 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{9}) + \left(T((8-6))^{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \\
 19692 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(2)^9 \right) + (6) \right) + \sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \\
 19745 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 19752 &:= \left(T(T(2)) \times \left(T(5) + \left(C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 19753 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), 5 \right) - T \left(\left(T(7) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 19754 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) - T \left(\left(C(7, \sqrt{9}) - 1 \right) \right) \\
 19778 &:= \left(\left(T(T(8)) - T(7) \right) \times \left(T(7) + \sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \\
 19783 &:= \left(\left(T(3) \times \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 19787 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right), 7 \right) / \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 19787 &:= \left(T(T(7)) - \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), 7 \right) / \left(-T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - 1 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19788 &:= \left(\left(- (T(T(8))) - T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) + \left(C\left(T(7), (\sqrt{9} + 1)\right) \right) \right) \\ 19836 &:= \left((6 + T(3)) \times T\left(C\left(8, \sqrt{9}\right) + 1\right) \right) \\ 19838 &:= \left(\left(T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right)\right) + 8 \right) \times 91 \right) \\ 19839 &:= \left(\left((T(9) \times T(T(3))) \times T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) - T\left(\sqrt{C(9,1)}\right) \right) \\ 19845 &:= \left(\left(- \left((T(5))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + T(T(8)) \right) \times T(C(9,1)) \right) \\ 19848 &:= \left(\left((-1) - \sqrt{9} \right) + T(C(8,4)) \right) \times 8 \\ 19848 &:= \left(8 \times \left(- (4) + T\left(C\left(8, (\sqrt{9} + 1)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\ 19857 &:= \left(\left(T((T(7) + T(5))) \times T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) - C(9,1) \right) \\ 19872 &:= \left(T\left(\sqrt{1 \times 9}\right) \times (T(8) + C(T(7), T(2))) \right) \\ 19874 &:= \left((T((T(4) \times 7)) \times 8) - T\left(\sqrt{C(9,1)}\right) \right) \\ 19892 &:= \left(\left((T(2)^9) + T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) - 1 \right) \\ 19893 &:= \left((3^9) + T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{C(9,1)}\right)\right) \right) \\ 19947 &:= \left(- ((T(T(7)) - 4) + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), (T(\sqrt{9}) - 1)\right)) \right) \\ 19971 &:= \left(- (T((-1) + T(7))) + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), (T(\sqrt{9}) - 1)\right) \right) \\ 19975 &:= \left((-1) + \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(C(9,7)) \right) \right) \times 5 \\ 19978 &:= \left((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) - \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times (-1) \right) \right) \\ 19978 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{1 \times 9})\right), \sqrt{9}\right) + (T(7) \times T(T(8))) \right) \\ 19979 &:= \left(\left(T(C(9,7)) \times \left(9 + T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\ 19983 &:= \left(T((3 \times 8)) + \left(\sqrt{9}^{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \\ 19998 &:= \left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T\left((T(9) - \sqrt{9})\right) \right) + T(T(C(9,1))) \right) \\ 20294 &:= \left(- (T(T(4))) + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), (2 + T(02))\right) \right) \\ 20328 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), (2 + 3)\right) - T(T(T(02))) \right) \\ 20343 &:= \left(C\left(T(T(3)), (\sqrt{4} + 3)\right) - T(T(02)) \right) \\ 20346 &:= \left(C\left(T(6), (\sqrt{4} + 3)\right) - T(02) \right) \\ 20349 &:= C\left(T\left(\sqrt{9 \times 4}\right), (3 + 02)\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20354 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) + (3 + 02) \\ 20358 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), 5 \right) + (3^{02}) \\ 20359 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) + (30/T(2)) \\ 20454 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5) \right) \right) \right), 4 \right) - T(T(T(02))) \\ 20459 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) + (T(T(4)) \times 02) \\ 20469 &:= \left(\left(T(T(9)) \times C \left(6, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T(T(T(T(02)))) \right) \\ 20478 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + ((C(T(7), 4) - T(02))) \right) \\ 20479 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + ((C(T(7), 4) - 02)) \right) \\ 20496 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\left(T(6) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), 4 \right) + T(T(T(02))) \\ 20559 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) + T((T(T(5)) / T(T(02)))) \\ 20654 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) - (- (T(60)) / T(T(2))) \\ 20758 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), 5 \right) + (T(T(7)) + T(02)) \\ 21189 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times T(T((1+1))) \right) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) \\ 21398 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(C(9,3)) \right) - 1 \right) - T(T(T(2))) \right) \\ 21399 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times T(C(9,3)) \right) - T(T((1+2))) \right) \\ 21414 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times (- (1) + T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2)))) \right) \\ 21437 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(7,3)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) - 1 \right) / 2 \right) \\ 21438 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (3 + T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2)))) \right) \\ 21496 &:= C \left(T(6), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \sqrt{4^{T(-1+T(T(2)))}} \\ 21497 &:= \left(\left(T(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - C(T((4+1), T(2))) \right) \\ 21498 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T \left(C \left(9, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + (T(12)) \right) \\ 21645 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(5) + T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), 6 \right) + T(T(12)) \\ 21749 &:= \left(\left(T(T(9)) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + (C(7,1) \times 2) \right) \\ 21897 &:= \left(\left(T(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - T((C(8,1) + 2)) \right) \\ 21944 &:= \left((T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4)))) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), (- (1) + T(T(2))) \right) \\ 21945 &:= \left(\left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) + T(T(9)) \right) \times T(T((1+2))) \right) \end{aligned}$$

- 21948 := $\left(\left(\left(C(8, \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 1 \right) - T(2) \right)$
- 21997 := $\left((T(7))^{\sqrt{9}} + C((9+1), 2) \right)$
- 22429 := $\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), (T(2) + \sqrt{4})) + T(2^{T(T(2))}) \right)$
- 22433 := $\left((C((3 + T(T(3))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + 2) / T(T(2)) \right)$
- 22558 := $\left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 5) + T(T((5 + T(T(2)))) \right) - 2 \right)$
- 22589 := $\left((C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 8) / (T(5) - T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(2))) \right)$
- 22738 := $\left((C(8, 3) \times T(T(7))) + \sqrt{2+2} \right)$
- 22748 := $\left(\left((C(8, \sqrt{4}) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(2)) \right) \times 2 \right)$
- 22824 := $\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times \left(C(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)}) - (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) \right) \right)$
- 22925 := $\left(- (C(T(5), T(T(2)))) + (C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(2)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \right)$
- 22939 := $\left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(2))) / T(2)) \right)$
- 22977 := $\left((7 \times C(T(7), \sqrt{9})) + T((T(2)^2)) \right)$
- 22988 := $\left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 8) / 9 \right) + (T((T(2)^{T(2)})) \right)$
- 22989 := $\left(T(T(9)) + \left((C(8, T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(2)} + 2 \right) \right)$
- 23279 := $\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - (T(7)^{T(2)})) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(2)) \right)$
- 23343 := $\left(C(T(3), \sqrt{4}) - \left((T(3)^{T(3)}) / (-2) \right) \right)$
- 23548 := $\left(T(C(8, \sqrt{4})) \times (T(C(5, 3)) + T(2)) \right)$
- 23834 := $\left(- \left((4^{T(3)}) \right) + \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times C(T(T(3)), T(2)) \right) \right)$
- 23848 := $\left(\left((T(T(8)) - T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(8) \right) - C(T(3), T(2)) \right)$
- 23884 := $\left(\left((\sqrt{4} - T(T(8))) \times (-T(8)) \right) - C(T(3), T(2)) \right)$
- 23895 := $\left(- (5) \times \left((\sqrt{9} - T(C(8, 3))) \times T(2) \right) \right)$
- 23919 := $\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times \left(- (1) + C(C(T(\sqrt{9}), 3), T(2)) \right) \right)$
- 23934 := $\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times \left((C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}) \times T(3) - 2 \right) \right)$
- 23935 := $\left(- (5) - \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}) \times (- (T(3) \times T(2))) \right) \right)$
- 23942 := $\left((C((2 \times T(4)), \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3))) + 2 \right)$
- 23943 := $\left((C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})) \times (\sqrt{9} \times T(3))) + T(2) \right)$

$$\begin{aligned} 23946 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4})) \times 9 \right) + 3 \right) \times 2 \\ 23961 &:= \left(\left(C(16, T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(3)) \right) \times T(2) \right) \\ 23964 &:= \left(\left(4 - \left(C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) \times (-3) \right) \right) \times T(T(2)) \right) \\ 23993 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}) + \left(T(\sqrt{9})^{T(3)} \right) \right) / 2 \right) \\ 23995 &:= \left(-5 - \left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9})^3 \right) \times (-T(2)) \right) \right) \\ 24256 &:= \left((T(T(6)) \times C(T(5), 2)) + C(\sqrt{4}, 2) \right) \\ 24269 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - (C(6, T(2)) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))) \right) \right) \\ 24454 &:= \left(\left(T(T(4)) \times \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) - T(4) \right) \right) - T(T(T(2))) \right) \\ 24485 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(C(8, 4)^{\sqrt{4}} - T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\ 24529 &:= \left(- \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + T(T((T(4) + T(2)))) \right) \\ 24534 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times (T(3) \times (C(T(5), 4) - 2)) \right) \\ 24555 &:= \left(- (T(5)) - \left(T \left(- \left((T(5) - C(T(5), \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \times (-T(T(2))) \right) \right) \\ 24556 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), 5) + T \left(T \left((T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + T(T(T(2))) \right) \\ 24564 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (6 \times C(T(5), 4)) \right) \times T(2) \right) \right) \\ 24569 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T((6 \times T(5))) \right) - C(\sqrt{4}, 2) \right) \\ 24594 &:= \left(\left(4 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times C(T(5), 4) \right) \right) \times T(T(2)) \right) \\ 24698 &:= \left(\left(C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times \left(T(6)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\ 24827 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) + C \left(T(T(2)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) \right) \\ 24839 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times (3 \times 8)) - C(\sqrt{4}, 2) \right) \\ 24841 &:= \left(1 - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times (-8) \right) \times T(C(T(4), 2)) \right) \right) \\ 24847 &:= \left(\left((7 + T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(C(8, 4)) \right) - T(2) \right) \\ 24849 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - ((T(4) \times T(C(8, 4))) + 2) \right) \right) \\ 24854 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times ((5 \times T(C(8, 4))) + 2) \right) \\ 24871 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T((1 \times 7)) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) / T(2) \right) \\ 24948 &:= \left(\left(T(8) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T \left(C \left((9 - \sqrt{4}), 2 \right) \right) \right) \\ 24959 &:= \left(\left(- (T(9)) + \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(4)) \right) \right) - T(T(T(2))) \right) \\ 24969 &:= \left(\left(T(C(9, 6)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times (4 + T(2)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24983 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(C((8+9), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 24989 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(C(9, \sqrt{T(8)})) \right) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) / T(2) \\
 24991 &:= \left(1 - \left(T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \times (-4 - T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 24992 &:= \left(2 - \left(T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \times (-4 - T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 24993 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \right) / T(\sqrt{4}) + T(2) \right) \\
 24995 &:= \left(\left(C(T(5), 9) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times (\sqrt{4} + T(2)) \right) \\
 24996 &:= \left(\left(-C(6, \sqrt{9}) + T(T((9+4))) \right) \times T(T(2)) \right) \\
 24997 &:= \left(\left(7 \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \right) + (4 + T(2)) \right) \\
 24998 &:= \left(8 - \left(T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \times (-4 - T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 24999 &:= \left(9 - \left(T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \times (-4 - T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 25019 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) - (T(10) \times C(T(5), T(2))) \right) \right) \\
 25258 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) - ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) \times (-5)) - 2) \right) \\
 25259 &:= \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) \times (-5)) - T(2)) \right) \\
 25349 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + (T(T(4)) \times (-T(3) + C(T(5), T(2)))) \right) \right) \\
 25395 &:= \left(-T(5) + \left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 3) - T(T(5)) \right) \times T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \\
 25434 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(4), T(3)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - T(T(2)) \right) \\
 25443 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) + T(2) \right) \\
 25465 &:= \left(\left(T((5 \times 6)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(C(5, 2)) \right) \\
 25473 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) \times T(T(7)) \right) \times T(\sqrt{4}) - C(T(5), 2) \right) \\
 25475 &:= \left(-5 + \left(\left(T(7) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times C(T(5), T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 25498 &:= \left(\left(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9}) \times T((T(4) \times 5)) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 25515 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{5-1})^5 \right) \times C(T(5), 2) \right) \\
 25586 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times \left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) - T(T(5)) \right) \right) - T(C(5, 2)) \right) \\
 25642 &:= \left(C(2, \sqrt{4}) + ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \right) \\
 25685 &:= \left(\left(\left(5 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \right) \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \times T(C(5, 2)) \\
 25694 &:= - \left(\left(T(4) - \left(C((\sqrt{9} \times 6), 5) \times T(2) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25696 &:= \left(- \left(C \left(\left(T(6) + \sqrt{9} \right), T(6) \right) \right) + \left(T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) \right) \\ 25697 &:= \left(- (7) + \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right), 5 \right) \times T(2) \right) \right) \\ 25841 &:= \left(1 + \left(T(4) \times \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) / T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \right) \\ 25846 &:= \left(6 + \left(T(4) \times \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) / T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \right) \\ 25934 &:= \left(- \left(4^{T(3)} \right) + \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times C(T(5), T(T(2))) \right) \right) \\ 25949 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) - \left(T(T(T(4))) \right) \right) \times \left(-T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) - T(T(C(5,2))) \\ 26159 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \times \left(T(T(5)) - 1 \right) - \left(C(T(6), T(2)) \right) \right) \\ 26297 &:= \left(- (T(7)) - \left(- (9) \times C \left(\sqrt{T(2)^6}, T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\ 26369 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) + \left(- (C(6,3)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \right) \right) \\ 26384 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) + \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + \left(T(T(3)) \times \left(-C(T(6), T(2)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 26443 &:= \left(\left(- (T((-3) + T(T(4)))) + C \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6 \right) \right) / 2 \right) \\ 26446 &:= \left(\left(6 \times T \left(T \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(4) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C(T(6), T(2)) \right) \right) \\ 26448 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times \left(\left(C(T(4), 4) \times T(6) \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\ 26466 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), 6) / \sqrt{4} \right) - T \left((6^2) \right) \right) \\ 26599 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - 6 \right) / T(T(2)) \right) \\ 26832 &:= \left(C \left(\left(- (2) + T(T(3)) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T \left((T(6) + T(2)) \right) \right) \\ 26845 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times \left((T(8) + T(6)) + 2 \right) \right) \\ 26849 &:= - \left(\left(T((-9) + T(T(4))) - \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \right) \right) \right) \\ 26859 &:= \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times \left(- \left((T(5) + T(8)) - C(T(6), T(2)) \right) \right) \right) \\ 26897 &:= \left(\left(C(T(7), 9) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left((T(T(6)) / T(2)) \right) \right) \right) \\ 26928 &:= \left((T(8) - T(2)) \times C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right), T(2) \right) \right) \\ 26929 &:= \left(\left(- (T(T((9-2)))) + C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), 6 \right) \right) / 2 \right) \\ 26943 &:= \left(T(T(3)) \times \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(9) \right) - C(T(6), T(2)) \right) \right) \right) \\ 27118 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(T((1+1))) \right) - (T(7)) \right) / 2 \right) \\ 27128 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(T(2)) \right) - (1+7) \right) / 2 \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27129 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + C \left((2 + 17), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27134 &:= \left(C \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right), - \left((1 - 7) \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 27334 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) / 2 \right) \\
 27338 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) / 2 \right) \\
 27459 &:= \left(- \left(9 \right) \times \left(\left(T \left(5 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27483 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(\left(T \left(7 \right) - 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 27485 &:= \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) \times T \left(\left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \times T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(7, T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 27495 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(4 + T \left(C \left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27549 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27582 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 27584 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 8 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27594 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \times C \left(T \left(7 \right), 2 \right) \right) \\
 27595 &:= \left(- \left(\left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27694 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(7 \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 27699 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(9 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - C \left(7, 2 \right) \right) \\
 27896 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) - \left(T \left(7 \right) + T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27899 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) - \left(T \left(7 \right) + T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 27924 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right)^{T \left(2 \right)} \right) \times T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) - C \left(7, 2 \right) \right) \\
 27925 &:= \left(- \left(5 \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \times C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7 \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27926 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(7 - T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 27929 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(7 - T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27969 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, 7 \right) \right) \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 27974 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(- \left(7 \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, 7 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27993 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7 \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 28255 &:= \left(T \left(\left(5 \times 5 \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \times C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28344 &:= \left(C \left(T(4), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left((T(T(3)) \times 8)^2 \right) \right) \\
 28345 &:= \left((T(5) \times T((T(T(4)) + (T(3)))) - C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2) \right) \right) \\
 28347 &:= \left(\left(T(C(7,4)) \times T \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) \right) - T(2) \right) \\
 28349 &:= T(9) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(T(T(4)) - T(3))} \right) - C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(T(2)) \right) \\
 28369 &:= \left(\left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) + (C(T(6),3))) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 28371 &:= \left(\left(C(T(-((1-7))),3) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times T(T(T(2))) \right) \\
 28394 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) \times C(8,2)) \right) \\
 28398 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) \times C(8,2)) \right) \\
 28442 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) + (8^{T(2)}) \right) \\
 28448 &:= \left((-8) + \left(\sqrt{4}^{T(4)} \right) \right) \times C(8,2) \\
 28454 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) - \left(C(T(5), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 28498 &:= \left(\left((-8) + T(C(9, T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) \times 8 + 2 \\
 28532 &:= \left(\left((T(T(T(2)))^3) + C(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \times 2 \\
 28565 &:= \left(5 + \left(T((T(6) - (5))) \times T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 28596 &:= \left(\left((T(T(6)) - T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(5)) \right) + T(C(8, T(2))) \right) \\
 28645 &:= \left(((T(T(5)) + 4) \times T(T(6))) + C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 28792 &:= \left(((T(T(2)) - T(T(9))) \times (-T(7))) - C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2) \right) \right) \\
 28843 &:= \left(T((3 + T(T(4)))) - \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / (-2) \right) \right) \\
 28954 &:= \left((4^5) + \left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 28959 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(9)) - \left(C(T(5), 9) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 29162 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(T(2))), 9) / T(\sqrt{16}) \right) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \right) \\
 29198 &:= 2^{T(T(\sqrt{9})-1)} - T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 29198 &:= \left((8^{T(\sqrt{9})-1}) - T(C(9, T(2))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29205 &:= \left(T(50) + \left(C\left(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(T(T(2))) \right) \right) \\
 29242 &:= \left(C\left(2, \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(T((2 \times 9))^2\right) \right) \\
 29243 &:= \left(\left(T((2 \times 9))^2\right) + \sqrt{C(4,3)} \right) \\
 29248 &:= \left(\left(C(29, T(2)) + \sqrt{4}\right) \times 8 \right) \\
 29248 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + C(29, T(2))\right) \right) \\
 29262 &:= \left(\left(T((T(2) \times 6))^2\right) + T\left(\sqrt{C(9,2)}\right) \right) \\
 29275 &:= \left(T(5) + \left((T(7) - T(T(2))) \times C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), T(2)\right)\right) \right) \\
 29281 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times C\left(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{9}\right)\right) + T(T(T(2))) \right) \\
 29281 &:= \left(T(T(T(2))) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), T(2)\right) \times \left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) + 1\right)\right) \right) \\
 29337 &:= \left((7 + T((-T(3)) + T(T(3)))) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{C(9,2)}\right)\right) \right) \\
 29343 &:= \left(C\left(\left(T(T(3)) - \sqrt{4}\right), T(3)\right) + T(T((9+2))) \right) \\
 29343 &:= \left(T(T((2+9))) + C\left(\left(T(T(3)) - \sqrt{4}\right), T(3)\right) \right) \\
 29357 &:= \left(((7 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right), T(2)\right) \right) \\
 29357 &:= \left(C\left(T(T(2)), \sqrt{9}\right) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(T(5)) + (7))) \right) \\
 29382 &:= \left(T(T(2)) + \left(\left(T(8) \times C\left(\left(T(3) \times \sqrt{9}\right), T(2)\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 29394 &:= \left(C\left(T(2), \sqrt{9}\right) - (C(T(T(3)), 9) / (-T(4))) \right) \\
 29429 &:= \left((C(T(T(T(2))), 9) / T(4)) + T\left(2^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \right) \\
 29436 &:= \left(((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times \sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) \\
 29438 &:= \left((C(T(T(T(2))), 9) / T(4)) + T\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}\right) \right) \\
 29459 &:= \left((C(T(T(T(2))), 9) / T(4)) + T\left(5 + T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \\
 29464 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left(\left(C\left(T(6), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) - T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 29472 &:= \left(\left(T((2 \times 9))^{\sqrt{4}}\right) + T(C(7,2)) \right) \\
 29474 &:= \left(-T(4) - \left(-\left(C\left(T(7), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times T((9+T(2)))\right) \right) \\
 29475 &:= \left(-T(5) + \left(\left(C\left(T(7), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times 9\right) + T(T(2)) \right) \right) \\
 29477 &:= \left(-7 - \left(-\left(C\left(T(7), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times T((9+T(2)))\right) \right) \\
 29479 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + \left(\left(C\left(T(7), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times 9\right) - 2\right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29482 &:= \left(\left(C \left(28, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 9 \right) - 2 \right) \\
 29491 &:= \left(\left(19 \times T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{C \left(9, 2 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 29554 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-C \left(T \left(5 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29554 &:= \left(C \left(\left(2 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29588 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \times \left(8 + T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 29588 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(- \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) + 8 \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29591 &:= \left(\left(1 + C \left(9, 5 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 29625 &:= \left(\left(5^{T \left(2 \right)} \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) + \sqrt{C \left(9, 2 \right)} \right) \right) \\
 29659 &:= \left(\left(- \left(2 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(6 \right) + T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29673 &:= \left(\left(T \left(2 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(T \left(6 \right) + C \left(T \left(7 \right), 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 29679 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) - \left(- \left(9 \right) \times \left(T \left(6 \right) + C \left(T \left(7 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29698 &:= \left(- \left(2 \right) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) - T \left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29715 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(- \left(9 \right) \times C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(\sqrt{-1+5} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29759 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(- \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), 9 \right) \right) / T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29785 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(5 \right) + T \left(C \left(8, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 29789 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{C \left(9, 8 \right)} + T \left(7 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 2 \right) \right) \\
 29791 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{C \left(9, 1 \right)}} \\
 29794 &:= \left(T \left(2 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(7 \right) \right) \right)^{C \left(\sqrt{9}, \sqrt{4} \right)} \right) \\
 29844 &:= \left(\left(T \left(2 \right) + 9 \right) \times \left(T \left(C \left(8, 4 \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 29895 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), 9 \right) \times \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) - \left(T \left(9 \right) \times T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 29921 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\left(1 + T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), 9 \right) / T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29925 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(2 \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times T \left(C \left(9, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 29934 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4^3} \right) - \left(\left(T \left(9 \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29945 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{5^4} - \left(T \left(9 \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29953 &:= \left(\left(T \left(3 \right) \times C \left(T \left(5 \right), 9 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) / T \left(2 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$29953 := \left(\left(T(T(T(T(2)))) / (-\sqrt{9}) \right) - \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times (-C(T(5), T(3))) \right) \right)$$

$$29958 := \left(\left(T(8) - \left(C(T(5), 9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times (-2) \right)$$

$$29959 := - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + (5 - (T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))) \right) \right)$$

$$29969 := \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) / (-6) \right) + ((T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))) \right)$$

$$29969 := \left(\left(T(T(2^{\sqrt{9}})) \right) \times T(9) - C(6, T(\sqrt{9})) \right)$$

$$29972 := \left(\left(T(T(2) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) + 2 \right)$$

$$29974 := - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + (-7 - (T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))) \right) \right)$$

$$29974 := \left(2 + \left((T(9) \times T(C(9,7))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$29977 := \left(\left(T(T(2) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) + 7 \right)$$

$$29977 := \left(\sqrt{7 \times 7} + (T(9) \times T(C(9,2))) \right)$$

$$29978 := \left(\left(T(T(2) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times T(C(9,7)) + 8 \right)$$

$$29979 := \left((T(C(9,7)) \times T(9)) + \sqrt{9^2} \right)$$

$$29982 := \left(\left(T(T(2)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + ((T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))) \right)$$

$$29991 := \left(T(T(\sqrt{1 \times 9})) + ((T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))) \right)$$

$$29994 := \left((4 \times T(\sqrt{9})) + ((T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))) \right)$$

$$29998 := \left(C(8, T(\sqrt{9})) + ((T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))) \right)$$

$$31749 := \left(\left(C(9, T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \times T((T(7) - 1)) - 3 \right)$$

$$31769 := \left(C(\sqrt{9} \times 6, 7) - T(T((1 + 3))) \right)$$

$$31796 := \left(C((T(6) - \sqrt{9}), 7) - T((1 + T(3))) \right)$$

$$31818 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - (C(18, (1 + T(3)))) \right) \right)$$

$$31822 := \left(-2 + C\left(\left(T(2) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right), (1 + T(3)) \right) \right)$$

$$31824 := C\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + ((2 \times 8)) \right), (1 + T(3)) \right)$$

$$31834 := \left(T(4) + C\left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right), (1 + T(3)) \right) \right)$$

$$31845 := \left(C\left(\left(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right), (8 - 1) \right) + T(T(3)) \right)$$

$$32284 := \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) - C\left(\left(2^{T(2)}, 3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$32295 := \left(\left(T(T(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \times T(T(T(2))) - T((T(2) \times 3)) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32358 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(C(5,3))) \right) + (T(2) \times T(3)) \right) \\
 32359 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T(T(C(5,3))) \right) + (-2 + T(T(3))) \right) \\
 32486 &:= \left(\left(- (T(6)) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \right) + C(T(T(2)), 3) \right) \\
 32488 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times (8 + T(T(T(4)))) \right) - C(T(T(2)), 3) \right) \\
 32645 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(5)) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{C(6,2)} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 32654 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{T(5)} \right) - T(C(6,2)) \right) + T(3) \right) \\
 32659 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 5 \right), T(6) \right) / 2 - T(T(T(3))) \right) \\
 32745 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times C(T(7), T(2)) \right) - 3 \right) \right) \\
 32748 &:= \left(\left(8^{-\sqrt{4}+7} \right) - C(T(T(2)), 3) \right) \\
 32875 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / T \left((2^3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32883 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{3^8} \times T(C(8,2)) \right) - 3 \right) \\
 32884 &:= \left(\left(C \left(- ((T(4) - T(8))), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / 2 - T(3) \right) \right) \\
 32886 &:= \left(\left(T(6) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times (T(C(8,2)) \times 3) \right) \\
 32887 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / T(8) - \sqrt{T(2) \times 3} \right) \right) \\
 32897 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) / T(8) + (T(T(T(2))) / 3) \right) \right) \\
 32924 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(C \left(T(T(2)), \sqrt{9} \right)^{T(2)} + T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32928 &:= \left(\left((C(8,2))^{\sqrt{9}} / 2 \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 32935 &:= \left(C(T(5), T(3)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(2) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 33244 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - ((4 + T(T(T(2)))) \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) \right) \right) \\
 33288 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(C(8, T(2))) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) + 3 \right) \\
 33348 &:= \left(\left(- (8) + T \left(C \left(\sqrt{4^3}, 3 \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \\
 33434 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{C(T(3), \sqrt{4})} \right) + T((T(3) \times T(3))) \right) \\
 33439 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 3 \right) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(3)))) \right) \\
 33483 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) \times T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) - 33 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33514 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(T \left(\left(1 + T \left(C \left(5, 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 33529 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 2 \right), 5 \right) - T \left(\left(- \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 33574 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(7^5 \right) - C \left(T \left(3 \right), 3 \right) \right) \right) \\ 33592 &:= \left(2 \times \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), C \left(5, 3 \right) \right) / T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 33628 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) + 2 \right), \left(6 \times 3 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 33643 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(3 \right) - \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T \left(6 \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) / 3 \right) \right) \right) \\ 33646 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right), \left(6 \times 3 \right) \right) - 3 \right) \\ 33649 &:= C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(- \left(4 \right) + T \left(6 \right) \right) \right), \left(3 \times T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\ 33698 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(\left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) / 3 \right) + \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 33882 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), 8 \right) / \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) - 33 \right) \\ 33884 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right), 8 \right) / T \left(3 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 33887 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right), 8 \right) / \left(3 + 3 \right) \right) \right) \\ 33893 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 8 \right) - T \left(3 \right) \right) / \left(- T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 33894 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9 \right) + T \left(C \left(8, 3 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\ 33895 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 8 \right) \right) / \left(- \left(3 + 3 \right) \right) \right) \\ 33914 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), - \left(\left(1 - 9 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(3 \right) \right) / T \left(3 \right) \right) \\ 33937 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 \times T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(3 \right), 3 \right) \right) \\ 33985 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) - \left(- \left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) / 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 34338 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(\left(3^4 \right) \right) \times T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 34349 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 4 \right) \times T \left(3 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 34374 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(7, 3 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 34455 &:= \left(T \left(5 \right) \times \left(C \left(\sqrt{5^4}, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 3 \right) \right) \\ 34479 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - T \left(C \left(7, 4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\ 34485 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{5^8} + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(T \left(C \left(4, 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 34495 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) / T \left(3 \right) \right) \\ 34497 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\left(- \left(4 \right) + T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34515 &:= \left(T(5) \times \left(1 + C(\sqrt{5^4}, 3) \right) \right) \\ 34528 &:= \left((T(T(8)) - 2) \times \left(T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) - 3 \right) \right) \\ 34544 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} + C(T(4), 5)) \times T((T(4) + T(3))) \right) \\ 34565 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left((T(6) + (5)) \times C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 3) \right) \right) \\ 34664 &:= \left(- \left((4^6) \right) + C(C(6, T(\sqrt{4})), T(3)) \right) \\ 34794 &:= \left((T(T(4)) \times (\sqrt{9} + T(C(7, 4)))) - T(T(3)) \right) \\ 34874 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times 7) \times (T(C(8, 4)) + T(3)) \right) \\ 34938 &:= \left((- (T(8)) + C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9})) \times \left(T(\sqrt{4})^3 \right) \right) \\ 34979 &:= - \left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) - (C(7, \sqrt{9}) \times (T(4)^3))) \right) \\ 35245 &:= \left((T(5) \times T((T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(T(2)))))) + (C(T(5), T(3))) \right) \\ 35385 &:= \left(C\left(\left(T(T(5)) / \sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(3)\right) - (T(5)^3) \right) \\ 35435 &:= \left(T(5) + \left((T(T(3)) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(T(C(5, 3))) \right) \right) \\ 35482 &:= \left((- ((T(2) - T(8))^{T(\sqrt{4})}) - (C(T(5), 3)) \right) \\ 35764 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4})^6 \right) + (7 \times C(T(5), T(3))) \right) \\ 35798 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T((T(9) - T(7))) \right) + (C(T(5), 3)) \right) \\ 35854 &:= - \left(\left(T\left(T\left(-\left(\sqrt{4} - T(5)\right)\right)\right) + (-8) \times C(T(5), T(3)) \right) \right) \\ 35929 &:= \left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 2) \times T((T(\sqrt{9}) + T(C(5, 3)))) \right) \\ 35931 &:= \left(T(T((1 \times 3))) \times T((\sqrt{9} + T(C(5, 3)))) \right) \\ 35934 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + \left(T(T(3)) \times T((\sqrt{9} + T(C(5, 3)))) \right) \right) \\ 35945 &:= \left((T(5) + (4^{\sqrt{9}})) \times C(T(5), 3) \right) \\ 35958 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + (C(T(5), \sqrt{9})) \right) \times T((T(5) - 3)) \right) \\ 35995 &:= \left((5^{T(\sqrt{9})}) + (C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 5) + (T(T(3)))) \right) \\ 36714 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times \sqrt{1 + C(T(7), T(6) - T(3))} \right) \\ 36844 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4}^{T(4)}) \times T(8) \right) - (C(6, 3)) \right) \\ 36897 &:= \left(\left(- (7) - \left(C(9, \sqrt{T(8)}) \times (-T(6)) \right) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36955 &:= \left(- (5) - \left(T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- (T(6) + 3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36964 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(T(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - C(6,3) \right) \right) \\
 37134 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(- (3) \times C(17, T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 37184 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T(T(8)) \right) \times \left(-C((1+7), 3) \right) \right) \\
 37228 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times T(7) - T(3) \right) \right) \\
 37234 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 3 \right) \right), T(2) \right) \times T(7) - T(3) \right) \right) \\
 37241 &:= \left(1 + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(2) \right) \times T(C(7, T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 37244 &:= \left(4 + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(2) \right) \times T(C(7, T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 37245 &:= - \left(\left(T(5) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - T((2 \times C(7,3))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 37282 &:= \left(T(T(T(2))) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(2) \right) \times T(7) + T(T(3)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 37468 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + \left(\left(C \left(T(6), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(7) - 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 37471 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(-((1-7))), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(7) + T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 37639 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 3 \right) + 6 \right) \times T(7) + T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 37822 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T(2) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times T(7) - T(3) \right) \right) \\
 37945 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times C \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - T(7) \right) \right), T(T(3)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38118 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times C(11, 8) \right) + 3 \right) \\
 38172 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-T(7) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(- (1) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), T(3) \right) \right) \\
 38225 &:= \left(T(C(5,2)) \times \left(2 + \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 38248 &:= \left(C \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4}) \right), T(T(2)) \right) - (8^3) \right) \\
 38339 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 3 \right) \times \left(T(T(3)) + 8 \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 38357 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(7)) - \left(C \left(\left(T(T(5)) / T(3) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 38388 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(\left(T(T(3)) \times \left(-T(8) \right) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 38396 &:= \left(- \left(\left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{9} \right) - T(3) \right) \right) \times \left(- (8) - T(T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 38415 &:= \left(\left((T(5) - 1)^4 \right) - C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(3) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38429 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \times T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(3) \right) \right) \\
 38457 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(7) \times C(T(5), 4) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 38458 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T \left(\left(T(5) \times 4 \right) \right) + C(8, T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 38486 &:= \left(\left(T(6) \times T \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(4) \right) \right) \right) + C(8, 3) \right) \\
 38493 &:= \left(T(T(3)) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + T((4 + C(8, 3))) \right) \right) \\
 38499 &:= \left(\left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times T(T(4)) \right) - T(C(8, 3)) \right) \\
 38523 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(\left(T(T(2)) - C \left(\left(T(T(5)) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(3) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38526 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(6)) + T(2) \right) - C \left(\left(T(T(5)) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38549 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(4)) \right) - \left(C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38557 &:= \left(\left(T(7) + C \left(\left(5 + T(5) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) \\
 38559 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(-5 + C(T(5), 8) \right) \right) - T(T(3)) \right) \\
 38579 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(7) \right) - \left(C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38585 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} - \left(C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38586 &:= \left(-6 + \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times \left(C(T(5), 8) - 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 38592 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(C(T(5), 8) - 3 \right) \right) \\
 38594 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - C(T(5), 8) \right) \times T(3) \right) \right) \\
 38595 &:= \left(\left(-5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \right) \right) \\
 38597 &:= \left(\left(-7 - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \right) \right) \\
 38598 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(C(T(5), 8) \times T(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38645 &:= - \left(\left(\left(5^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))} \right) - \left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38648 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{4} \right), 6 \right) - \left(T(8)^3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 38732 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(2))) - \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), 7) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 38742 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - \left(C \left(\left(T(7) - 8 \right), T(3) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38747 &:= \left(\left(-7 - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(\left(T(7) - 8 \right), T(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38749 &:= \left(\left(-9 - \sqrt{4} \right) + C \left(\left(T(7) - 8 \right), T(3) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38753 &:= \left(\left(- (C((T(3) + T(5)), 7)) + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) / (-3) \right) \\
 38754 &:= \left(C\left(4 \times 5, \sqrt{T(7) + 8}\right) - (T(3)) \right) \\
 38756 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{T(6) - 5} - (C((T(7) - 8), T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 38758 &:= \left(\left(C((T(8) - T(5)), 7) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / 3 \right) \\
 38759 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + (-5) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 38774 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7 + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 38781 &:= \left(C\left(-((1 \times 8)) + T(7), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T(T(3)) \right) \\
 38784 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times 8 + (C((T(7) - 8), T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 38785 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{58}} + (C((T(7) - 8), T(3))) \right) \\
 38789 &:= \left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) + (8 + C((T(7) - 8), T(3))) \right) \\
 38796 &:= \left(\left(6 \times T(\sqrt{9}) + (C((T(7) - 8), T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 38798 &:= \left(T(8) + \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 7\right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / 3 \right) \right) \\
 38799 &:= \left(\left(T(9) - T(\sqrt{9}) + (C((T(7) - 8), T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 38802 &:= \left(C\left(20, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + (T(8) + T(3)) \right) \\
 38816 &:= \left(C\left((T(6) - 1), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + C(8, 3) \right) \\
 38828 &:= \left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2)\right) - \left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times (-8) \right) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) \right) \\
 38838 &:= \left(C\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T((T(8) / 3)) \right) \\
 38843 &:= \left(C\left(C\left(T(3), T(\sqrt{4})\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + (83) \right) \\
 38864 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(T(T(6)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times C(8, T(3)) \right) \\
 38931 &:= \left(C\left((-1) + T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + T\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times 3\right)\right) \right) \\
 38955 &:= \left(- (C(T(5), 5)) - \left(\left(- (\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(8)) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \right) \\
 38968 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) + C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3\right) \right) \right) \\
 38976 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), 7) / \sqrt{9} \right) + (T(8) \times T(3)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38991 &:= \left(C \left(\left(- (1) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) / T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38995 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) - 8 \right) \right) + \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 38999 &:= \left(\left(C \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), \sqrt{9} \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 8 \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39144 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times C \left(9, 3 \right) \right) \\
 39172 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(- (1) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39187 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) + \left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right)} - 1 \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39225 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) + C \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) \\
 39248 &:= \left(\left(8 + T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(- (2) + T \left(C \left(9, 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39269 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(T \left(C \left(9, 6 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) / \left(- T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39283 &:= \left(\left(T \left(3 \right) + C \left(8, 2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39284 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T \left(8 \right) \right) \right)^{T \left(2 \right)} \right) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), 3 \right) \right) \\
 39288 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \times \left(C \left(8, T \left(2 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39312 &:= \left(2 \times \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(1 + T \left(3 \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39385 &:= \left(\sqrt{5^8} + C \left(C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39414 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(- (1) + T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39424 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(C \left(4, 2 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4^9} \right) / 3 \right) \\
 39426 &:= \left(C \left(C \left(6, T \left(2 \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39428 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) + 2 \right) + C \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39438 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \times 3 \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39447 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) + T \left(9 \right) \right) \times 3 \\
 39467 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(6 \right) \right) / T \left(4 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) / 3 \right) \\
 39537 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(5 \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39572 &:= \left(\left(2 \times T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 39578 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C \left(T \left(8 \right) - 7, 5 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) / \left(-3 \right) \right) \\
 39583 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) + 8, 5 \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) / 3 \right) \\
 39584 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \times C \left(8, 5 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{T \left(3 \right)} \right) \right) \\
 39585 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 + C \left(8, 5 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39586 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T(6) + 8), 5 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) / 3 \right) \\ 39587 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C \left((-7 + T(8)), 5 \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) / (-3) \right) \\ 39588 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(8 + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), 5 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) + 3 \right) \\ 39592 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C(29, 5) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) / (-3) \right) \\ 39648 &:= \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(T(6) - \left(9^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 39669 &:= \left(\left((9 \times T(6)) \times T \left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T(3) \right) \right) \\ 39684 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times (T(6) \times 9) \right) - (T(3)) \right) \\ 39789 &:= \left((98 \times T(T(7))) + C \left(\sqrt{9}, 3 \right) \right) \\ 39895 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 39903 &:= \left(\left(30 \times C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 3 \right) \\ 39915 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(T(19) \times T \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 39978 &:= \left(T \left(T(8) \right) + \left(C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right) \times (9 + 3) \right) \right) \\ 39985 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - 3 \right) \right) \\ 39997 &:= \left((T(7) + 9) \times T \left(\left(T(9) + C \left(\sqrt{9}, 3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 40245 &:= \left(T(54) + C \left(20, T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 40278 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times \left(C \left(T(7), 2 \right) + T \left(T \left(T(04) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 40294 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(4) \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + C \left(20, T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 40656 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(6), 5 \right) - T(6) \right) \times \sqrt{04} \right) \\ 40754 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) + (T(7)) \right) \times \sqrt{04} \right) \\ 40824 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right)^{T(T(2))} \right) \times C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{04} \right) \right) \right) \\ 40858 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 5 \right) + (80) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\ 41245 &:= \left(T \left((T(5) + T(T(4))) \right) + C \left((T(T(T(2))) - 1), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 41388 &:= \left(T \left((T(8) + T(8)) \right) + C \left((T(T(3)) - 1), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 41559 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(5) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left((5 + 1) \right) \right) \times T \left(T(4) \right) \right) \right) \\ 41875 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(C \left(T(7), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / (-1 + T(4)) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41969 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), 9 \right) / \left(- \left(1 \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 41976 &:= \left(\left(6 + T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(1 + T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 42225 &:= \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right), T \left(2 \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 42229 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(- \left(2 \right) + T \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\ 42245 &:= \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(C \left(\left(2^{T \left(2 \right)} \right), 4 \right) \right) \right) \\ 42256 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) + \left(\left(- \left(5 \right) + T \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\ 42259 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 5 \right) \times 2 \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 42273 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(\left(C \left(7, 2 \right) \times T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\ 42347 &:= \left(\left(C \left(7, 4 \right)^3 \right) - T \left(\sqrt{2^{T \left(4 \right)}} \right) \right) \\ 42414 &:= \left(\left(41 \times T \left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), 2 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 42434 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - \left(4 \right) \right)^2 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\ 42446 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), \sqrt{4} \right) - \left(4 \right) \right)^2 \right) + T \left(4 \right) \right) \\ 42449 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times 4 \right), \left(\sqrt{4} + T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \\ 42464 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - C \left(T \left(6 \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{2^{T \left(4 \right)}} \right) \right) \\ 42468 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(8 \right) - C \left(\left(6 \times 4 \right), \left(T \left(2 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 42478 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} - \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), 4 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-2 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 42492 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(2 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), 4 \right) - T \left(2 \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\ 42494 &:= \left(C \left(\left(4 \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \left(\sqrt{4} + T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(4 \right) \right) \\ 42496 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) - 2 \right) \times 4 \right) \\ 42498 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} - C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times 4 \right), \left(T \left(2 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 42536 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) + 3 \right), 5 \right) + \sqrt{2^{T \left(4 \right)}} \right) \\ 42539 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right), 5 \right) + \sqrt{T \left(-T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right)} \right) \\ 42549 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times 4 \right), 5 \right) + T \left(\left(T \left(2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\ 42559 &:= \left(C \left(\left(9 + T \left(5 \right) \right), \sqrt{5^2} \right) + T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \\ 42587 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) - T \left(T \left(C \left(5, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 42589 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 8 \right) / 5 \right) + T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42666 &:= \left((6^6) + \left(- (C(T(6), T(2))) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 42679 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - (- (T(7)) \times (C(6,2) - T(T(T(4)))) \right) \right) \\
 42693 &:= \left(T(T(3)) \times \left(9 + C\left((T(6) + T(2)), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 42745 &:= - \left(\left((T(T(5)) + T(4)) - \left(C(7, T(2))^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \right) \right) \\
 42752 &:= \left((- (T(2)) - T(T(5))) + \left(C(7, T(2))^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \right) \\
 42755 &:= -T(T(5)) + (5 \times 7)^{C(T(2), \sqrt{4})} \\
 42868 &:= \left(C(8,6) \times \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(2) \right) \right) + T(T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 42877 &:= \left(\left((- (C(7,7)) + T(8))^{T(2)} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 42927 &:= \left(\left((C(7, T(2))^{\sqrt{9}} - T(2)) + T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 42946 &:= \left(C\left(C\left(6, T(\sqrt{4}) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + T(T((T(2) + T(4)))) \right) \\
 42954 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 5 \right) + T((T(9) + 2)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 42959 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), 5 \right) / 9 \right) \times \left(T(T(T(2))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 42981 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(1 + T\left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right)^2 - T(T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 42984 &:= \left((- (4) + T\left(C\left(8, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(T(2)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \\
 42998 &:= \left(\left((8^{\sqrt{9}}) \times C(9, T(2)) \right) - T(4) \right) \\
 43117 &:= \left((T(7) \times T(T(T((C(1,1) + 3)))) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 43228 &:= \left(- (T(8)) + \left((- (2) + T(C(T(T(2)), 3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 43239 &:= \left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times \left(\left(3^{T(T(2))} \right) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43263 &:= \left(T((3 \times 6)) \times C(23, \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 43337 &:= \left(\left(C(7,3)^3 - \left(T(T(T(3))) \times (-\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43344 &:= \left(\left(\left(T\left(C\left(T(4), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 3 \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 43358 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 5 \right) + C(T(T(3)), 3) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 43365 &:= \left(T(5) \times \left(T(T(6)) + \left(C(T(T(3)), 3) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43454 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 5 \right) + (T((T(T(4)) - 3))) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 43463 &:= \left((C(T(T(3)), 6) - T(T(T(4)))) - \left(T(T(3))^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \right) \\
 43482 &:= \left(C\left(\left(T(2) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(4) \right) - T\left(\left(T(T(3)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43484 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(4))) \times \left(-\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - T(T(T(4))) \right) + C \left(T(T(3)), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43529 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - (2 + C((T(5) + 3), T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 43539 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(T(3)) \right), 5 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{3^4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43542 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(2))^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) - C((T(5) + 3), T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 43547 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + T(T(5)) \right) \right) - C(T(T(3)), 4) \right) \\
 43548 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times (-T(4)) \right) + C((T(5) + 3), T(4)) \right) \\
 43599 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + (-9) \times C((T(T(5)) / T(3)), 4) \right) \right) \\
 43639 &:= \left(\left((9 \times T(T(3))) \times T(T(6)) \right) - C \left(T(3), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43645 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(\left(T(C(6,3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43655 &:= - \left(\left(C(T(5), 5) - \left(\left(6^{T(3)} + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43673 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(3)) + T(T(7)) \right) - \left(\left(T(C(6,3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43674 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times (-T(7)) \right) + C((6 \times 3), T(4)) \right) \\
 43694 &:= - \left(\left(\left(4^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - C((6 \times 3), T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 43728 &:= \left(\left((T(8) \times T(2)) \times T(T(7)) \right) - T \left(C \left(T(3), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43778 &:= \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times 7 \right) \right) + \left(C(7,3)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \right) \\
 43779 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + C((T(7) - ((7 + 3))), T(4)) \right) \\
 43813 &:= \left(T(T((3 + 1))) + C \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times 3 \right), T(4) \right) \right) \\
 43814 &:= \left((T(T(4)) + 1) + C \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times 3 \right), T(4) \right) \right) \\
 43822 &:= \left(\left(2^{T(T(2))} \right) + C \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times 3 \right), T(4) \right) \right) \\
 43839 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(3) \right), 8 \right) + \left((3^4) \right) \right) \\
 43842 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(T(2)) \times T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right), 8 \right) + (T(T(3)) \times 4) \right) \\
 43849 &:= \left(C \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right), 8 \right) + T((3 + T(4))) \right) \\
 43862 &:= \left(2 \times \left(- (T(6)) + \left(C(8, T(3))^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43875 &:= \left(T(5) \times C \left(\left(\sqrt{T(7) + 8} + T(T(3)) \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43878 &:= \left(T((8 + 7)) + C \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times 3 \right), T(4) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43891 &:= \left(1 + \left(-\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - T(8)\right)\right) \times C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \\
 43892 &:= \left(2 + \left(-\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - T(8)\right)\right) \times C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \\
 43893 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}\right) \times (T(8) - 3)\right) + T(\sqrt{4})\right) \\
 43894 &:= \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9\right), 8\right) + T((T(3) + T(4)))\right) \\
 43895 &:= \left(5 + \left(-\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - T(8)\right)\right) \times C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \\
 43896 &:= \left(C\left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})\right) - \left(8 \times \left(T(3)^4\right)\right)\right) \\
 43925 &:= \left(C(T(5), T(2)) + \left((T(T(9)) \times T(T(3))) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 43929 &:= \left(T((9 \times 2)) + C\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(3)\right), T(4)\right)\right) \\
 43964 &:= \left(-\left(T((T(4) + (6)))\right) + \left(T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), 3\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \\
 43983 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) - \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - C\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(3)\right), T(4)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 43996 &:= \left(\left(6^{T(\sqrt{9})}\right) - \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), 3\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 44094 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right)^{\sqrt{04}} - T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \\
 44095 &:= \left(-5 + \left(T\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{04})\right)\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \\
 44096 &:= \left(\left(T\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{04}} - 4\right) \\
 44145 &:= \left((T(T(5)) + T(41)) \times C\left(T(4), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 44199 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9}\right) \times T(T((1 + T(4))))\right) - T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \\
 44239 &:= \left(-\left(T((C(9, 3) - 2))\right) \times \left(-\left(T(4) - T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \\
 44243 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - T(T(T(2)))\right) - \left(\left(T(4)^4\right)\right)\right) \\
 44245 &:= \left(5 \times \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(T(T(2)))\right), 4\right) - T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) \\
 44257 &:= \left((T(T(7)) \times (C(T(5), 2) + (4))) + T(\sqrt{4})\right) \\
 44258 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) - \left(\left(T(T(2)) + \left(\left(T(4)^4\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 44265 &:= \left(5 \times \left(C\left((T(6) + 2), 4\right) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 44272 &:= \left((C(-((T(2) - T(7))), T(T(2))) / 4) - T(\sqrt{4})\right) \\
 44279 &:= \left(\left(C\left(-\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - T(7)\right)\right)\right), T(T(2))\right) / 4 + 4\right) \\
 44285 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{58}}, T(T(2))\right) / 4\right) + T(4)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44299 &:= \left(T(T(9)) + \left(\left(T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(2))) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 44329 &:= \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + \left(-2 + \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 44331 &:= \left(T(T(T((1 \times 3))) + \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 44333 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(\left(T(C(T(3), 3))^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 44334 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(3))) \right) + \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 44343 &:= \left(\sqrt{3^{T(4)}} + \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 44358 &:= \left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 5) + T(T(T(3) \times T(4))) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 44424 &:= \left(C(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(2)), T(4)) + T(T((4+4))) \right) \\
 44425 &:= \left(T(5^2) + \left(C(T(4), 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 44428 &:= \left(T(T(8)) + \left(C(T(T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4}), T(4)) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 44429 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - \left(C(T(T(T(2))), 4) - T(T(T(4))) \right) \times T(4) \right) \right) \\
 44478 &:= \left(\left(T(8) \times T(T(7)) + C(T(4), 4) \right) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 44496 &:= \left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \times \left(C(T(4), 4) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 44497 &:= \left(T(T(7)) - \left(9 - \left(C(T(4), 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 44498 &:= \left(\left(C(8, T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) + T(T(T(4)) - T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 44521 &:= \left((1 + C(2 \times 5), 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 44538 &:= \left(T(T(8) + 3) + C(T(5) + T(\sqrt{4}), T(4)) \right) \\
 44584 &:= \left(C(T(\sqrt{4}) \times 8, 5) + T(4^{T(\sqrt{4})}) \right) \\
 44632 &:= \left((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) - C(6 \times 4, T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 44649 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{T(4)} \right) - \left(T(C(6, 4))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 44681 &:= \left(\left((1 + C(8, 6)) \times T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) \\
 44689 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 8 \right) \times \left(C(6, T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 44698 &:= \left(\left(T(C(8, \sqrt{9})) \times T(T(6) / T(\sqrt{4})) \right) + T(4) \right) \\
 44751 &:= \left(\left((1 - T(T(5))) \times \left(-C(T(7), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \right) \\
 44754 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times \left(C(T(5), 7) + \left(\sqrt{4}^{T(4)} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44766 &:= \left((6^6) - \left(T(C(7,4)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\ 44778 &:= \left(T(87) + \left(C(T(7),4) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\ 44798 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(C(8,\sqrt{9})) \times T(7) \right) + T(T(4)) \right) + T(T(4)) \right) \\ 44799 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(9)) \right) + C((T(7) - T(4)), T(4)) \right) \\ 44827 &:= \left(\left(- (T(7)) \times \left(- (T(2)) - T(C(8, T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) \right) + (T(T(4))) \\ 44836 &:= \left((6^{T(3)}) - C((8 \times \sqrt{4}), 4) \right) \\ 44838 &:= \left((T(8) \times (T(3) + T(C(8,4)))) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\ 44845 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times C((T(8) - T(4)), 4) \right) \right) \\ 44847 &:= \left(\left(C((T(7) - (4)), \sqrt{T(8)}) - T(T(4)) \right) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 44849 &:= \left((T(9) - \sqrt{4}) \times (8 + T(C(T(4), \sqrt{4}))) \right) \\ 44858 &:= \left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 5) + (T(\sqrt{8^4})) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\ 44859 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(5)) - (T((8 + T(4))) \times T(T(4))) \right) \\ 44862 &:= \left(\left(C((T(2) + T(6)), \sqrt{T(8)}) - T(4) \right) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 44864 &:= \left(\left(C((4 \times 6), \sqrt{T(8)}) - 4 \right) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 44942 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(\left(C(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})) + \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\ 44969 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 6) - \left((T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(4))) \right) \right) \\ 44999 &:= \left(- (C(9,9)) - \left(- (T(9)) \times (T(4)^{T(\sqrt{4})}) \right) \right) \\ 45099 &:= \left(9 \times \left(T(\sqrt{9}) + C(T(05), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) \\ 45116 &:= \left((6^{T(T(1+1))}) - T(T(C(5, \sqrt{4}))) \right) \\ 45215 &:= \left(5 \times \left(- (1) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) / T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \right) \\ 45221 &:= \left(1 + \left((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) \times 5) / T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\ 45222 &:= \left(((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) / T(T(2))) \times 5) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\ 45223 &:= \left(((C(T(T(3))), T(T(2))) / T(T(2))) \times 5) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 45224 &:= \left(4 + \left((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) \times 5) / T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\ 45226 &:= \left(((C(T(6), T(T(2))) / T(T(2))) \times 5) + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\ 45227 &:= \left(7 + \left((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) \times 5) / T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45229 &:= \left(9 + \left((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) \times 5) / T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right)\right) \\ 45279 &:= \left((9 + C(T(7), 2)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(\sqrt{4}))\right) \\ 45289 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{T(8)}}\right) + (-2 - C(T(5), 4))\right) \\ 45291 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{1 \times 9})^{T(T(2))}\right) - (C(T(5), 4))\right) \\ 45293 &:= \left(\left(T(3)^{T(\sqrt{9})}\right) + (2 - C(T(5), 4))\right) \\ 45294 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9})^{T(T(2))}\right) - (C(T(5), 4))\right)\right) \\ 45298 &:= \left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8) \times 9}, (T(2) + (5))\right) + T(T(T(4)))\right) \\ 45339 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T((3 \times T(T(3))))\right) + (C(T(5), T(4)))\right) \\ 45357 &:= \left((C(T(7), (5 - 3)) \times T(T(5))) - T(\sqrt{4})\right) \\ 45423 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3))^2\right) \times \left(-(\sqrt{4} - C(T(5), \sqrt{4}))\right)\right) \\ 45457 &:= \left((T(T(7)) + ((C(T(5), T(4)) \times T(5)))) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))\right) \\ 45464 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), 6\right) - \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(5))\right) / T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\ 45494 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) - \left(\left(T(9) + T(T(4))\right) \times C\left(T(5), T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\ 45495 &:= \left(T(5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(4)\right) + C(T(5), T(4))\right)\right) \\ 45675 &:= \left(T\left(\left((5 \times 7) - 6\right) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\ 45748 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(8) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + \left(T(7) \times T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\ 45755 &:= \left(\left(5^5\right) + \left(T(T(7)) \times C\left(T(5), \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\ 45819 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) - \left(C\left(\left(-1 + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right), 5\right)\right)\right) \times \left(-T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\ 45825 &:= \left(T\left(\left(5^2\right)\right) \times \left(T(8) + C\left(T(5), \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\ 45845 &:= \left(\left(T\left(\left(5 \times T(4)\right)\right) \times T(8)\right) - T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\ 45874 &:= \left(-4 + \left(T(T(7)) \times \left(8 + C\left(T(5), \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\ 45898 &:= \left(\left(T(8) \times T\left(\left(T\left(C(9, 8)\right) + (5)\right)\right)\right) - \sqrt{4}\right) \\ 45899 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(9)) \times T(9)\right) - T(T(8))\right) - C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\ 45915 &:= \left(T(5) \times \left(1 + C\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(5)\right), 4\right)\right)\right) \\ 45927 &:= \left(\left(C(T(7), 2) \times \sqrt{9^5}\right) / \sqrt{4}\right) \\ 46296 &:= \left(\left(6^{T(\sqrt{9})}\right) - (T(2) \times T(C(6, 4)))\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46299 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - C((T(2) + T(6)), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 46344 &:= T(\sqrt{4})^{T(C(4,3))} - T(T(6)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 46355 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- (C(5,3)) - (T(6)^{T(\sqrt{4})}) \right) \right) \\ 46368 &:= \left((8 \times T(6)) \times C((3 + T(6)), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 46398 &:= \left(T((-8) + T(9)) \times C((T(3) + (6)), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 46411 &:= \left((T(T(11)) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\ 46421 &:= \left((T(C(12, \sqrt{4})) \times T(6)) - T(4) \right) \\ 46428 &:= T(8)^{C(T(2), \sqrt{4})} - T(T(6)) + T(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46443 &:= \left((T(3)^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))}) - (T(\sqrt{4}) + C(T(6), \sqrt{4})) \right) \\ 46446 &:= \left((6^{-4+T(4)}) - C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 46557 &:= \left(C(7,5) \times (T(T((5+6))) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\ 46734 &:= \left((T(T(\sqrt{4}))^{T(3)}) + C((7+6), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 46769 &:= \left((T(\sqrt{9})^6) + (-7) + T(C(6,4)) \right) \\ 46775 &:= \left((T(T(5)) - C(7,7)) + (6^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))}) \right) \\ 46776 &:= \left((T(T((6 - C(7,7)))) + (6^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))}) \right) \\ 46783 &:= \left((T(3)^{\sqrt{T(8)}}) + (7 + T(C(6,4))) \right) \\ 46833 &:= \left((T(C(T(3), 3)) \times (-8) + T(T(6))) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 46863 &:= \left(- (3) + \left((6^{\sqrt{T(8)}}) + C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\ 46886 &:= \left((T(T(6)) - C(8,8)) + (6^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))}) \right) \\ 46889 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{C(9,8)})^{\sqrt{T(8)}} \right) + T(T(6)) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\ 46932 &:= \left((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) + C((\sqrt{9} + T(6)), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 47034 &:= \left((T(T(\sqrt{4}))^{T(3)}) - (0 - C(T(7), \sqrt{4})) \right) \\ 47125 &:= \left((5^{T(2)}) \times (-1) + C(T(7), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 47224 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(2))) + (-((2^7)) \times T(T(4))) \right) \\ 47245 &:= \left(((C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) - 2) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(4)) \right) \\ 47284 &:= - \left((\sqrt{4} - ((T(8)^{T(2)}) + T(C(7,4)))) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47288 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)}^{\sqrt{T(8)}} + (2 + T(C(7,4))) \right) \right) \\
 47289 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((T(8)^{T(2)} + T(C(7,4))) \right) \right) \\
 47292 &:= \left(\left((T(T(2))^{T(\sqrt{9})} + T(T(2))) + (T(C(7,4))) \right) \right) \\
 47439 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times (-T(3) + T(T(4)))) - C(T(7), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 47524 &:= \left(((C(T(4), 2) \times 5) - (7))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 47624 &:= \left(-(4) + \left(T(T(2)) \times \left(T(6) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47634 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + \left((T(3) \times T(6)) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 47646 &:= \left(6 \times \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + \left((T(6) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47655 &:= \left(-(T(5)) \times \left((T(T(5)) - T(6)) - C(T(7), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 47658 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times \left(5 + \left(T(6) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47664 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times \left(6 + \left(T(6) \times C(T(7), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47796 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) - \left(T(7) \times T(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 47848 &:= \left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 4) \times 8 \right) - (T(7) + (4)) \right) \\
 47849 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(8) \right) - \left(T(7) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 47922 &:= \left(\left((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))} + T(T(9))) + T(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 47928 &:= \left(8 \times \left(T(T(2)) + \left(C((\sqrt{9} \times 7), 4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47948 &:= \left(\left((T(8) \times \sqrt{4}) \times T(C(9, 7)) \right) - (4) \right) \\
 47958 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times \left(-(T(5) - C((9+7), T(4))) \right) \right) \\
 47983 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{T(8)}\right), 9\right) - T(T(7)) \right) - T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 47986 &:= \left(\left(6\sqrt{T(8)} + C\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 7\right), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) \right) \\
 47988 &:= \left(T(8) + \left((T(8) \times T(C(9, 7))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 47992 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{9}) \times 9 \right) + (T(7)) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 47994 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times \left(-(9) + C((9+7), T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 48048 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times C\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 08\right), T(4)\right) \right) \\
 48144 &:= \left((4 + T(T(4))) \times C\left(18, T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) \\
 48224 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))} + C(8, \sqrt{4})) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48248 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{T(8)}} - 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 48249 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))} \right) - T(2) \right) + T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48258 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(8, 5 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(8 \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \\
 48264 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(4 \right) + 6 \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(8 \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 48281 &:= \left(\left(-1 + T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 48283 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + 4 \\
 48288 &:= \left(T \left(8 \right) + T \left(C \left(8, T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(8 \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \\
 48289 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + T(4) \\
 48297 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \\
 48335 &:= \left(5 \times \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right)^3 + T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48355 &:= \left(-5 + \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(-3 + T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48372 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) + 7 \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) + \left(T \left(8 \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \\
 48427 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(7, 2 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(8 \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \\
 48432 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(4 \right) + 8 \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \\
 48445 &:= \left(-T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), 4 \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 48446 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \times C \left(T \left(4 \right), 4 \right) - \sqrt{8^4} \right) \\
 48464 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 48469 &:= \left(-T \left(9 \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \times C \left(T \left(4 \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 48483 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(8 \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \\
 48485 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 48487 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 48493 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + 4 \\
 48496 &:= \left(T \left(6 \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 48538 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(5 + 8 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48548 &:= - \left(\left(T(8) - C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(5) \right), 8 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 48549 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(T(T(5)) \times T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48566 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)) \right) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 48567 &:= \left(\left(T(T(C(7,6))) \times T(T(5)) \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 48633 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), 3) + T(6) \right) \times T(8) - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 48636 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), 3) + T(6) \right) \times \sqrt{T(8)^{\sqrt{4}}} \right) \\
 48638 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 3 \right) + T(6) \right) \times T(8) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 48681 &:= \left(T(18) - \left(- (T(T(6))) \times T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48685 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(T(6) \times T \left(\sqrt{8^4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 48713 &:= \left(- \left((T(3) + 1) \right) - \left(- (T(T(7))) \times T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48719 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) - C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48726 &:= \left(\left(T(C(6,2)) \times T(T(7)) \right) + \left(8 - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 48747 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(7)) \times C(T(4), 7) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 48748 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) + C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 48756 &:= \left(\left(T(6) + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(7))) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 48768 &:= \left(8 \times \left(6 + \left(T(T(7)) \times C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48792 &:= \left(C \left(\left(- (2) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), 7 \right) - T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48852 &:= \left(\left(2 - T(T(5)) \right) \times \left(- (8) - T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48882 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8))) \right) \times \left(-\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48944 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) - T((4 \times 9)) \right) \times C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 48953 &:= \left(C \left((3 + T(5)), 9 \right) - \left(T(T(8)) / \left(-\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 48962 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 + T \left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - T(4) \right) \\
 48986 &:= \left(\left(- (6) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) - 8 \right) \right) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48987 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(7)+8} \right), 9 \right) - 8 \right) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 48992 &:= \left(\left((-2) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 9 \right) \right) / \sqrt{T(8)} + 4 \right) \\
 48993 &:= \left(T(3) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 9 \right) - 8 \right) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48994 &:= \left(\left((T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(9) \right) - C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 48998 &:= \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8) \times 9}, 9 \right) + T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49137 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C \left(T(7), (T(3) - 1) \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) / \left(-\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 49155 &:= \left(T(5) + \left(T(5) \times C \left(T \left((1 + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49173 &:= \left(37 \times \left(-1 + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49182 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + 1 \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49189 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(- \left((T(8) + 1) \times C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49195 &:= \left(\left(T(5) \times C \left(T \left((T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) + T \left(T(4) \right) \right) \\
 49253 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T(3) \right) - C \left(T(5), T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49274 &:= - \left(\left(T(4) - \left((T(C(7,2)) - 9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49275 &:= \left(T(5) \times \left(C \left(T(7), T(2) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9}^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49277 &:= \left(-7 + \left((T(C(7,2)) - 9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 49278 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - \left((T(C(7,2)) - 9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49288 &:= \left(T \left(T(8) \right) + \left(C \left((T(8) / 2), 9 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 49314 &:= - \left(\left(T \left((T \left(T \left((4 + 1) \right) \right) - T \left(T(3) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49332 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T(2)^3), T(3) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 49333 &:= \left(\left(C \left((3^3), T(3) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 49334 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)^3, T(3) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49336 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T(6) + T(3)), T(3) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) / T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49338 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T \left(T(3) \right) \right), T(3) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 49339 &:= \left(\left(C \left((9 \times 3), T(3) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 4 \right) \\
 49346 &:= \left(\left((T \left(T(6) \right) + 4) \times T \left(C \left(T(3), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - 4 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49358 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) - \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(T(T(4)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49365 &:= \left(T(5) \times \left(T(T(6)) + C \left(\left(T(3) \times \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 49374 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(T(C(7,3)) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 49385 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times \left(T(C(8,T(3))) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - T(T(4)) \right) \\
 49416 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) + 1 \right) \times \left(C \left(T(4), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49432 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(T(T(T(3))) \times \left(C \left(T(4), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 49437 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(7)) + T(3) \right) \right) \times C \left(T(4), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \\
 49459 &:= \left(- (T(9)) - \left(C \left(\left(T(5) + \sqrt{4} \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times (-4) \right) \right) \\
 49468 &:= \left(- (T(8)) + \left(C \left(\left(T(6) - 4 \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 49483 &:= \left(- (T(T(3))) + \left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - 4 \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 49485 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(\left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(9) \right) \times T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 49495 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(9) \right) \times T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 49496 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \times T(T(4)) \right) \times T(9) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 49504 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(05) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 49528 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + C \left((2 + T(5)), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 49534 &:= \left(\left(T(43) \times (-5) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49544 &:= \left(4 \times \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(5) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T(4) \right) \right) \\
 49595 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{9} \right) \times (T(5) + (94)) \right) \\
 49634 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) \times (-3) \right) + \left(\left(C \left(T(6), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T(4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49638 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3 \right) \right) \times T(T(6)) \right) + T \left(\left(T(9) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49642 &:= \left(\left(- (T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) + \left(\left(C \left(T(6), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49649 &:= \left(\left(T(T(9)) + C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right), 9 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49655 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), 5 \right) + \left(\left(6^{T(\sqrt{9})} \right) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 49666 &:= \left(C(6,6) + \left(T \left(\left(T(6) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 49739 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(C \left(- \left(T(3) - T(7) \right), 9 \right) / (-T(4)) \right) \right) \\
 49799 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(\left(\left(T(7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + T(4) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49824 &:= \left((C(4,2) \times 8) \times \left(T(T(9)) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 49827 &:= \left(T(7) + \left(C\left(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (T(94)) \right) \right) \\
 49893 &:= \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - T((89+4)) \right) \\
 49938 &:= \left(T(C(8, T(3))) \times \left(\sqrt{9} \times (T(9) - (4)) \right) \right) \\
 49956 &:= \left(-(6) \times \left(-(C(T(5), 9)) - T(\sqrt{9^4}) \right) \right) \\
 49972 &:= \left(2 \times \left((7 \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 49973 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(C\left((T(7) - T(\sqrt{9})), 9 \right) / T(4) \right) \right) \\
 49974 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((7 \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 49976 &:= \left(((T(6) - (7)) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) - 4 \right) \\
 49978 &:= \left(\left((T(\sqrt{T(8)}) - 7) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 49982 &:= \left(((T(T(2)) + 8) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 49986 &:= \left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T\left((T(9) + T(9)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 50694 &:= - \left((T(4 \times T(T(\sqrt{9})))) - (C(T(6), T(05))) \right) \\
 50943 &:= \left(- (T(3^4)) + C\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(05) \right) \right) \\
 51183 &:= \left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T\left(T(-((T((1+1)) - T(5)))) \right) \right) \\
 51338 &:= \left(C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(3) \right) - T\left((T(T(3)) + T(T(-((1-5)))) \right) \right) \\
 51624 &:= - \left(\left((T(T(\sqrt{4}))^{T(T(2))}) - (C(T((6+1)), 5)) \right) \right) \\
 51636 &:= C(T(6), T(3)) - T\left(6 + T\left(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} \right) \right) \\
 51647 &:= -T(T(7)) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), 6 \right) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} \right) \right) \\
 51689 &:= \left(\left(-(T(T(9))) + C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), 6 \right) \right) - T\left(T\left(T(-((1-5)))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 51745 &:= - \left(\left(C\left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - (T((T(7)+1)) \times T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 51822 &:= C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} \right) \right) \\
 51864 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right), 6 \right) - \left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) - 1 \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) \\
 52173 &:= \left(\sqrt{C(T(T(3)), 7) + 1} \times T((2 + T(5))) \right) \\
 52184 &:= \left(- (T(4^{\sqrt{8+1}})) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 52194 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(\left(1 + 2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \\
 52242 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 52243 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) - 5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 52244 &:= \left(\left(- \left(4 \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 52246 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + 2 \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 52264 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T \left(4 \right)^6} \times \left(-2 \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \\
 52269 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(T \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) \times T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \\
 52368 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) \right), 6 \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \times T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52394 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 52429 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(4 \right) \times T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - 5 \\
 52439 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(4 \right) \times T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + 5 \\
 52464 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(\left(6 \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \\
 52496 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \\
 52499 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52569 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - C \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) - T \left(2 \right) \right), 5 \right) \\
 52729 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\left(7 + T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + 5 \\
 52746 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - T \left(C \left(7, T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 52787 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{7\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)}} - C \left(\left(T \left(7 \right) - T \left(2 \right) \right), 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52788 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(\left(T \left(7 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52824 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(8 \right) / T \left(2 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 52844 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 8 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52863 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(5 \right) \right) \\
 52869 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(6 \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(- \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 52883 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-\sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + 5 \right) \\
 52886 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(8 \right) + T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) / T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$52893 := \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(T(2))\right) + T(5) \right) \right)$$

$$52896 := \left(C\left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})\right) - (8 \times T((T(2) + T(5)))) \right)$$

$$52898 := - \left(\left(\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{9}\right) + T(8) \right) - C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(5)\right) \right) \right)$$

$$52935 := \left(\left((T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))) \times T\left(\sqrt{C(9,2)}\right) \right) + (T(5)) \right)$$

$$52939 := \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(3)\right) - \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(2)\right) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$52943 := \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) \right) + 5 \right)$$

$$52949 := \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) - \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(2)\right) - T(5) \right) \right)$$

$$52964 := - \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) - \left(\left(C\left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + (2 \times T(T(5))) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$52968 := \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 6\right) - (T((T(9) + T(2))) + T(T(5))) \right)$$

$$52986 := \left(\left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T(T(9)) \right) - (T(2)^5) \right)$$

$$52989 := \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T\left((T(9) + \sqrt{25})\right) \right)$$

$$52993 := - \left(\left((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9))) - \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(T(2))\right) - 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$53145 := \left(C\left(\sqrt{5^4}, (-1) + T(3)\right) + T(5) \right)$$

$$53183 := \left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T((1 + (3 \times T(5)))) \right)$$

$$53229 := \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{C(9,2)}\right), T(T(2))\right) - T((3 \times T(5))) \right)$$

$$53247 := \left(\left(\left(T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right)^2 + (T(3)) \right) - T(T(5)) \right)$$

$$53349 := - \left(\left(T(T(9)) - \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{4} \times 3\right), T(3)\right) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$53354 := \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times C\left(T(5), 3\right) \right) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(5)\right) \right) \right)$$

$$53356 := \left(\left(T(T(6))^{\sqrt{5-C(3,3)}} \right) - (5) \right)$$

$$53357 := \left((T(C(7,5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - \sqrt{T(T(3)) - 5} \right)$$

$$53427 := \left(\left(T(C(7,2))^{\sqrt{4}} + T((T(3) + (5))) \right) \right)$$

$$53438 := \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(3)\right) - (T(43) - T(T(5))) \right)$$

$$53447 := \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times (-\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(3)\right) - 5 \right) \right)$$

$$53452 := \left(\left(T(T((2+5))) \times (-\sqrt{4}) \right) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(5)\right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53454 &:= \left(\left(T(4) - T \left(\left(T(T(5)) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53459 &:= \left(\left(T((T(T(9)) / T(5)) / (-T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53473 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) + \left(T(T(7)) \times (-\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53474 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + \left((T(7)^{\sqrt{4}}) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53477 &:= \left(\left(-((T(7) \times T(7)) - T(\sqrt{4})) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53478 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(8)) - C(C(7, \sqrt{4}), T(3)) \right) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53481 &:= \left(\left(T(C(-((1-8)), \sqrt{4})) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) + (T(T(5))) \right) \\
 53482 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T((T(2) + T(8))) + \sqrt{4} \right) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53486 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + (C(T(4), 3) + (5)) \right) \\
 53494 &:= \left(\left(T((T(4) + T(9))) / (-\sqrt{4}) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53495 &:= \left(- \left(T(C(5, \sqrt{9})) \right) - (T((4 \times T(T(3)))) \times (-T(5))) \right) \\
 53499 &:= \left(- (T(9)) + \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (T(3) \times T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 53538 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - (-T(3)) \times T(T(5)) \right) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53542 &:= \left(- (2) - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 53544 &:= \left(\left((-4) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53549 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - ((T(T(5)) \times T(3)) - (5)) \right) \\
 53559 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(5)) \right) - (T(5)) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53564 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 6) - (T((T(T(5)) / 3)) - (T(T(5)))) \right) \\
 53583 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}) - (T(5)) \right) - T(T((3+5))) \right) \\
 53584 &:= \left(\left(T((\sqrt{4} \times 8)) \times (-5) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53588 &:= \left(\left(- (T(T(8))) + C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(5))) \right) - T(\sqrt{T(T(3)) - 5}) \right) \\
 53593 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) - (5) - T(T((3+5))) \right) \right) \\
 53594 &:= \left(\left(- (4) - T(T((\sqrt{9} + (5)))) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53598 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (9 - T(T(5))) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53629 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(2))) - 635 \right) \\
 53634 &:= \left(C(T((\sqrt{4} \times 3)), 6) - (T(35)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53674 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (T(7) \times T(6)) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53682 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(6)) \right) - T((T(T(3)) + (5))) \right) \\
 53684 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T(8) \right) \right) \right) - ((C(T(6), T(3)) + T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 53686 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) + T((C(6,3) + 5)) \right) \\
 53687 &:= \left(- (T(T(7))) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 6 \right) - T((3 + T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 53688 &:= \left(- (T(T(8))) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 6 \right) + (T(3) \times T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53698 &:= - \left(\left(T \left((T(8) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - (C(T(6), T(3)) - (5)) \right) \\
 53736 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(3)) - T \left(\sqrt{(7-3)^5} \right) \right) \\
 53744 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(4)) + T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(7) \right) \right) \right) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53759 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - ((T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) - C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\
 53783 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T((T(7) + 3)) \right) + (T(5)) \right) \\
 53789 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (T((T(7) + T(3))) - T(T(5))) \right) \\
 53795 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) - (T(T(3))) \times 5 \right) \\
 53796 &:= \left(C \left(T(6), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - ((T(7) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(5))) \right) \\
 53802 &:= \left(\left(- (2) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(08)} \right) \right) \right) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \right) \\
 53824 &:= \left(\left(T(T(4)) \times \left(- (2) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53827 &:= \left(T(7) + \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (T((T(3) \times 5))) \right) \right) \\
 53828 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(T(2)) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 53834 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(3) \right) - (T((8 + T(T(3)))) - 5) \right) \\
 53837 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(7)) - \left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (T(3) + T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53843 &:= \left(C \left(T(T(3)), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - (T(C(8, T(3))) + (T(5))) \right) \\
 53844 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times C \left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53845 &:= - \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - T(8) \right) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53847 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(T(T(7)) + T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + 8 \right) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53849 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - (83 \times 5) \right) \\
 53852 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left((2+5) \right) \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53857 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) - (5) \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53859 &:= \left(\left(T \left(9 \right) \times \left(- \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 53864 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) - 6} \right) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53867 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - \left(T \left(3 \right) - T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53868 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(6 \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + \left(- \left(3 \right) \times T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53871 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 53873 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 53879 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) / T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53883 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + \left(- \left(3 \right) \times T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53886 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T \left(- \left(8 - 35 \right) \right) \right) \\
 53887 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left(- \left(8 \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53889 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53891 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(1 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53896 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(6 \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 8 \right) + \left(- \left(3 \right) \times T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53898 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(8 \right) \times T \left(9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 53912 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(1 - \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53913 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{1 \times 9} \right) \right) - T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) + \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53914 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(- \left(1 \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53919 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) / \left(- \left(1 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 53921 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(1 + T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53927 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(7^{T(2)} \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 53939 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(9 \right) - C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53942 &:= \left(\left(T(2) - T \left(\left(4 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53944 &:= \left(\left(T(4) - \left(T(T(4)) \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53945 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{5^4} \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53948 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 4 \right) \right) + \left(-9 - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 53958 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T(8) + T(5) \right) \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53959 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(9)) - T(T(5)) \right) / \left(-\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53962 &:= \left(\left(-2 - T \left(\left(T(6) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53963 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T(T(3)) + T(6) \right) \right) / \left(-\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53969 &:= \left(\left(T(T(9)) - C \left(T(6), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53983 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(- \left(8^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53984 &:= \left(\left(-T(4) \right) \times C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53987 &:= \left(\left(-7 + \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (-T(9)) \right) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53988 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (-T(9)) \right) \right) \right) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53989 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - \left(T(9) \times T(3) + 5 \right) \right) \\
 53992 &:= \left(\left(-2 + \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times (-T(9)) \right) \right) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\
 53993 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T(9) - T(T(T(3))) \right) + 5 \right) \right) \\
 53994 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(4) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-9) \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53996 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(6)) - T(T(9)) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \\
 53997 &:= \left(T(7) \times (-9) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(3) \right) - T(5) \right) \right) \\
 53998 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 53999 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(T(9) \times T(3) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 54024 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(T(2)) \right) - \left(\sqrt{04} \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54028 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{04} \right) \right) \right) - 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54036 &:= \left(- \left(T(T(6)) - 3 \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{04} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54038 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{04} \right) \right) \right) + 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54043 &:= \left(- \left(T(T(T(3))) - T(4) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{04} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54044 &:= \left((T(T(4)) \times (-4)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{04}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54048 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)}^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \right) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{04}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54049 &:= \left(- ((T(T(9)) - (T(40)))) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54054 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) - T((04 \times 5)) \right) \\
 54084 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{T(4) \times T(80)} \right) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54089 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{T(8)}) - (T(T(04)) + T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54093 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) - T((T(\sqrt{04}) + (T(5)))) \right) \\
 54099 &:= \left(- (T(9)) + (C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(\sqrt{04}))) - (T(T(5)))) \right) \\
 54117 &:= \left((- (7) \times T(T(T((1+1)))) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54122 &:= \left(((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - 1) - T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - (T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54124 &:= \left(((C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(2))) + 1) - T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - (T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54128 &:= \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(2))) - T(((1^4) + T(5))) \right) \\
 54129 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(2))) - ((- (1) + T(4)) \times T(5)) \right) \\
 54138 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - (C(T(T(3)), T(- ((1-4)))) - T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 54139 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(3)) - ((1+4) + T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54142 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (\sqrt{1 \times 4} + T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54143 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (1 + T((T(4) + (5)))) \right) \\
 54146 &:= \left((C(T(6), T((4-1))) + \sqrt{4}) - T(T(5)) \right) \\
 54148 &:= \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (- ((1 \times 4)) + T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54149 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (T(T((1+4))) - (5)) \right) \\
 54152 &:= - \left(((T(T(T(T(2)))) - ((T(T(5)) - 1))) - C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5))) \right) \\
 54154 &:= \left(T(4) + (C(T((5+1)), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (T(T(5)))) \right) \\
 54155 &:= \left(\left(- (T(T(5))) + \sqrt{T(T(5)) + 1} \right) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54158 &:= \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(5)) - (- (14) + T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54159 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(5)) - T(((- (1) + T(4)) + (5))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54164 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), 6 \right) - (T(14) - (5)) \\
 54166 &:= \left(\left((C(T(6), 6) + 1) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) - (T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54172 &:= \left(- \left((T(T(T(2))) + (71)) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54173 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), (7-1)) - T \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T(5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54174 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), (7-1) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(5) \right) \\
 54178 &:= \left(- \left((87-1) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54179 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(7) \right) + 1 \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54183 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T((1+T(4))) \right) - (T(5)) \right) \\
 54186 &:= \left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(((1-4) + T(5))) \right) \\
 54192 &:= \left((-2) \times T((9-1)) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54193 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - T((1+T(4))) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 54194 &:= \left(- (T(T(4))) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T(-((1-4))) \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 54196 &:= \left(- \left((69-1) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54198 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - T((-((1 \times 4)) + T(5))) \\
 54199 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - (-1) + T((-4) + T(5))) \\
 54204 &:= \left(- (T(T(4))) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(02 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 54206 &:= \left(- \left((60-2) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54208 &:= \left(- (C(8, T(02))) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54209 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T(T(02)) \right) - T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54212 &:= \left((T(2) - T(T((1+T(2)))) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54215 &:= \left(- \left((51-2) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54218 &:= \left((-T(8) - T((1+T(2)))) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\
 54221 &:= - \left(\left(T((1+T(T(2)))) - \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54229 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T(T(2)) \right) - \left(T(2) + \sqrt{4^5} \right) \\
 54231 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right), T(T(2)) \right) - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \\
 54232 &:= \left(C \left(T \left((2 \times 3) \right) \right), T(T(2)) \right) - \sqrt{4^5} \\
 54235 &:= \left(- \left((T(T(5)) - C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right), T(T(2)))) + T \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T(5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54238 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \\
 54242 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (2 + (4 \times 5)) \right) \\
 54244 &:= - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times T(4)) - C(T((2+4)), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54246 &:= \left((-6) \times T(\sqrt{4}) + (C(T((2+4)), T(5))) \right) \\
 54248 &:= \left((-8) \times \sqrt{4} + C(T((2+4)), T(5)) \right) \\
 54251 &:= \left(C(T((1+5)), T(T(2))) + \left((\sqrt{4} - T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54254 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times (-5)) + C(T((2+4)), T(5)) \right) \\
 54255 &:= \left(T(5) - \left((-C(T(5), T(2))) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) \\
 54261 &:= \left(C(T((1 \times 6)), T(T(2))) - \sqrt{4+5} \right) \\
 54267 &:= \left(-7 + \left(C(T(6), T(T(2))) + (\sqrt{4} \times 5) \right) \right) \\
 54268 &:= \left(T(8) + \left(C(T(6), T(T(2))) - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \\
 54273 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{7+2})) + (4+5) \right) \\
 54274 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + T(C(7,2)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 54276 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), T((7-2))) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + (T(5)) \right) \\
 54277 &:= \left(C((-7) + T(7), T(T(2))) - \left((\sqrt{4} - T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54278 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) - (7 - C(T((2+4)), T(5))) \right) \\
 54279 &:= \left(C((\sqrt{9} \times 7), (2+4)) + T(5) \right) \\
 54281 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{1+8})), T(T(2))) + (\sqrt{4} + T(5)) \right) \\
 54282 &:= \left(\left(T(2) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + (C(T((2+4)), T(5))) \right) \\
 54283 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}) + (24 - 5) \right) \\
 54286 &:= \left(C(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}) + (2 + (4 \times 5)) \right) \\
 54287 &:= \left(-7 + \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(2))) + (\sqrt{4} \times T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54289 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{T(8)}) + \left((T(2) + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54291 &:= \left(-1 + \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(2))) + T((\sqrt{4} + 5)) \right) \right) \\
 54293 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{9})) + (24 + 5) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54294 &:= \left((T(4) \times \sqrt{9}) + C(T((2+4)), T(5)) \right) \\ 54295 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(T(2)) \right) + T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 54296 &:= \left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{C(9,2)} \right) + \sqrt{4^5} \right) \\ 54297 &:= \left(- (7) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(T(2)) \right) + (T(T(4)) - (T(5))) \right) \right) \\ 54298 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(2 + \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \\ 54299 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(T(2) + \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \\ 54306 &:= \left((T(6) + T(T(03))) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\ 54307 &:= \left(T(7) + \left(C \left(T \left(T(03) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T(5) \right) \right) \\ 54313 &:= \left(- (T(3)) + T(T((1+3))) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\ 54318 &:= \left(((8+1) \times T(3)) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\ 54321 &:= \left((T(12) - T(T(3))) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\ 54322 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right), T \left(T(2) \right) \right) + \left(3 + T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 54329 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{C(9,2)} \right), T(3) \right) - T(T(4)) \right) + T(T(5)) \right) \\ 54334 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 3 \right) \right), T(3) \right) + T(T(4)) \right) + (T(5)) \right) \\ 54343 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + ((T(T(3)) \times 4) - (5)) \right) \\ 54349 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + ((T(T(3)) - 4) \times 5) \right) \\ 54351 &:= T \left(\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} \right) + T(T(3)) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \\ 54352 &:= \left((C \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right), T(5) \right) - 3) + T \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T(5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 54354 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(5) \right) + (C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), (T(4) + (5)) \right)) \right) \\ 54355 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T(5) \right) \times \left(C \left(T(5), 3 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - (5) \right) \\ 54357 &:= \left(T((7+5)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T(5) \right) \right) \\ 54358 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) - T \left(T \left(T(3) \right) \right) \right) + (T((T(4) + T(5)))) \right) \\ 54366 &:= \left(C \left(T(6), 6 \right) + \left(T(3) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\ 54368 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - (C \left(T(6), T(3) \right) - T(4)) \right) - T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\ 54374 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \right), T(3) \right) - T(4) \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \\ 54377 &:= \left(- (7) + \left(C \left((7 \times 3), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + (T \left(T(5) \right)) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54381 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{1+8} \right) \right), T(3) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54382 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(- \left((2-8) \right) \right), T(3) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54383 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(T(34) / 5 \right) \right) \\
 54386 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(6), T \left((8-3) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54388 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(\left(T(3) - \sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54389 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(\left(3 + \sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54391 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(3) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54392 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(\left(T(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54393 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(T(3) \right) \right) + \left(T(4) \times T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54394 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{4 \times 9} \right), T(3) \right) + T(4) \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54395 &:= \left(5 + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(3) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54396 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(6), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(T(3) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54398 &:= \left(8 + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(3) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54399 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(9) \right) + C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), \left(T(4) + (5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54408 &:= \left(\left(T(8) \times 04 \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54412 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T \left(T(2) \right) + 1 \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54414 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left((4-1) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(T(4) \times T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54415 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(5) + 1 \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54417 &:= \left(C \left(T \left((7-1) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54419 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right) - T \left(T(4) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54423 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), T \left(T(2) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54426 &:= \left(- (6) - \left(\left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \times \left(-C \left(T(4), 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54428 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T \left(T(2) \right) \right) + \left(44 + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54429 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \times \left(-C \left(T(4), 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54431 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\left(T(3) \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \times \left(-C \left(T(4), 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54433 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), T(3) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T(4) \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54434 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(T(3)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \times (-C(T(4), 5)) \right) \right) \\
 54436 &:= \left(\left((C(T(6), T(3)) + T(T(4))) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T(T(5)) \right) \\
 54438 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} - \left(\left(T(3)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \times (-C(T(4), 5)) \right) \right) \\
 54439 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + T((T(4) + (5)))) \right) \\
 54441 &:= \left(\left((1 + T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \right) \right) - \left(T(T(4)) - C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54443 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + ((4 + T(T(4))) + T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54446 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times T(-((\sqrt{4} - T(5)))) \right) \right) \\
 54456 &:= \left((C(T(6), T(5)) + \sqrt{4}) + T((4 + T(5))) \right) \\
 54463 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \\
 54468 &:= \left(T(8) - \left(\left(6^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) \times (-C(T(4), 5)) \right) \right) \\
 54469 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 6) + (C(T(4), 4) - (5)) \right) \\
 54473 &:= \left((T(T(T(3))) - 7) + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54474 &:= \left(C((T(\sqrt{4}) \times 7), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T((4 \times 5)) \right) \\
 54476 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{-6 + T(T(7))}) + \sqrt{4} \right) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54482 &:= \left(T(T(T(T(2)))) + \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + ((\sqrt{4} - T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 54483 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + ((T(\sqrt{4}) - (T(5)))) \right) \right) \\
 54484 &:= \left(-(T(T(4))) + \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (T(T(4)) \times (-5)) \right) \right) \\
 54491 &:= \left((1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 54492 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{9})) + \sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^{T(4)}} \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 54497 &:= \left(-(7) + \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + (\sqrt{4} \times T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 54498 &:= \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(\sqrt{9})) + \left(-(\sqrt{4}) \times (T(\sqrt{4}) - T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 54504 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(05)) + (\sqrt{4} \times T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54512 &:= \left((T((T(T(T(2))) + 1)) - 5) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54517 &:= \left(T((7 + 15)) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54522 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) + \left(T(5) + \left(T(\sqrt{4})^5 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54523 &:= \left((T(T(T(3))) / (-T(2))) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54524 &:= \left((-T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2))) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54528 &:= \left((T(8) \times (-2)) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54529 &:= \left(((T(9) \times T(T(2))) - 5) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54542 &:= \left((-T(2)) - T(T(4)) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54544 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + ((5 \times T(T(4))) + 5) \right) \\
 54547 &:= \left(T(T(7)) + \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) - (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 54548 &:= \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + ((T(T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) / (-5)) \right) \\
 54549 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + ((T(5) + 4) \times T(5)) \right) \\
 54554 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + ((5 \times T(T(4))) + T(5)) \right) \\
 54557 &:= \left(-((T(7) + T(5))) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54558 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times (T((5 \times T(5))) - C(T(4), 5)) \right) \\
 54559 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(5)) + (((T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) \right) \\
 54564 &:= - \left((T(\sqrt{4} + 6)) - \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54568 &:= - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + (-C(T(6), T(5))) - T((T(4) + T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 54569 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 6) - ((-T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) / (-5)) \right) \\
 54571 &:= \left((-1) - T(7) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54573 &:= \left((T(T(T(3))) + (T((7 + 5)))) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54574 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} - T(7)) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54578 &:= \left((\sqrt{T(8)} - T(7)) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54579 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times (-7)) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54582 &:= \left((-T(2) \times \sqrt{T(8)}) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54583 &:= \left(-T(3) + \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(5)) + (T((T(4) + T(5)))) \right) \right) \\
 54584 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times (-8)) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54586 &:= \left(-((6 + 8)) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54587 &:= \left((-7 - \sqrt{T(8)}) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54588 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54589 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) \right) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54591 &:= \left(- \left((1 \times 9) \right) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54592 &:= \left(- \left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54593 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) / (-\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54594 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4 \times 9} \right) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54596 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) + ((T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) / 5) \right) \\
 54597 &:= - \left(\left(T(-((7-9))) - \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54598 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} / (-\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54599 &:= \left(- \left(C(9,9) \right) + \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54607 &:= \left(\sqrt{706} + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54614 &:= \left(T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - \left(1 - \left(C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54622 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), 6) + \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54624 &:= \left(C(T(C(4,2)), 6) + \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54627 &:= \left(C(T(7), 2) + \left(C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - T(5) \right) \right) \\
 54637 &:= \left(T((T(7) - T(3))) + \left(C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54641 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + T \left(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^6} \right) \right) + C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) \right) \\
 54644 &:= \left((T(T(T(4))) / 4) + \left(C(T(6), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 54649 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + \left((T(T(6)) / T(\sqrt{4})) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54654 &:= \left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(5)) + \left(T((6 \times \sqrt{4})) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54665 &:= \left(- (5) + C(T(6), 6) + T(T(\sqrt{4} + (5))) \right) \\
 54666 &:= \left((T(T(6)) + C(T(6), 6)) + T(T(\sqrt{4} + (T(5)))) \right) \\
 54667 &:= \left(T(T(7)) + \left(C(T(6), 6) - \sqrt{4+5} \right) \right) \\
 54669 &:= \left((T(9) + C(T(6), 6)) + \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54684 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(6)) \right) \times (4 + T(T(5))) \right) \\
 54686 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \right) + \left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4})) - (5) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54687 &:= \left(T(T(7)) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 6\right) + \left(\sqrt{4} + T(5)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54691 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\left(1 + T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) + T(6) \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54696 &:= \left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{9}\right) + \left(\left(T(T(6))^{\sqrt{4}}\right) + (5) \right) \right) \\
 54697 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{96}} \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54699 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) + T\left(\left(6 \times 4\right) + 5\right) \right) \\
 54722 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right), T\left(T(2)\right)\right) + \left(-7 + T\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times T(5)\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54723 &:= \left(\left(-T(3) + T\left(\left(2 + T(7)\right)\right)\right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54724 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T\left(T(2)\right)\right) + \left(T\left(\left(T(7) + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) - (5)\right) \right) \\
 54729 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), T\left(T(2)\right)\right) + T\left(\left(C(7,4) - 5\right)\right) \right) \\
 54732 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(2)) + T\left(T\left(T(3)\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 54733 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(3)) \times T\left(T(3)\right)\right) + T(7) \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54734 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(3)\right) + \left(T\left(\left(T(7) + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (5)\right) \right) \\
 54736 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(6), T(3)\right) + (7)\right) + T\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54742 &:= \left(\left(\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right)\right)\right) \times \left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \right) - 5 \right) \\
 54754 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(5)\right) + \left(7 \times \left(T\left(T(4)\right) + T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54764 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), 6\right) + \left(-T(7) + T\left(\sqrt{4^5}\right)\right) \right) \\
 54768 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 6\right) + \left(T(7) \times \left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54769 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), 6\right) + \left(\left(7 \times T\left(T(4)\right)\right) + T\left(T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54775 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(5) \times 7\right) + T\left(T(7)\right)\right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54783 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T\left(T(3)\right) + T(8)\right)\right) + C\left(\left(T(7) - T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right), 5\right) \right) \\
 54784 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + \left(\left(T\left(T(7)\right) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) + T\left(T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54786 &:= \left(\left(\left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T\left(T(7)\right)\right) - 4 \right) + T\left(T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54788 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + \left(\left(T\left(T(7)\right) - \sqrt{4}\right) + T\left(T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54794 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) + \left(\left(T\left(T(7)\right) + 4\right) + T\left(T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54796 &:= \left(C\left(T(6), T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) + \left(T(7) \times \left(4 + T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54819 &:= \left(9 \times \left(1 - \left(T\left(C\left(8, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times \left(-T(5)\right)\right)\right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54833 &:= \left((T(33) + 8) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54839 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(3)\right) + (T(T(8))) \right) - T\left(-\left(\sqrt{4} - T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54852 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right), T(5)\right) + \left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{4} + (5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 54853 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), T(5)\right) - T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) + (T((T(T(4)) - (T(5)))) \right) \\
 54859 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(5)\right) + T((T(8) - (T(4)/5))) \right) \\
 54889 &:= \left(- (T(T(9))) + \left(\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T(T(T(4))) \right) + (T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 54894 &:= \left(T\left(\sqrt{T(49)}\right) + \left(C\left(T\left((8 - \sqrt{4})\right), T(5)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54896 &:= \left(C\left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + \left((8^{T(\sqrt{4})}) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54898 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + \left(T(T(8)) - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \\
 54927 &:= \left((C(T(7), T(2)) - T(9)) \times (\sqrt{4} + T(5)) \right) \\
 54928 &:= \left((T(T(8)) - 2) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{9 \times 4}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54952 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right), T(5)\right) + \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - 5 \right) \right) \\
 54954 &:= - \left(\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right) - \left(\left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54955 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{9}\right) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54962 &:= \left((T(2) \times T(T(6))) + \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + 5 \right) \right) \\
 54966 &:= \left(C\left(T(6), 6\right) - \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(T(\sqrt{4}) - T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54972 &:= \left((T(T(T(2))) \times T(7)) + \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + (T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 54977 &:= \left((- (T(7)) + T((- (7) + T(9)))) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 54979 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) + T(7)\right)\right) + \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + (T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 54988 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + \left((9^{T(\sqrt{4})}) - (5) \right) \right) \\
 54993 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + (9^{\sqrt{4+5}}) \right) \\
 54994 &:= \left(\left(T(4) + C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) + \left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 54995 &:= \left(\left(\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times T(T(4)) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 54998 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + \left((9^{T(\sqrt{4})}) + (5) \right) \right) \\
 55125 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(5), 2\right)^{\sqrt{-1+5}} \right) \times 5 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55239 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(3) \right) + \left(T(2) \times T((5 \times 5)) \right) \right) \\ 55254 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) + \left(T((T(T(2)) + (5))) \times T(5) \right) \right) \\ 55264 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(4)^6} + C((T(T(2)) + (T(5))), T(5)) \right) \\ 55287 &:= \left(T \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + (T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\ 55288 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(2^{5+5} \right) \right) \\ 55289 &:= \left(T(T(9)) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(T(2)) \right) - (5 + 5) \right) \right) \\ 55298 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - T(T(9)) \right) \right) + \left(C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 5 \right) \right) \\ 55345 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(T(5), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - \left(T((T(3) \times 5)) \times T(T(5))) \right) \right) \right) \\ 55384 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(4)^{\sqrt{T(8)}}} + \left(C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\ 55439 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(3) \right) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) - C(5,5) \right) \\ 55459 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(5) \right) - \left((-T(4)) \times T(T(5)) + (5) \right) \right) \\ 55469 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 6 \right) - \left((-T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - (5) \right) \right) \\ 55485 &:= \left(\left(5 + T \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(T(T(5)) + (T(5)) \right) \right) \\ 55489 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T \left(\left(T(T(4)) - T((T(5)/5)) \right) \right) \right) \\ 55495 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(\left(4^5 \right) - T(5) \right) \right) \\ 55497 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), T(5) \right) + T(5) \right) \right) \\ 55594 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(5) \right) \times C(T(5), 5) \right) \right) \right) \\ 55599 &:= \left(T(T(9)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), T(5) \right) + T \left(\left(T(T(5)) / 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 55698 &:= \left(- \left(T(T(8)) \right) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(6)) + \left(C(T(5), 5) \right) \right) \right) \\ 55794 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(T((9 + C(7,5))) \times T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\ 55819 &:= \left(T(T((9+1))) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) + T(5) \right) \right) \\ 55828 &:= \left(C(8,2) - \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times 5 \right) \right) \times \left(-T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\ 55834 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + (T(5) + T(5)) \right) \right) \right) \\ 55865 &:= \left(T(56) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) + 5 \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55876 &:= \left((T(T(6)) \times 7) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) - 5 \right) \right) \\ 55889 &:= \left(\left(C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T(T(8)) \right) - 55 \right) \\ 55895 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{9} \right) + (T(8) \times T(55)) \right) \\ 55899 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(T(T(9)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + C(5,5) \right) \right) \\ 56094 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(4) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - (0 - C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\ 56155 &:= \left(T \left(\left(- (5) + T \left(\sqrt{T(T(5)) + 1} \right) \right) \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\ 56184 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (- (16) \times T(T(5))) \right) \\ 56264 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(4)}^6 \times 2 \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\ 56334 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times T(T((3 \times 3))) \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\ 56344 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{(4 \times 4)^3} \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\ 56349 &:= \left(\left(T(T(9)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) + (T(5))) \right) \\ 56388 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - ((T(T(3)) - (T(65)))) \right) \\ 56409 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), T \left(T(\sqrt{04}) \right) \right) + T(65) \right) \\ 56427 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{7+2} \right) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (C(T(6), 5))) \right) \\ 56447 &:= \left(- (T(7)) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + T(T((6+5))) \right) \right) \\ 56449 &:= \left(\left(T((9+T(4)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + (C(T(6), 5)) \right) \\ 56454 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right), T(5) \right) + ((T(4) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(5))) \right) \\ 56464 &:= \left(T(T(4)) + \left(C \left(T(6), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + T(65) \right) \right) \\ 56484 &:= \left(\left((T(4) \times T(T(8))) / T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\ 56595 &:= \left(\left((5^{\sqrt{9}}) + T(T(5)) \right) \times T(T(C(6,5))) \right) \\ 56658 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - T(T(5)) \right) \times (-T(6)) \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\ 56682 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(2)}^8 \right) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(C(6,5)))) \right) \\ 56749 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + T(((- (7) + T(6)) \times 5)) \right) \\ 56794 &:= \left(\left(T(4) \times T \left(- \left(T(\sqrt{9}) - T(7) \right) \right) \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\ 56839 &:= \left(\left(T(T(9)) + C \left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(6)-5} \right) \right) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 56846 &:= \left(C(6, T(\sqrt{4})) - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \times (- (T(T(6)) + T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 56874 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T((-7 + T(8))) \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\
 56884 &:= \left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times T(8) \right) \right) + (- (8) + C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\
 56889 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + T((T(8) + T(8))) \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\
 56892 &:= \left(T \left(\left(\left(T(2) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 8 \right) \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\
 56894 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T((9 \times 8)) \right) + C(T(6), T(5)) \right) \\
 56898 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + ((T((9 \times 8)) + C(T(6), T(5)))) \right) \\
 56935 &:= \left((T(C(5,3)) \times T(T(9))) + T \left(\sqrt{T(6) - 5} \right) \right) \\
 56946 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + ((T(C(9,6)) + T(5))) \right) \\
 56952 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T(2) - C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times (6 + T(T(5))) \right) \\
 56973 &:= \left(\left(T((T(3) \times 7)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \right) \\
 56987 &:= \left(- (T(7)) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (T(C(9,6))) \right) \times T(5) \right) \right) \\
 57114 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T(T((1+1))) \right) + (T(75)) \\
 57239 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), T(3) \right) + (T((T(T(2)) + T(7)) \times 5)) \\
 57264 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), 6 \right) + (- ((T(2) - T(7)) \times T(T(5)))) \\
 57339 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(T((7+5)))) \right) \right) \\
 57342 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - (3 - T(T((7+5)))) \\
 57348 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - (- (3) - T(T((7+5)))) \\
 57384 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T(C(8,3)) \right) \right) \times T((- (7) + T(5))) \right) \\
 57389 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(\sqrt{-3 + T(7)}^5 \right) \\
 57393 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) - (- (T(7)) \times T(T(5))) \\
 57474 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right), 7 \right) / \sqrt{4} - T(T((- (7) + T(5)))) \\
 57477 &:= \left(\left(7 \times C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times (T(T(7)) - T(5)) \right) \\
 57564 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \times (T(5) + T(C(7,5))) \right) \\
 57594 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - (- (5) \times T(T((- (7) + T(5)))) \\
 57834 &:= \left(T(T(T(4))) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - (T(T(7)) \times (-5)) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 57848 &:= \left(C(8, \sqrt{4}) \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) \times (-5))) \right) \\
 57894 &:= \left((T(T(4)) \times T(T(9))) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 7\right) / T(T(5)) \right) \right) \\
 57946 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), T(4)) / T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (-7 \times T(T(5))) \right) \\
 57948 &:= \left(\left(C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(9)) \right) - (7 + 5) \right) \\
 57955 &:= \left(\left(T(T(5)) \times \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) + T(7) \right) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 57984 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times (C((8+9), 7) - T(T(5))) \right) \\
 58092 &:= \left(T(-((T(2) - 90))) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 58219 &:= \left((T(91) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \right) \\
 58224 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right), T(T(2))\right) + (-((T(2) - T(8))) \times T(T(5))) \right) \\
 58254 &:= \left((T((4 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 58268 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(T(2)))) \right) + C(8, 5) \right) \\
 58294 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{4}) - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(2))) \times (-C(8, 5))) \right) \\
 58299 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - ((T(T(9)) + T(T(2))) \times (-C(8, 5))) \right) \\
 58354 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right) \times T(5)\right)\right) + \left(\left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - (5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 58356 &:= \left((C(T(6), T(5)) - 3) + T\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 58359 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right), T(5)\right) + T\left(\left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times 5\right)\right) \right) \\
 58362 &:= \left((T(2) + C(T(6), T(3))) + T\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(5)\right)\right) \right) \\
 58386 &:= \left(((T(6) + T(T(8))) \times T(3)) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 58387 &:= \left(\left(T\left(\left(T(7) - \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \times T(T(T(3))) \right) - C(8, 5) \right) \\
 58424 &:= \left(\left(T\left(\left(4^{T(2)}\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \\
 58428 &:= \left(T(8) \times \left((T(2))^{T(\sqrt{4})} + T(C(8, 5)) \right) \right) \\
 58429 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right) - \left(C\left(T(T(T(2))), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + T(T((8+5))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58435 &:= \left(-T(5) + \left(C\left(T(T(3)), T\left(T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) + T(T((8+5))) \right) \right) \\
 58445 &:= \left(\left(-5 + T\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(4)\right)\right) \right) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(5)\right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 58446 &:= \left(C \left(T(6), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (4 - T(T((8+5)))) \right) \\
 58451 &:= \left(\left(1 + T \left(T \left((T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\
 58452 &:= \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T(5) \right) - \left(-(\sqrt{4}) - T(T((8+5))) \right) \right) \\
 58453 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(T(3)), T(5) \right) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T(T((8+5))) \right) \\
 58454 &:= \left(\left(4 + T \left(T \left((T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\
 58456 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(6), T(5) \right) + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + T(T((8+5))) \right) \\
 58458 &:= \left(\left(8 + T \left(T \left((T(5) - \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\
 58498 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left(T(94) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58542 &:= \left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + T \left((T(T(5)) - T((-8) + T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 58557 &:= \left(\left(T \left((-T(7)) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) + T(5) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\
 58578 &:= \left(\left(T(8) + T \left((-T(7)) + T(T(5)) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) \\
 58582 &:= \left(-2 + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) + (T(8) \times T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 58587 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) / T(5) \right) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 5 \right) \right) \\
 58666 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(6), (T(T(6)) / T(6)) \right) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T(T(5)) \right) \\
 58699 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right), 9 \right) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(8))) \right) / 5 \right) \\
 58729 &:= \left(T \left((T((9+2)) + T(7)) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) \right) \\
 58793 &:= \left(C \left(T(T(3)), 9 \right) + \sqrt{T \left(T(7) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right)} \right) / 5 \\
 58818 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) - \left((C((1+8), 8^5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58849 &:= \left(T(94) + \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + (T(T(5))) \right) \right) \\
 58934 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(4))) - (T(3) \times T(T(9))) \right) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 58942 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(T(T(2))), T(4) \right) / T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (T(8) + T(T(5))) \right) \\
 58944 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4})^{T(4)} \right) - T \left((C(9,8) + 5) \right) \right) \\
 58973 &:= \left(\left((3 \times C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + (5) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 58989 &:= \left(\left(T(T(9)) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + (T(T(9)) \times C(8,5)) \right) \\
 58993 &:= \left(\left((3^9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (C(8,5)) \right) \\
 59029 &:= - \left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(2)) - (09^5) \right) \right) \\
 59187 &:= \left(\left(C(T(7), T(\sqrt{T(8)})) / (-1 + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) - T(5) \right) \\
 59236 &:= \left((T(T(6)) + C(T(3), T(2))) \times (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 5) \right) \\
 59238 &:= \left(T(8) - \left(C((3^{T(2)}), T(\sqrt{9})) / (-5) \right) \right) \\
 59248 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 9) / 5) \right) \\
 59349 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{T(4)} \right) + \left(C(T(3), \sqrt{9}) \times T(5) \right) \right) \\
 59443 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (-4 - (T(T(9)) \times 5)) \right) \\
 59547 &:= \left(\left(C(T(7), \sqrt{4}) + T(T(5)) \right) + (9^5) \right) \\
 59571 &:= \left((T(T((1+7))) \times T(T(5))) - C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 5) \right) \\
 59579 &:= \left(((T(T(9)) + T(7)) \times 5) + C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), T(5)) \right) \\
 59625 &:= \left((T(5) \times T(2)) \times \left(C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) - (5) \right) \right) \\
 59643 &:= \left(C(T(T(3)), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - (T(6) + (-T(9)) \times T(T(5)))) \right) \\
 59658 &:= \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(5)) - (6 + (-T(9)) \times T(T(5))) \right) \\
 59659 &:= \left((T(9) \times T(T(5))) + \left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) - (5) \right) \right) \\
 59689 &:= \left(T((T(\sqrt{9}) + T(8))) + (C(T(6), 9) / 5) \right) \\
 59949 &:= \left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(9) \right) + (9^5) \right) \\
 59955 &:= \left(\left(T(5) \times T((5 + C(9, \sqrt{9}))) \right) - T(T(5)) \right) \\
 59965 &:= \left(T(T(5)) + \left(\left(C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) \times T(9) \right) - (5) \right) \right) \\
 59974 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (7 \times C((9+9), 5)) \right) \right) \\
 59979 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + (7 \times C((9+9), 5)) \right) \\
 59997 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + (C((9+9), 5)) \right) \right) \\
 60249 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 4) + C(T(T(T(2))), 06) \right) \\
 61447 &:= \left(\left(C(T(7), 4) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + (1 + T(6)) \right) \\
 61453 &:= \left(\left(C(T(T(3)), 5) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T(T((1+6))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 61875 &:= \left(C(T(5), 7) + \left(T(8) \times T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{16}\right)\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 62694 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + C(9, 6) \right) \times \left(T(2)^6 \right) \right) \\
 62754 &:= - \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + (5)\right)\right) + \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62763 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{36} \right) - \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62768 &:= - \left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) + \left((6 - C(T(7), T(T(2)))) / 6 \right) \right) \right) \\
 62775 &:= \left(- T(5) - \left(C\left(T(7), T\left(\sqrt{7+2}\right)\right) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62782 &:= \left(\left(- (2) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62784 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 8 \right) - \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62785 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (5) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + C(T(7), T(T(2))) \right) / 6 \right) \\
 62788 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - 8 \right) - \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62792 &:= \left(\left(T(T(2)) / \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62794 &:= \left(C(4, \sqrt{9}) - \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62795 &:= \left(\left(T(5) / \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62797 &:= \left(C(7, T(\sqrt{9})) - \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62798 &:= \left(\left(- (8) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) - C(T(7), T(T(2))) \right) / (-6) \\
 62799 &:= \left(\sqrt{9 \times 9} - \left(C(T(7), T(T(2))) / (-6) \right) \right) \\
 62919 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), \left(1 + T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) - \left(T\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(T(6)\right)\right) \right) \\
 62979 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times \left(T\left(T(7)\right) + 9\right) \right) + C\left(T\left(T\left(T(2)\right)\right), 6\right) \right) \\
 62994 &:= \left(\left(T\left(\left(4 \times T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \times T\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right), T(2)\right)\right) \right) - 6 \right) \\
 62995 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(T\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right), \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(\left(T(2) + T(6)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 63258 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), 5\right) \times T(2) \right) + T\left(T\left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(3)\right)\right)\right) / T(6)\right)\right) \right) \\
 63287 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(T(2))\right) / T(3) \right) \right) - T(6) \right) \\
 63379 &:= - \left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right) - \left(7^{T(3)}\right) \right) + C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), 6\right) \right) \\
 63444 &:= \left(\left(- T(4) + T\left(T\left(T(4)\right)\right) \right) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) + C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), 6\right) \\
 63449 &:= \left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times T\left(T\left(T(4)\right)\right) \right) - \left(T(T(4)) - C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), 6\right) \right) \right) \\
 63494 &:= \left(\left(T\left(T\left(T(4)\right)\right) \times T\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \right) - \left(T(4) - C\left(T\left(T(3)\right), 6\right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63495 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(T(\sqrt{9}) - (T(T(C(4,3))) \times T(T(6))) \right) \right) \\ 63497 &:= \left(- (T(7)) + \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} + (C(T(T(3)),6)) \right) \right) \\ 63498 &:= \left(\left(T(8) \times (C(9, T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(3))) \right) - (6) \right) \\ 63846 &:= \left(\left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4})) \times (8 \times T(3)) \right) + (6) \right) \\ 63944 &:= \left(\left(- (T(T(4))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \right) + (C(T(T(3)),6)) \right) \\ 63984 &:= \left(\left(T((T(4) \times 8)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + C(T(T(3)),6) \right) \\ 64245 &:= \left(- (T(5)) - \left(C\left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(2))\right), 4\right) \times (-T(6)) \right) \right) \\ 64254 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) - ((C((T(5) + T(2)), 4) \times T(6))) \right) \right) \\ 64285 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + (T(2)^{T(4)}) \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \\ 64296 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(T(C(9, T(2))) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + (6) \right) \right) \\ 64344 &:= \left(\left(4 + C\left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(3)\right), 4\right) \right) \times T(6) \right) \\ 64393 &:= \left(C\left(T(T(3)), \sqrt{9}\right) + \left(T\left(\left(T(T(T(3))) / T(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times T(6) \right) \right) \\ 64416 &:= \left(61 \times \left(T\left(C\left(T(4), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (T(6)) \right) \right) \\ 64435 &:= \left(\left(- (T(5)) + C\left(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) \times (T(T(4)) - (6)) \right) \\ 64505 &:= \left(- (T(50)) + C\left(\left(5 + T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(6) \right) \right) \\ 64739 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(9)) + \left(\left(T(3) - C\left(\left(T(7) - \sqrt{4}\right), T(6)\right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 64856 &:= \left(C\left(\left(T(6) + (5)\right), T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + (-4) \times T(T(6)) \right) \\ 64882 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - \left(T(T(8))^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \right) / (-6) \right) \\ 64912 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(2))) + 1\right)^{\sqrt{9}} + C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right), 6\right) \right) \right) \\ 64939 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right), 3\right) \times (T(9) + (4)) - T(T(6)) \right) \right) \\ 64974 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\left(T(4) + (7)\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) / (-4) \right) \times (-T(6)) \right) \\ 64996 &:= \left(\left(6 \times T(T(9)) \right) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right), T(4) / 6\right) \right) \right) \\ 65339 &:= \left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times (-T(T(3))) \right) + C\left(\left(T(T(3)) + (5)\right), T(6) \right) \right) \\ 65437 &:= \left(- \left((7^3) \right) + C\left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) + 5, T(6) \right) \right) \\ 65455 &:= \left(- (T((5 \times 5))) + C\left(\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) + 5, T(6) \right) \right) \\ 65465 &:= \left(C\left(\left(5 + T(6)\right), T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) - ((T(5) \times T(6))) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65543 &:= \left(- (T(T(T(3)))) + \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + 5 \right), 5 \right) - 6 \right) \right) \\
 65549 &:= \left(C \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{4}) + T(5) \right), 5 \right) - T(T(6)) \right) \\
 65554 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + 5 \right), 5 \right) - (-5 + T(T(6))) \right) \\
 65654 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + ((T(T(5)) - (C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)))) \right) \right) \\
 65689 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 8 \right) \right) - C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 65774 &:= \left(C \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T(7) \right) \right), C(7,5) \right) - (6) \right) \\
 65822 &:= \left((2 \times T(T(T(2)))) + C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 5 \right), T(6) \right) \right) \\
 65825 &:= \left(C \left((5 + T(T(T(2)))) \right), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + T((T(5) - (6))) \\
 65828 &:= \left((8 \times T(T(2))) + C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 5 \right), T(6) \right) \right) \\
 65845 &:= \left((T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 5 \right), T(6) \right) \right) \\
 65846 &:= \left(T((T(6) - T(4))) + C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 5 \right), T(6) \right) \right) \\
 65855 &:= \left((5 \times T(5)) + C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 5 \right), T(6) \right) \right) \\
 65885 &:= \left(C \left(\left(5 + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + (5 \times T(6)) \\
 65948 &:= \left((8 \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 5 \right), T(6) \right) \right) \\
 65969 &:= \left((9 \times T(6)) + C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 5 \right), T(6) \right) \right) \\
 65996 &:= \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) + C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 5 \right), T(6) \right) \right) \\
 66242 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(T(2)))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + C(26, T(6)) \right) \\
 66245 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(5) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + C(26, T(6)) \right) \\
 66465 &:= \left(T(5) \times \left(\left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(6) \right) + T(6) \right) \right) \\
 66914 &:= \left(\left(- (T(T(4))) \times \left(1 - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + (C(T(6), 6)) \right) \\
 66948 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \times T(T(4)) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - (C(T(6), 6)) \right) \\
 67386 &:= \left(C \left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left((3^7) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 67456 &:= \left(T((T(6) - (5))) \times T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + T(C(7,6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 67689 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 6 \right) / 7 \right) - T(T(6)) \right) \right) \\
 67828 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} - C(T(T(T(2))), 8) \right) \times 7 \right) / (-T(6)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 67829 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right), 8 \right) \times \left(-7 \right) \right) / \left(-T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 67949 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(C \left(7, 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 67977 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(7 \right) \times \sqrt{C \left(9, 7 \right)} \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 68244 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \times T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 68248 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - \left(2 - \left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \times T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 68334 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) / 6 \right) \\ 68475 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) - 6 \right) \\ 68495 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(T \left(\left(T \left(4 \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \times T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 68538 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \times 3 \right), 5 \right) \times 8 \right) - \left(6 \right) \right) \\ 68788 &:= \left(- \left(8 \right) + \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \times C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(\left(8 - 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 68789 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 68793 &:= \left(- \left(3 \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(-C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(\left(8 - 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 68794 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(-C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(\left(8 - 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 68799 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(-C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(\left(8 - 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 68817 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), \sqrt{1+8} \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) + \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 68875 &:= \left(- \left(5 \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(8 \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right), 6 \right) \right) \\ 68949 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(9 \right) - \left(4 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(C \left(8, 6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 68974 &:= \left(T \left(4 \right) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \right) \times T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 69027 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{09} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \\ 69245 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 69299 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), 6 \right) \right) \\ 69315 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(1 \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 69328 &:= \left(C \left(8, 2 \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 69345 &:= \left(T \left(5 \right) \times \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 69348 &:= \left(\left(8 + \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69435 &:= \left(\left(T(T(C(5,3))) + T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T(\sqrt{9} + (6)) \right) \\ 69549 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{9}) - (C(T(4),5) \times (-T(9) - T(T(6)))) \right) \\ 69558 &:= \left(C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(5)\right) - ((-T(5) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(6))) \right) \\ 69615 &:= \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{16}) \times (T(9) + (6)) \right) \\ 69658 &:= -\left(\left(T\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)})\right) - \left((5^6) + C\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 6\right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 69825 &:= \left(-T(5) \times \left(C\left(T(T(2)), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T(96) \right) \right) \\ 69837 &:= \left(\left(C(T(7), 3) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) + (T(T(9)) + (6)) \right) \\ 69889 &:= \left(C\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + \left((8 - \sqrt{9})^6 \right) \right) \\ 69895 &:= \left((5^{T(\sqrt{9})}) + \left(C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + 6 \right) \right) \\ 69957 &:= \left(C((7 + T(5)), T(\sqrt{9})) - T(96) \right) \\ 69965 &:= \left(-C(T(5), 6) - \left(T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \times (-T(6)) \right) \right) \\ 71289 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(8) \right)^{C(2,1^7)} \right) \\ 71456 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) - T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) \right) \times T(T((1 \times 7))) \right) \\ 71484 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) - T((C(8,4) + 1)) \right) \times (-T(7)) \right) \\ 72296 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{9})) / T(T(T(2))) \right) - 2 \right) \times T(7) \right) \\ 72346 &:= \left(-6 - \left(\left(C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(3)) / T(T(T(2))) \right) \times (-T(7)) \right) \right) \\ 72388 &:= \left(T(8) - \left(\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(3)\right) / T(T(T(2))) \right) \times (-T(7)) \right) \right) \\ 72583 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) - \left(\left(C\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(5)\right) / T(T(T(2))) \right) \times (-T(7)) \right) \right) \\ 72669 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times (-T(T(6))) \right) + (C(C(6, T(2)), 7)) \right) \\ 72846 &:= \left(T\left((T(6) - T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \times \left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2)\right) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\ 72999 &:= \left(9 \times \left(-9 + \left(C(T(\sqrt{9}), T(2)) \times T(T(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\ 73199 &:= \left(\left(T\left((C(9, \sqrt{9}) - 1) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right) - 7 \right) \\ 73424 &:= \left(-\left(4^{T(T(2))} \right) + C\left(C\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})), 3\right), 7\right) \right) \\ 73425 &:= \left(\left(5 + C\left(T(T(T(2))), T(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) \times T((3 + 7)) \right) \\ 73464 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (C((T(6) + (4)), T(T(3))) - T(T(7))) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}73647 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \times (3 \times 7) \right) \\74186 &:= \left(- (T(6)) + \left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 1 \right), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (T(T(7))) \right) \right) \\74199 &:= \left(- (T((9 \times 9))) + C \left(\left(- (1) + T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right), 7 \right) \right) \\74207 &:= \left(C \left((T(7) - T(T(02))), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (T(T(7))) \right) \\74213 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T(T(3)) + 1), T(T(2)) \right) + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (T(T(7))) \right) \\74249 &:= \left(\left(C \left((9 \times \sqrt{4}), T(T(2)) \right) \times 4 \right) - (7) \right) \\74368 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(C \left(T(6), 3 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\74382 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} \times T(3) \right), 4 \right) \times 7 \right) \\74384 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + (C((8 \times 3), 4) \times 7) \right) \\74388 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + (C((8 \times 3), 4) \times 7) \right) \\74465 &:= \left(- (T(5)) + \left(C \left(T(6), T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (\sqrt{4} \times T(7)) \right) \right) \\74579 &:= \left(- \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(C \left((7 + T(5)), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (T(7)) \right) \right) \\74585 &:= \left(C \left(((T(5) - 8) + T(5)), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (T(7)) \right) \\74586 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(T(T(8)) \times \left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{4} \right) + (7) \right) \right) \right) \\74594 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{9} \right) \times (5^4) \right) - T(T(7)) \right) \\74612 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T(T(T(2))) + 1), 6 \right) + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - 7 \right) \\74613 &:= C \left((T(T(3)) + 1), \left((T(6) + \sqrt{4}) - (7) \right) \right) \\74614 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - \left(C \left((1 + T(6)), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + 7 \right) \right) \right) \\74615 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(C \left((1 + T(6)), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + 7 \right) \right) \\74618 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + 1 \right), 6 \right) - \left((\sqrt{4} - (7)) \right) \right) \\74619 &:= \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + C \left((1 + T(6)), T \left(- ((4 - 7)) \right) \right) \right) \\74622 &:= \left(\left(C(22, 6) + \sqrt{4} \right) + (7) \right) \\74627 &:= \left(C \left((T(7) - T(T(2))), 6 \right) + (\sqrt{4} \times 7) \right) \\74641 &:= \left(C \left(\left((1^4) + T(6) \right), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + (T(7)) \right) \\74679 &:= \left(C \left(- \left((T(\sqrt{9}) - T(7)) \right), 6 \right) + T((4 + 7)) \right) \\74746 &:= \left(C \left(T(6), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + (C(T(7), 4) + (7)) \right) \\74754 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - (T(T(5)) \times (T(C(7, 4)) - (7))) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}74844 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(4), \sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(\left(T(8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times T(7) \right) \\74898 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(T(8)) - 9 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{T(8)} - C(T(4), 7) \right) \right) \right) \\74913 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(T(3)) + 1 \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + T((-4) + T(7)) \right) \\74936 &:= \left(- (6) - \left(\left(- (T(T(3))) \times T \left(C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + T(7) \right) \right) \\74939 &:= \left(\left(T(C(9, 3)) \times T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - \left(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7) \right) \right) \\74941 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) + T(7) \right) \right) \\74949 &:= \left(T \left(\left(C(9, 4) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(T(T(4)) + T(7) \right) \right) \\74969 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(C(9, 6)) \times T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - 7 \right) \\74989 &:= \left(- (9) + \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + T(7) \right) \right) \\74991 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 + T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 7 \right) \\74992 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(2))) \times T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + T(7) \right) \\74994 &:= \left(- (4) + \left(\left(T \left(T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + T(7) \right) \right) \\74996 &:= \left(\left(T(6) \times T \left(C \left(9, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - T(7) \right) \right) \right) \\75279 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - C \left(T(7), T(2) \right) \right) \times \left(5 - T(7) \right) \right) \\75341 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\left(1 + T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right), T(3) \right) / 5 \right) - 7 \right) \\75379 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(C \left(T(7), T(3) \right) / 5 + T(7) \right) \right) \\75395 &:= - \left(\left(\left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T(3) \right) - \left(5^7 \right) \right) \right) \\75481 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\left(- (1) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right), T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times T(5) \right) + T(T(7)) \right) \\75496 &:= \left(\left(T(6) \times T \left(C \left(9, T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T(T(5)) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\75545 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(T(T(5)) \times \left(-T \left((5 \times 7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\75582 &:= C \left(\left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} + T(5) \right), \left(T(5) - (7) \right) \right) \\75597 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times T(T(5)) \right) - T \left(- \left((5 - 7) \right) \right) \right) \\75689 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-T \left(C(8, 6) \right) \right) \right) + \left(5^7 \right) \right) \\75964 &:= \left(\left(\left(4 - C \left(T(6), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) / (-5) \right) \times 7 \right) \\76134 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times T \left(T(T(3)) \right) \right) - C \left(\left(- (1) + T(6) \right), 7 \right) \right) \right) \\76194 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) + T(9) \right) \right) - C \left(\left(- (1) + T(6) \right), 7 \right) \right) \right) \\76328 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C(8, 2) \right) + \sqrt{T(3)^6} \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76435 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(T \left(C \left(T(3), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76544 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right), 5 \right) - T(T((6+7))) \right) \\
 76891 &:= \left(C \left(\left(1 + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(67) \right) \\
 76895 &:= \left(- \left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(6)) \right) - T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 76976 &:= - \left(\left((6 + T(7))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - C(T(6), 7) \right) \\
 77198 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), \sqrt{9} \right) + 1 \right) \times \left(T(T(7)) / 7 \right) \right) \\
 77234 &:= \left(- \left(T(T(4)) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(2)) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77244 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(2)) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \right) \\
 77245 &:= \left(- (5) \times T(T(4)) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(2)) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77267 &:= \left(- \left(T \left((T(7) - 6) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(2)) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77268 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(T(6)) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(2)) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77282 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2) \right), 7 \right) - 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 77292 &:= \left(T(2) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(2)) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77296 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T(6) \right) - \left(C \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), T(2) \right), 7 \right) + 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 77298 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T(8) \right) / \left(-\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(2)) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77345 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T \left(T(5) \right) + T \left(T(4) \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(3) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77349 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(3) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77373 &:= \left(T \left(T(3) \right) \times (-7) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(3) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77394 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(\sqrt{-T(3) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \right) \\
 77395 &:= \left(- \left(\left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(3) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77415 &:= -T(T(5) - 1) + C \left(\sqrt{-T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right) \\
 77443 &:= T \left(T \left(T(3) \right) \right) / \left(-T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + T(T(7))}, 7 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77454 &:= \left(- (T((-4) + T(5))) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77465 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{-5 + T(6)} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77478 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times (-7) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77482 &:= \left((-2) - T(8) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77485 &:= \left(C(T(5), 8) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) - (T(T(7))) \times T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 77486 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(C \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 7 \right) - T(7) \right) \right) \\
 77489 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{9}) + \left(C \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 7 \right) - T(7) \right) \right) \\
 77491 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(C \left(C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 7 \right) - T(7) \right) \right) \\
 77492 &:= \left(C \left(\left((2 + \sqrt{9}) \times 4 \right), 7 \right) - T(7) \right) \\
 77493 &:= \left(- ((3 \times 9)) + C \left(\sqrt{-T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77494 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(C \left(C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 7 \right) - T(7) \right) \right) \\
 77498 &:= \left(\sqrt{T(8)} + \left(C \left(C \left(T(\sqrt{9}), T(\sqrt{4}) \right), 7 \right) - T(7) \right) \right) \\
 77499 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - (C(((9 + 4) + 7), 7)) \right) \right) \\
 77514 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - C \left(\sqrt{-1 - 5 + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \right) \\
 77515 &:= \left(- (5) + C \left(\sqrt{-1 - 5 + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77554 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + (C((5 + T(5)), 7) + T(7)) \right) \\
 77645 &:= \left(\left(5^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-6 + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77646 &:= \left(\left(T(6) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-6 + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77655 &:= \left((T(T(5)) + (T(5))) + C \left(\sqrt{-6 + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77656 &:= \left(T((T(6) - (5))) + C \left(\sqrt{-6 + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77667 &:= \left((7 \times T(6)) + C \left(\sqrt{-6 + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right) \\
 77688 &:= \left(\left(8 \times T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) + C \left(\sqrt{-6 + T(T(7)), 7} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77723 &:= \left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(C\left(\sqrt{-T(T(2)) + T(T(7))}, 7\right) - (T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 77744 &:= \left(T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + \left(C\left(\sqrt{-T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(7))}, 7\right) - 7 \right) \right) \\
 77798 &:= \left((T(C(8, \sqrt{9})) \times (7 \times 7)) - T(T(7)) \right) \\
 77845 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{5^4}) + (C((-8) + T(7)), 7) \right) \\
 77918 &:= \left(-8 + \left(C\left((-1) + T(T(\sqrt{9}))\right), 7\right) + (T(T(7))) \right) \\
 77923 &:= \left(-3 + \left(C\left(C(T(T(2)), \sqrt{9}), 7\right) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 77926 &:= \left(C\left(C(T((6/2)), \sqrt{9}), 7\right) + T(T(7)) \right) \\
 77929 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(C\left(C(T(T(2)), \sqrt{9}), 7\right) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 77932 &:= \left((T(T(2)) + \left(C\left(C(T(3), \sqrt{9}), 7\right) \right)) + T(T(7)) \right) \\
 77947 &:= \left((T(T(7)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + C\left(\sqrt{-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(7))}, 7\right) \right) \\
 77952 &:= \left(\left((2^5) \times \sqrt{C(9, 7)} \right) \times T(T(7)) \right) \\
 77982 &:= \left(\left(2 \times T\left(T(\sqrt{T(8)})\right) \right) + C\left(\sqrt{-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(7))}, 7\right) \right) \\
 77985 &:= \left(T\left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right)\right) + C\left(\sqrt{-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(7))}, 7\right) \right) \\
 78126 &:= \left(C(6, T(T(2))) + \left(\left(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)} \right)^7 \right) \right) \\
 78135 &:= \left(C(5, 3) + \left(\left(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)} \right)^7 \right) \right) \\
 78184 &:= \left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8)) \right) + C\left(\left(-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right), 7\right) \right) \\
 78186 &:= \left(T\left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right)\right) + C\left(\left(-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right), 7\right) \right) \\
 78189 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T(T(8)) \right) + C\left(\left(-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right), 7\right) \right) \\
 78195 &:= \left((T(5) \times T(9)) + C\left(\left(-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right), 7\right) \right) \\
 78332 &:= \left(2 \times \left(C\left(C(T(3), 3), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) + T(T(7)) \right) \right) \\
 78399 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) + C\left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right), 7\right) \right) \\
 78441 &:= \left(C\left(\left(1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right)\right), T(T(\sqrt{4})) \right) + T(87)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78534 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(C \left(8, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78594 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(C \left(8, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78645 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) \times T \left(8 \right) \right) - \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 78729 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(T \left(2 \right)^7 \right) \times T \left(C \left(8, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78732 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T \left(2 \right) \times 3}^7 \right) \times T \left(C \left(8, 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 78734 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(- \left(\left(3^7 \right) \times T \left(C \left(8, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78738 &:= \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} - \left(- \left(\left(3^7 \right) \times T \left(C \left(8, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78791 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right)^7 \right) + T \left(T \left(C \left(8, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78855 &:= \left(T \left(5 \right) \times \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) - \left(T \left(8 \right) \times \left(-7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78925 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(5, 2 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) - \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) + T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78936 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) / 3 \right) \right), T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) / \left(8 + 7 \right) \right) \\
 79112 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times \sqrt{1 + C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 7 \right)} \\
 79137 &:= \left(\left(7 \times T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right), 7 \right) \right) \\
 79368 &:= \left(\left(8 \times T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right), 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 79394 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(4 \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 79593 &:= \left(- \left(3 \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-C \left(9, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79594 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-C \left(9, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79599 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) + C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) / T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 7 \right) \right) \\
 79786 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(6 \right) \times \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \times T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 79874 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), 7 \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 79892 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - T \left(7 \right) \right) \\
 79914 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(9, 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79948 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \times C \left(C \left(T \left(4 \right), 9 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T \left(7 \right) \right) \\
 80586 &:= \left(\left(C \left(6, \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) + T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(08 \right) \right) \right) \\
 81984 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) + \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 82329 &:= \left((T(9) \times T((T(2) \times C(T(3), T(2)))) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 82348 &:= \left(\left((C(8, T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(T(3))))^2 \right) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 82349 &:= \left((T(9) \times T((T(4) \times T(3)))) - C(T(T(2)), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 82434 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + (- (T(C(T(3), \sqrt{4}))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \right) \right) \\
 82435 &:= \left(- (5) - (- (T(C(T(3), \sqrt{4}))) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \right) \\
 82545 &:= \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) + (T(T(5)) \times (T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \right) \\
 82781 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times (- (C(T(7), T(2))) - T(T(8))) \right) \right) \\
 82784 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times (- (C(T(7), T(2))) - T(T(8))) \right) \right) \\
 82848 &:= \left(8 \times \left((C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), 8) / T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)))) \right) \right) \\
 83289 &:= \left((T(9) \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) + \left(C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \\
 83418 &:= \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times C(14, 3) \right) - (T(T(8))) \right) \\
 83489 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + \left(- \left(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(\sqrt{4})) \right) \times T(T((T(T(3)) - 8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 83545 &:= \left(T(C(5, \sqrt{4})) \times \left(T(T(C(5, 3))) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \\
 83586 &:= \left(((T(6) \times T(T(8))) - T(C(5, 3))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 83598 &:= \left(((T(T(8)) \times T(T(9))) / 5) - C(T(T(3)), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 83726 &:= \left((C(6, T(2)) \times T(T((7 + T(3)))) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 83728 &:= \left(\left(C(\sqrt{T(8)}, T(2)) \times T(T((7 + T(3)))) \right) + 8 \right) \\
 83835 &:= \left(T(C(C(5, 3), 8)) \times \sqrt{3^8} \right) \\
 83896 &:= \left(- (C(6, \sqrt{9})) + \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(3)) \right) \times T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 83936 &:= \left(C(6, 3) + \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(3)) \right) \times T(T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 83964 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{T(4)}^6 \times C(9, 3) \right) - T(8) \right) \\
 83969 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times C(T(6), 9) \right) - T(T(T(3))) \right) / T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 83994 &:= \left(\left((T(4)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times C(9, 3) \right) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 83995 &:= \left(T(5) - \left(\left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) \times (-T(3)) \right) / T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \\
 84357 &:= \left(C(T(7), 5) + \left(T(T(3)) \times \left(T(\sqrt{4}) - T(T(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84381 &:= \left(\left(T((1+T(8))) \times T(C(T(3), \sqrt{4})) \right) + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 84386 &:= \left(\left(T(T((T(6)-8))) \times C(T(3), T(\sqrt{4})) \right) + (T(T(8))) \right) \\
 84398 &:= \left(\left(C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times (-T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) \right) - (T(T(8))) \right) \\
 84427 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times (-2) + C(T(4), 4) \right) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 84485 &:= \left(-5 - \left(T(C(8, 4)) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - T(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84565 &:= \left(C(T(5), 6) - \left(T(T(5)) \times \left(T(\sqrt{4}) - T(T(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84579 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left((-7) - T(T(C(5, 4))) \right) \times T(T(8)) \right) \\
 84594 &:= \left(\left(C(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T((5+\sqrt{4}))) \right) - (T(T(8))) \right) \\
 84764 &:= - \left(\left(T((T(4)+T(6))) - \left(T(T(7)) \times C(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84822 &:= \left(C((T(T(T(2)))) - 2), 8) - \left(T(T(T(4))) \times \left(-\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 84843 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3))^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) + C((-T(8)) + T(T(4))), 8) \right) \\
 84889 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) + \left(8 \times \left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(\sqrt{4})) \times (-8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84928 &:= \left(\left(C(T(\sqrt{T(8)}), T(2)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4}^{\sqrt{T(8)}} \right) \right) \\
 84952 &:= \left(T(T(T(T(2)))) - \left(\left(T(T(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \times (-T(T(4))) \right) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \\
 84984 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) - C(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 4) \right) \times (-8) \right) \\
 84996 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(6), \sqrt{9}) + T(T(9)) \right) - 4 \right) \times T(8) \right) \\
 85246 &:= \left(C(T(6), T(\sqrt{4})) + ((T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \right) \\
 85272 &:= \left(T(2) \times \left(C((T(7) - T(T(2))), T(5)) / \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 85296 &:= \left(\left(T(C(6, \sqrt{9})) \times T(T((2+5))) \right) + T(8) \right) \\
 85322 &:= \left(C((2+T(T(T(2))))), T(3)) - \left(\left(5^{\sqrt{T(8)}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 85329 &:= \left(\left(T(\sqrt{C(9, 2)}) \times T((T(3) \times T(5))) \right) - T(T(8)) \right) \\
 85442 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(2))) - 4 \right) \times \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 85644 &:= \left(\left(T(4) \times C((T(\sqrt{4}) \times 6), 5) \right) - T(8) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 85885 &:= \left((T(T(5)) \times (8 + T(T(8)))) + C\left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 85934 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right), 3\right) + ((9 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8))) \right) \\
 85943 &:= \left(C\left(\left(T(T(3)) - \sqrt{4}\right), 9\right) - C(T(5), 8) \right) \\
 86142 &:= \left(T(T(T(2))) \times \left((C(4,1)^6) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 86267 &:= \left((T(7) \times T(T((6 \times 2)))) - C\left(6, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 86274 &:= \left(\left((C(T(4), 7)^2) - T(6) \right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 86295 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (T((2 \times T(6))) + T(T(8))) \right) \\
 86344 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(4)) - T(\sqrt{4}) \right)^3 \right) - C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 86349 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times (T(4) + T(T(3)))) + C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 86457 &:= \left((C(7,5) + (4^6)) \times T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 86526 &:= \left(((T(C(6,2)) \times T(T(5))) + (T(6))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 86604 &:= \left((T(T(T(4))) \times T(06)) + \left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) \\
 86649 &:= \left(T(9) - \left((T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(6))) - \left(C\left(T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86844 &:= - \left(\left(C\left(T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right), T(4)\right) + (T(T(8)) \times (6 - T(T(8)))) \right) \right) \\
 86919 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times C((1 \times 9), 6)) - T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 86929 &:= \left((C(9, T(2)) \times T(T(9))) - \left(T(T(6)) / T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) \\
 86934 &:= \left(((- (C(4,3)) \times T(T(9))) \times (-T(6))) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 86939 &:= \left((C(9,3) \times T(T(9))) - C\left(6, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 87227 &:= \left((C(T(7), 2) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T\left(\left(7 + \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) \\
 87279 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times (-T(7))) + \left(C\left(T(T(T(2))), 7\right) - T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) \\
 87344 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} + C(T(4), T(3))) \times \left(T(T(7)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 87346 &:= \left(\left(T(T(6)) \times T\left(\left(T(\sqrt{4})^3\right)\right) \right) + T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87395 &:= \left(- (C(T(5), 9)) + \left(T(T(T(3))) \times \left(T(T(7)) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 87654 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times C(T(5), 6) \right) - T(T(7)) \right) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 87757 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) - C(T(5), 7) \right) + \left(T(T(7)) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 87876 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(T(6), 7) \times T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) / T(7) \right) + (T(T(8))) \right) \\
 87926 &:= \left(C(6, T(2)) + \left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times T\left(T\left(\left(7 + \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 87927 &:= \left(T(C(7, 2)) - \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(7)) \right) \times (-T(8)) \right) \right) \\
 87934 &:= \left(\left(T(T((T(4) + 3))) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) + T\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) \\
 87945 &:= \left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + T((7 \times 8))\right) \right) \\
 88144 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) \times \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + 1 \right) \right) + \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) \\
 88425 &:= \left(- (T(5)) \times \left(- \left(\left(C(T(2), \sqrt{4})^8 \right) + T(T(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 88487 &:= \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times \left(8 + C\left(T(4), \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \right) - T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) \right) \\
 88648 &:= \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right), T(\sqrt{4})\right) - \left(- (T(T(6))) \times T\left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 88745 &:= \left(- \left(C(T(5), T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) - \left(\left(- (T(T(7))) \times T\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) + T(8) \right) \\
 88962 &:= \left(T(T(2)) - \left(- (T(6)) \times \left(T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) + (T(T(8))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89236 &:= \left(C(T(6), 3) + \left(T(T(T(2))) \times T\left(T\left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 8\right)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 89245 &:= \left(- (5) - \left((- (4) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 89325 &:= \left((5^2) \times \left(3 + T\left(C\left(9, \sqrt{T(8)}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 89373 &:= \left(\left((3 + T(7))^3 \right) \times \sqrt{C(9, 8)} \right) \\
 89484 &:= \left(4 \times \left(T(C(8, 4)) \times 9 + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 89494 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T(4))) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(T(T(4)) + \sqrt{C(9, 8)} \right) \right) \\
 89549 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(9)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) - T\left(T\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \right) \right) - T(8) \\
 89678 &:= \left(\left(\left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) + (T(T(7))) \right) \times T\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) + 8 \right) \\
 89734 &:= \left(\left((- (T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T\left(T\left(C\left(7, T\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \right) + 8 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 89748 &:= \left(\left(8 + T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T(8) \right) \\
 89774 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), 7 \right) \times 7 \right) / 9 \right) - \left(T \left(T(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89796 &:= \left(\left(\left(6 + T \left(T(9) \right) \right) + T(7) \right) \times C \left(9, \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \\
 89826 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(C \left(T(6), T(2) \right) \right) - T \left(T(8) \right) \right) \times \left(-T(9) \right) \right) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \\
 89828 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(2) \right) + \left(T \left(T(8) \right) \right) \right) \times T(9) \right) + 8 \right) \\
 89832 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T(2) \right) - \left(T \left(T(3) \right) \times T \left(\left(C \left(8, \sqrt{9} \right) + T(8) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89834 &:= \left(- (4) + \left(T \left(T(3) \right) \times T \left(\left(C \left(8, \sqrt{9} \right) + T(8) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89838 &:= \left(T \left(\left(T(8) / T(3) \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(C \left(8, \sqrt{9} \right) + T(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89938 &:= \left(C \left(8, T(3) \right) - \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(9) \right) \right) \times T \left(T(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89949 &:= \left(\left(T(9)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right) - T \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + T \left(C(9, 8) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 91146 &:= \left(T(6) + \left(C \left(T(4), (1+1) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 91245 &:= \left(T \left(T(5) \right) + \left(C \left(T(4), 2 \right)^{\sqrt{1 \times 9}} \right) \right) \\
 91343 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T(3) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right), T \left((3+1) \right) \right) - T \left(T(9) \right) \right) \\
 91497 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 91728 &:= \left(C(8, 2) \times C \left(T(7), \sqrt{1 \times 9} \right) \right) \\
 91747 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(7) \right) + 19 \right) \\
 91938 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(3) \right) + \left(T(91) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 92294 &:= \left(\left(- (4) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) \right) \\
 92343 &:= - \sqrt{T \left(-T(3) + T \left(T(4) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(T(3) \right) - 2, 9 \right)} \\
 92344 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T(4) \right) - C \left(\left(T \left(T(3) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 92347 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T(7) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + C \left(\left(T \left(T(3) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) \right) \\
 92348 &:= \left(\left(- \left(T(8) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(\left(T \left(T(3) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) \right) \\
 92373 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{-3 + T(7)} - C \left(\left(T \left(T(3) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 92379 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - (7) \right) - C \left(\left(T \left(T(3) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 92381 &:= \left(\sqrt{1+8} + C \left(\left(T \left(T(3) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) \right) \\
 92382 &:= \left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} + C \left(\left(T \left(T(3) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92384 &:= \left(C \left((T(T(4)) - T(8)), (3^2) \right) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 92388 &:= \left(T(\sqrt{8+8}) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9) \right) \\ 92389 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} + 8) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9) \right) \\ 92396 &:= \left((T(6) - \sqrt{9}) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9) \right) \\ 92398 &:= \left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9) \right) \\ 92399 &:= \left(T((9 - \sqrt{9})) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9) \right) \\ 92434 &:= \left((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))) + (C(T(4), 2)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\ 92447 &:= \left((T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - ((C(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(2)) + 9)) \right) \\ 92456 &:= \left((T(T(6)) \times T(T(5 + \sqrt{4}))) - C(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 92463 &:= \left(3 \times (T(6) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-C(T(T(2)), \sqrt{9})))) \right) \\ 92483 &:= \left(T((T(3) + 8)) + C((- (\sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(2)))) , 9) \right) \\ 92498 &:= \left(T(T((8 - \sqrt{9}))) + C((- (\sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(2)))) , 9) \right) \\ 92545 &:= \left(- (5) \times (T(T(4)) - C((T(5) + T(2)), T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\ 92568 &:= \left(T(C(8,6)) \times ((T(5)^2) + \sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 92576 &:= \left(((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T(5))) - C(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 92595 &:= \left(5 \times (C((\sqrt{9} + T(5)), T(T(2))) - T(9)) \right) \\ 92609 &:= \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + C((T(06) - 2), 9) \right) \\ 92687 &:= \left((T(T(7)) \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) - (- (T(T(6))) + C(T(T(T(2))), \sqrt{9})) \right) \\ 92815 &:= \left(- (5) \times (1 - C((T(8)/2), T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\ 92835 &:= \left(5 \times (C((3 \times \sqrt{T(8)}), T(T(2))) + \sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 92843 &:= \left((T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times (T(C(8,2)) + \sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 92874 &:= \left(T((T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7))) + C((T(\sqrt{T(8)}) - 2), 9) \right) \\ 92892 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(T(\sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{T(8)}} \right) - T(C(T(T(2)), \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\ 92925 &:= \left((- (T(5)) + T((2^{\sqrt{C(9,2)}}))) \times T(9) \right) \\ 92987 &:= \left((T(7) \times T((T(8) + T(9)))) - C(T(2), \sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 93024 &:= \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times C(20, (T(3) + 9)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 93079 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(70 \times C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 93278 &:= \left(\left(T \left(8 \right) \times T \left(72 \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 93292 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right)^{T \left(\sqrt{9} \right)} \right) \times 2 \right) - C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 93294 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(C \left(9, 2 \right)^3 \right) - 9 \right) \right) \\
 93332 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left(T \left(3 \right)^{T \left(3 \right)} \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 93387 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \times C \left(T \left(3 \right), 3 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 93434 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right), T \left(4 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 93545 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - \left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times T \left(39 \right) \right) \right) \\
 93725 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(C \left(5, 2 \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 93747 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) - 39 \\
 93763 &:= \left(- \left(3 \right) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 93766 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(T \left(6 \right) + \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 93769 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 93778 &:= \left(- \left(8 \right) + \left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(\left(C \left(7, T \left(3 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 93785 &:= \left(\left(T \left(- \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) - T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) - C \left(3, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 93794 &:= \sqrt{C \left(4, \text{sqrt}9 \right)} + T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \\
 93795 &:= \left(\left(\left(5 \sqrt{C \left(9, 7 \right)} \right) \times T \left(3 \right) \right) + T \left(9 \right) \right) \\
 93796 &:= \left(C \left(6, T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) + 9 \right) \right) \\
 93827 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) + C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 93887 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) + \left(C \left(8, 3 \right) + T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 93888 &:= \left(T \left(8 \right) \times \left(T \left(\left(T \left(8 \right) + T \left(8 \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 93987 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) + \left(- \left(9 \right) + T \left(C \left(T \left(3 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 94157 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) - \left(- \left(C \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) - 1 \right), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 94217 &:= \left(71 \times \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right), T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 94282 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(C \left(8, 2 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\left(T \left(4 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 94353 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \times \left(C \left(T \left(5 \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4^9} \right) \right) \\
 94383 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) - 8 \right), T \left(3 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(4 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 94386 &:= \left((C((T(6) - 8), T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 94394 &:= \left(T\left(\left(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) + C\left((T(T(3)) - \sqrt{4}), 9 \right) \right) \\
 94398 &:= \left(\left(T(T(8)) - \left(-C(T(\sqrt{9}), 3) \right) \times T(T(T(4))) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 94416 &:= \left(T(T(6)) + \left(C(14, \sqrt{4}) \times T(T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 94435 &:= \left(T(C(5, 3)) \times \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T\left((T(T(4)) + \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 94448 &:= \left(C((-T(8)) + T(T(4)), T(4)) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times T(T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 94482 &:= \left(2 \times \left(T(T(8)) - \left(T(C(T(4), \sqrt{4})) \times (-T(9)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 94488 &:= \left(\left(T(8) \times T\left((T(8) \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - \left(C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 94494 &:= \left(\left((T(4) \times T(9)) \times C(T(4), 4) \right) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 94495 &:= \left(-5 - \left(-((T(9) \times T(4))) \times C(T(4), T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 94589 &:= \left(T\left(T\left((\sqrt{9} + 8) \right) \right) + C((T(5) + 4), 9) \right) \\
 94642 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left(T(T(\sqrt{4}))^6 \right) \right) + C\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 94821 &:= \left(\left(T(T(T((1+2)))) \times T(C(8, \sqrt{4})) \right) + T(T(9)) \right) \\
 94829 &:= \left(\left(\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 2 \right) \times T(C(8, \sqrt{4})) \right) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 94848 &:= \left(T\left((T(8) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \times \left(8 + C(T(4), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 94864 &:= (T(4 \times 6) + 8) \sqrt{C(4, \sqrt{9})} \\
 94883 &:= \left((T(T(T(3))) + 8) \times \left(T(C(8, \sqrt{4})) - 9 \right) \right) \\
 94959 &:= \left((9^5) + \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 4) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 94976 &:= \left((T(T(6)) \times T(T(7))) + \left(T(C(9, T(\sqrt{4}))) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 94983 &:= \left(\left(-((C(T(T(3)), 8) + T(9)) \times T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \right) / (-T(9)) \right) \\
 95373 &:= \left(-((T(T(3)) - (T(T(7)) \times C(T(T(3)), T(5)))) / T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) \right) \\
 95424 &:= \left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times \left(-\left(T(T(2)) - \left(T(4) \times C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 95544 &:= -\left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) - \left(T((4 \times 5)) \times C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 95545 &:= \left(-5 + \left(T((4 \times 5)) \times C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 95595 &:= \left(\left(C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \times T((5 + T(5))) \right) + T(9) \right) \\
 95627 &:= \left(\left((T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) \times T(T(6)) \right) + \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 95757 &:= \left((C(T(7), T(5)) / (T(T(7)) - T(5))) - \sqrt{9} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 95774 &:= \left(- \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(4 \right) \times 7 \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(7 \right), 5 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 95785 &:= \left(\left(5^8 \right) - \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), 5 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 95865 &:= \left(T \left(5 \right) \times \left(\left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) + C \left(T \left(5 \right), 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 95899 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(9 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T \left(8 \right)} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(5 \right), 9 \right) \right) \\
 95942 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(5 \right), 9 \right) \right) \\
 96222 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(\left(2^{T \left(2 \right)} \right), 2 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 96249 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(4 \right), T \left(2 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 96573 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(5 \right), 6 \right) \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 96628 &:= \left(T \left(C \left(8, 2 \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) + \left(T \left(6 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 96699 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) + T \left(C \left(9, 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times T \left(6 \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 96888 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) \times \left(8 \times 8 \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(6 \right), T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 96974 &:= \left(\left(\left(4^7 \right) \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(6 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 96999 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \times T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97245 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right), - \left(2 - 7 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 97255 &:= \left(5 \times \left(C \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) + 2 \right), 7 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97345 &:= \left(5 \times \left(C \left(\left(- \left(4 \right) + T \left(T \left(3 \right) \right) \right), 7 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97364 &:= \left(\left(46^3 \right) + T \left(C \left(7, T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97377 &:= \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), \sqrt{T \left(7 \right) - 3} \right) - T \left(\left(7 \times T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97475 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(T \left(5 \right) \right) \times T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97476 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(6 \right) \right) + \left(C \left(T \left(7 \right), - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97539 &:= \left(\left(\left(T \left(9 \right)^3 \right) + C \left(T \left(5 \right), 7 \right) \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97554 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(5 \right) \times C \left(T \left(5 \right), 7 \right) \right) + T \left(T \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97559 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 5 \right) \times 5 \right) - T \left(T \left(\left(7 + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97574 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(7 \right), 5 \right) \right) + T \left(\left(T \left(7 \right) + 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 97674 &:= \left(\left(\left(4^7 \right) \times 6 \right) - T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97728 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(8 \right) \right) - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(T \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(T \left(7 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97752 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(\left(2^5 \right) \right) \right) + C \left(T \left(7 \right), \sqrt{T \left(7 \right) - \sqrt{9}} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 97784 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(\left(T(4) + T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - \left(C \left(T(7), \sqrt{T(7) - \sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97854 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + T \left(T(5) \right) \right) \times \left(T \left(T(8) \right) + T \left(C \left(7, T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97867 &:= \left(\left((7 \times T(6)) \times T \left(T(8) \right) \right) - C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97884 &:= \left(\left(T \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times T(8) \right) \right) \times T(8) \right) + \left(C \left(T(7), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97924 &:= \left(- \left(T \left(T(4) \right) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T(2) \right) \right), 9 \right) + 7 \right) / \left(-\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97944 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T(4) \right) \right) / \left(-T(4) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + T \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97947 &:= \left(\left(\left(-7 \right) \times T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-T \left(C \left(9, 7 \right) \right) \right) + T(9) \right) \\
 97964 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T(4) - \left(C \left(T(6), 9 \right) - T(7) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97982 &:= \left(T(2) + \left(\left(C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), 9 \right) + 7 \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97986 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(6), \left(T(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + T(7) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97992 &:= \left(T \left(T(2) \right) - \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 9 \right) + T(7) \right) / \left(-\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97993 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(T \left(T(3) \right), 9 \right) + T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + T(7) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97994 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right), 9 \right) + T(9) + T(7) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97998 &:= \left(\left(T(8) + \left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 9 \right) + T(7) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98057 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), 5 \right) + 08 \right) - T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 98157 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), 5 \right) - T \left(T \left(\left(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98199 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 9 \right) + \left(1 + T \left(T(8) \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98247 &:= \left(C \left(T(7), \left(\sqrt{4} + T(2) \right) \right) - \left(T(8) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 98252 &:= \left(\left((2 \times T \left(T(5) \right)) + 2 \right) \times T \left(C \left(8, T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 98265 &:= \left(- \left(T(5) \right) + C \left(T \left(T(6) / T(2) \right), \left(8 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 98267 &:= \left(\left(C \left(T(7), \left(T(6) + 2 \right) \right) + 8 \right) - T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 98272 &:= \left(- \left(2 \right) + \left(C \left(T(7), - \left(T(2) - 8 \right) \right) - T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 98275 &:= \left(- \left(5 \right) + C \left(T(7), \sqrt{2 \times 8 + 9} \right) \right) \\
 98277 &:= \left(C \left(T(7), \left(7 + \left(2 \times 8 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98278 &:= \left(- \left(8 \right) + \left(C \left(T(7), - \left(T(2) - 8 \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 98295 &:= \left(T(5) + C \left(T \left(9 - 2 \right), \left(8 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 98297 &:= \left(C \left(T(7), \left(\sqrt{9} + 2 \right) \right) + \left(8 + 9 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98357 &:= \left((C(T(7), 5) + T(T(3))) + (C(8, \sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 98399 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + (C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 3) \times (T(T(8)) / (-9))) \right) \right) \\
 98435 &:= \left(T(5) + \left((C(T(T(3)), T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(8))) / 9 \right) \right) \\
 98457 &:= \left((C(T(7), 5) + T((T(4) + 8))) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98468 &:= \left((8 + T(T(6))) \times \left(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(C(8, T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \\
 98492 &:= \left(\left((C(T(T(T(2))), 9) + T(T(T(4)))) + \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98514 &:= \left(\left(C(T((T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 1)), 5) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98517 &:= \left(\left(C(T(7), (1 \times 5)) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \right) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98519 &:= \left((C(T((T(\sqrt{9}) + 1)), 5) + 8) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 98575 &:= \left((-5) + C(T(7), 5) + T(8 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98595 &:= \left((T(T(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) + (-T(5) + T(T(8)))) \times T(9) \right) \\
 98628 &:= \left(\left((T(C(8, 2)) + T(6)) \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \right) - 9 \right) \\
 98634 &:= \left(- \left(T(\sqrt{4}) \right) - \left(T(T(T(3))) \times \left(-T(6) - T(C(8, T(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 98648 &:= \left(8 \times \left(C((-4) + T(6), \sqrt{T(8)}) - T(9) \right) \right) \\
 98649 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(\sqrt{9})) + \left(C(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^6}, \sqrt{T(8)}) / (-\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 98663 &:= \left(\left(T(T(3)) - C((T(6) + (6)), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) / (-\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98665 &:= \left(-5 + \left(C((T(6) + (6)), \sqrt{T(8)}) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 98668 &:= \left(\left(C(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(6) \right), T(6)) - \sqrt{T(8)} \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98669 &:= \left(\left(-\sqrt{9} + C((T(6) + (6)), \sqrt{T(8)}) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98735 &:= \left(C(T(5), 3) + C(T(7), (8 - \sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 98744 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\left(T(\sqrt{4})^{T(\sqrt{4})} \right), 7 \right) + T(T(8)) \right) / 9 \right) \\
 98745 &:= \left(T((T(5) \times \sqrt{4})) + (C(T(7), (8 - \sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 98769 &:= \left(C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 6) + ((7 + T(8)) \times T(T(9))) \right) \\
 98778 &:= \left((T(8) + (C(T(7), 7) / T(8))) \times \sqrt{9} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98785 &:= \left(C \left(T(5), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + \left(\left(T(T(7)) \times T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) \right) \right) - T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98792 &:= \left((2^9) + C \left(T(7), (8 - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98799 &:= \left((T(T(9)) \times 97) - T \left(C(8, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98835 &:= \left(- (T(5)) \times \left(- \left((3^8) \right) - C(8, T(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 98838 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, 3 \right) - T(T(8)) \right) \times (-T((8+9))) \right) \\
 98892 &:= \left(\left(C \left((T(2) \times 9), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) + T(T(8)) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98924 &:= \left((T(T(T(4))) \times 29) + C \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98949 &:= \left(C \left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) + \sqrt{4}), T(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (T(T(8)) \times (-\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 98952 &:= - \left((T(2) - T(59)) \times C(8, \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98995 &:= \left(- (5) - \left(- (T(99)) \times C \left(\sqrt{T(8)}, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 98997 &:= \left((T(7) \times (T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) - T(8))) + T(9) \right) \\
 99371 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(T(7) \times (T(T(3)) - T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \\
 99374 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(T(7) \times (T(T(3)) - T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \\
 99428 &:= - \left(\left(\left(T \left(\sqrt{T(8)} \right) + (T(T(T(2)))^4) \right) - C(T(T(\sqrt{9})), 9) \right) \right) \\
 99465 &:= \left(5 \times \left(C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) + (\sqrt{9}^9) \right) \right) \\
 99492 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left((T(2) + 9), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(9) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 99496 &:= \left(C(6, T(\sqrt{9})) + \left(T \left(T \left((\sqrt{4} + 9) \right) \right) \times T(9) \right) \right) \\
 99498 &:= \left(\left(T \left(C \left((T(8) / \sqrt{9}), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times T(9) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 99552 &:= \left((- (2) - T(T(5))) \times \left(-C \left((T(5) + \sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 99554 &:= \left((T(4)^5) - \left(C(T(5), \sqrt{9}) - 9 \right) \right) \\
 99585 &:= \left(C(T(5), 8) - \left((- (T(5)) \times T(T(9))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 99595 &:= \left(\left(C(5, \sqrt{9})^5 \right) - (9 \times T(9)) \right) \\
 99645 &:= \left(C(T(5), T(\sqrt{4})) \times \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 99657 &:= \left(C(T(7), 5) + \left((T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{9})) - 9 \right) \right) \\
 99723 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(T(3))) + \left(T(T(2)) - \left(T(7) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 99729 &:= \left((T(C(9, T(2))) \times T(7)) - T \left(T \left((9 - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99732 &:= \left((T(2) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(7) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 99738 &:= \left((T(T(8)) / (-3)) + (T(7) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 99759 &:= \left((T((-T(9)) + T(T(5)))) \times C(7, \sqrt{9}) + 9 \right) \\
 99764 &:= \left(T\left(\sqrt{T(T(4)) - 6}\right) \times (-7 + T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 99774 &:= \left(T(4) - (T(7) \times (7 - T(C(9, \sqrt{9})))) \right) \\
 99793 &:= \left((T(T(3)) \times T(97)) - C(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 99795 &:= - \left((T(T(5)) + T(9)) - (T(7) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 99874 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{4}) - (-T(T(7))) \times (T(8) + T(C(T(\sqrt{9}), \sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 99912 &:= \left(C\left(\left(2 + T\left(T(\sqrt{1 \times 9})\right)\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) - T(T(9)) \right) \\
 99939 &:= - \left((T(T(\sqrt{9})) + (T((T(T(3)) / \sqrt{9})) \times (-T(C(9, \sqrt{9})))) \right) \\
 99948 &:= \left(T(8) + \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + T\left(T(\sqrt{9})\right)\right), T(\sqrt{9})\right) - T(T(9)) \right) \right) \\
 99957 &:= \left(\left(C\left(T(7) - (5), T(\sqrt{9})\right) + T(9) \right) - T(T(9)) \right) \\
 99972 &:= \left(T(T(2)) + \left((T(7) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) + T(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 99977 &:= \left(-T(7) + \left((T(7) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9}))) + T(9) \right) \right) \\
 99978 &:= \left(T\left(\sqrt{T(8)}\right) - \left((-T(7)) \times T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers** [2, 3, 4]. Friedmann [6, 7] also made some study in this direction. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Following subsections give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers are with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **Quadratic numbers**, **Cubic numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing **selfie numbers** is by use of **permutable powers**, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

3.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfie numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &:= 1^1 & 3529 &:= -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2 \\
 23 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 & 4316 &:= 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3 \\
 1239 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & 4355 &:= 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5 \\
 1364 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 & 39339 &:= -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3 \\
 1654 &:= -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5 & 46350 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4 \\
 1837 &:= 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 & 46360 &:= 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6 \\
 2137 &:= -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2 & 397612 &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3 \\
 2173 &:= -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7 & 423858 &:= 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5 \\
 2537 &:= 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 & 637395 &:= 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7 \\
 3125 &:= -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5 & 758014 &:= 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8 \\
 3275 &:= -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 & 778530 &:= 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8 \\
 3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 & 804637 &:= 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15647982 &:= 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6 \\
 17946238 &:= 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7 \\
 57396108 &:= -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8 \\
 134287690 &:= 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1 \\
 387945261 &:= 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5 \\
 392876054 &:= 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\
 392876540 &:= -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2
 \end{aligned}$$

More details can be seen in author's work [20].

3.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$$\begin{aligned}
 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 14641 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 &= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \\
 15552 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 16377 &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8 - 2)^{3+3}/2 \\
 116565 &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) &= 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 131072 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned}
 656250 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656251 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656252 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 2 = 2 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656253 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 3 = 3 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656254 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 4 = 4 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656255 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 5 = 5 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656256 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 6 = 6 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656257 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 7 = 7 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656258 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 8 = 8 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656259 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 9 = 9 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

The past work up to 6 digits numbers can be seen in [14, 15, 16, 30].

3.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\
 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\
 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\
 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned}
 35280 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35281 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35282 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35283 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35284 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35285 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35286 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35287 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35288 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35289 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!. \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [26, 27].

3.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$	$1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1}$
$19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$	$1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9}+2-1}$
$19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$	$2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$
$19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$	$3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$
$839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$	$9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9}$
$839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$	$12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$
$839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$	$19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$
$839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$	$42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$
$995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$	$59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 0 + 9^5$
$999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$	$999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$
$999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [14, 15].

3.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in **digit's order** and its reverse

$$\begin{aligned} 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\ 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} &= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\ 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\ 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\ 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\ 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7}. \\ 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 &= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5040 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5041 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5042 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5043 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5044 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5045 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5046 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5047 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5048 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5049 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!
 \end{aligned}$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$120 := ((1 + 2)! - 0)!;$	$25 := 5^2$
$127 := -1 + 2^7$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$1673 := -1 - 6 + 7!/3$	$289 := (9 + 8)^2$
$1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9}$	$3894 := (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}) \times 3$
$1680 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!}$	$4957 := 7! - 59 - 4!$
$38970 := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70$	$6992 := 2^9 + 9 \times 6!$
$38986 := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6}$	$26493 := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3$
$40310 := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10$	$30792 := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92)$
$90894 := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!)/4$	$54476 := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6$
$91560 := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!)$	$75989 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!) + 5^7$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [14, 15, 16].

3.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 143 &:= -1 + F(4 \times 3) &= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 986 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) &= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11) \\
 2585 &:= F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) &= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\
 12819 &:= 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9) &= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1 \\
 24297 &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) &= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2) \\
 39394 &:= -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)} &= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\
 74997 &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) &= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7 \\
 87937 &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) &= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \\
 98703 &:= 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) &= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34 &:= F(3 \times F(4)) & 36 &:= 6^{F(3)} \\
 233 &:= F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3)) & 143 &:= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 630 &:= F(F(6)) \times 30 & 231 &:= F(13) - 2 \\
 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) & 377 &:= F(-7 + 7 \times 3) \\
 2079 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 & 986 &:= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 4864 &:= F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) & 1165 &:= 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1)) \\
 8759 &:= -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8)) & 1596 &:= F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1))) \\
 8849 &:= -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8)) + F(F(8)) & 2592 &:= F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2)) \\
 9349 &:= -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9))) & 9756 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 834660 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834661 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834662 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834663 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834664 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834665 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834666 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834667 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834668 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834669 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21960 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21961 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21962 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21963 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21964 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21965 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21966 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21967 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21968 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$21969 := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2.$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [23, 24].

3.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

$1069 := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$	$874 := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$
$1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$	$0105 := 50 + T(10)$
$2887 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$	$1155 := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$
$4965 := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$	$1224 := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$
$4999 := 49 + T(99)$	$2418 := T(81) - T(42)$
$99545 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$	$99632 := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$
$99546 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6.$	$99633 := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 2210 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2211 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2212 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2213 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2214 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2215 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2216 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2217 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2218 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2219 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))).
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details see author's work [21, 31].

3.8 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways**, **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 6435 &:= C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\ 15504 &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ 54264 &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4 + 5})!) \\ 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!). \end{aligned}$$

$12650 := C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!)$	$28 := C(8, 2)$
$12870 := C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!)$	$792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7)$
$14950 := C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!)$	$924 := C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!)$
$18564 := C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!)$	$2024 := C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!)$
$19448 := C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8)$	$4845 := C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4)$
$26334 := C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4})$	$00378 := C(C(8, \sqrt{7 - 3}), 0! + 0!)$
$43758 := C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8)$	$00792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!)$
$53130 := C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!).$	$00924 := C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)).$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$25920 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0$	$98280 := 0 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$
$25921 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1$	$98281 := 1 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$
$25922 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2$	$98282 := 2 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$
$25923 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3$	$98283 := 3 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$
$25924 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4$	$98284 := 4 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$
$25925 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5$	$98285 := 5 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$
$25926 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6$	$98286 := 6 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$
$25927 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7$	$98287 := 7 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$
$25928 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8$	$98288 := 8 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9})$
$25929 := (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9.$	$98289 := 9 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}).$

For more details refer author's work [22].

3.9 Binomial Coefficients and Triangular Numbers

Below are some examples of selfie numbers written by use of **binomial coefficients** and **triangular numbers** together.

$231 := T(T(C(2 \times 3, 1)))$	$286 := C(T(6) - 8, T(2))$
$241 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(C(4, 1))$	$0139 := C(9, 3) + T(10)$
$1535 := T(T(C(1 \times 5, 3))) - 5$	$1588 := -8 + T(C(8, 5) \times 1)$
$1561 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(C(6, 1))$	$5026 := C(T(5), T(T(02))) + T(6)$
$2922 := -T(2) + C(T(2) \times 9, T(2))$	$01754 := C(T(4), 5) \times 7 - 10$
$12256 := -T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + C(2 + T(5), 6)$	$01755 := T(5) \times C(T(5), 7) / T(10)$
$12339 := (C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), 3) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 9$	$13992 := T(T(2)) + T(T(9) - 9) \times T(T(C(3, 1)))$
$17432 := C(17, T(4)) - T(T(T(3)) \times T(2))$	$17155 := 5 \times (C(T(5) - 1, 7) - 1)$
$18647 := C(18, 6) + T(T(4)) + T(7)$	$22718 := T(8) \times (1 + T(C(7, T(2)))) + 2$
$28593 := (T(T(2)) \times T(C(8, 5)) - T(9)) \times 3$	$26943 := (C(T(T(3)), 4) \times 9 + T(6)) / 2$
$62397 := T(T(T(6)) / T(2)) \times T(T(3)) - T(C(9, 7))$	$46512 := C(T(T(T(2))) - 1, 5) \times T(6 - 4)$
$98752 := T(T(9) - 8) + C(T(7), 5) - T(T(T(T(2))))$	$52946 := T(T(6)) - T(T(T(4))) - 9 + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
$99315 := T(T(9)) + C(9 \times 3 + 1, 5)$	$53484 := -T(4) \times T(8 + 4) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$
$99945 := -T(C(9, 9) + 9) + T(4)^5$	$98317 := C(T(7), -1 + T(3)) - 8 + T(9)$

First column values are in digit's order and second column values are in reverse order of digits. Below are symmetric blocks of values in digit's order and reverse order of digit's.

$21420 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 0 = 0 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21421 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 1 = 1 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21422 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 2 = 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21423 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 3 = 3 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21424 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 4 = 4 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21425 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 5 = 5 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21426 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 6 = 6 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21427 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 7 = 7 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21428 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 8 = 8 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21429 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 9 = 9 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$

For more details refer author's work [34].

3.10 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\
 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\
 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\
 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\
 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 49548 &:= -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\
 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 50424 &:= 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\
 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & 52895 &:= (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\
 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}. & 53995 &:= (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 86640 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0 & 5640 &:= 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86641 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1 & 5641 &:= 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86642 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2 & 5642 &:= 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86643 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3 & 5643 &:= 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86644 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4 & 5644 &:= 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86645 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5 & 5645 &:= 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86646 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6 & 5646 &:= 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86647 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7 & 5647 &:= 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86648 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8 & 5648 &:= 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86649 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9. & 5649 &:= 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

3.11 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 2883 &:= K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3 & 00938 &:= K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!) \\
 2888 &:= K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8 & 01051 &:= K(15, 010) \\
 3640 &:= K(3!, 6) \times 40 & 01199 &:= K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10) \\
 14939 &:= -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9 & 59938 &:= K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5 \\
 14959 &:= (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9 & 62424 &:= 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6) \\
 15144 &:= K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4! & 63384 &:= 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6! \\
 15347 &:= (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7) & 63744 &:= 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!) \\
 15399 &:= K(1 \times 5!/3!, 9) \times 9 & 63973 &:= K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6).
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 99360 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99361 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99362 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99363 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99364 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99365 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99366 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99367 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99368 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99369 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

3.12 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, \quad n > 0, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$48 := -Q(4) + Q(8)$	$49 := Q(-9 + Q(4))$
$81 := Q(8 + 1)$	$89 := Q(9) + 8$
$128 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$	$224 := (Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2))$
$292 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$	$275 := Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$
$322 := Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2$	$736 := Q(Q(6) - Q(3)) + 7$
$1036 := 10^3 + Q(6)$	$0107 := 7 + Q(010)$
$1125 := Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$	$0231 := -Q(13) + Q(20)$
$1729 := 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$	$1257 := 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$
$9843 := (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3$	$2239 := -Q(9) + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2))$
$10025 := 100^2 + Q(5)$	$08136 := Q(6) + Q(Q(3) + 1 + 80)$
$10384 := (-1 + Q(Q(03))) \times 8 \times Q(4)$	$99712 := Q(Q(2)) \times 1 \times (Q(79) - 9)$
$99378 := 9 \times (Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8$	$37293 := -3 + (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3).$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 12680 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12681 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12682 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12683 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12684 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12685 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12686 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12687 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12688 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12689 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

3.13 Cubic-Type Selfies

The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$U(n) := n^3, n > 0, n \in \mathbf{N}.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **cubic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$125 := 1^2 \times U(5)$ $522 := 5 \times 2 + U(U(2))$ $991 := -9 + U(9 + 1)$ $1371 := (1 + 3) \times U(7) - 1$ $1715 := 1 \times U(7) \times 1 \times 5$ $2587 := -U(2) + 5 \times (U(8) + 7)$ $9945 := U(9) + 9 \times 4^5$ $10125 := (10 - 1)^2 \times U(5)$ $16444 := U(16) \times 4 + U(4) - 4$ $30375 := U(30) + U(3 + 7 + 5)$ $99873 := U(9) \times (9 + U(8)/(7 - 3))$	$512 := U(2 + 1 + 5)$ $991 := (U(1 + 9) - 9)$ $0235 := 5 \times (U(3) + 20)$ $0263 := U(3) + U(6) + 20$ $1735 := 5 \times (3 + U(7) + 1)$ $5974 := -4 + 7 \times (U(9) + U(5))$ $00157 := -U(7) + 5 \times 100$ $01928 := 8 \times (U(U(2)) + U(9) - U(10))$ $45194 := -4 + U(9) \times (1 + U(5) - U(4))$ $99535 := 5 \times (U(U(3)) + U(5) + 99)$
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First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$22950 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

$$22951 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

$$22952 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

$$22953 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

$$22954 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

$$22955 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

$$22956 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

$$22957 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

$$22958 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

$$22959 := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2)))$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

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